

**KWAME NKRUMAH UNIVERSITY OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY,
KUMASI
COLLEGE OF AGRICULTURE AND NATURAL RESOURCES
FACULTY OF AGRICULTURE
DEPARTMENT OF CROP AND SOIL SCIENCES**

**ASSESSMENT OF GENETIC DIVERSITY AND AGRONOMIC
PERFORMANCE OF FONIO (*Digitaria exilis* (Kippist) Stapf) ACCESSIONS
IN GHANA**

RICHARD YAW AGYARE

FEBRUARY, 2025

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IN GHANA**

RICHARD YAW AGYARE

(BSc. AGRICULTURE; MSc. AGRONOMY (PLANT BREEDING))

**A THESIS SUBMITTED TO THE DEPARTMENT OF CROP AND SOIL
SCIENCES, KWAME NKRUMAH UNIVERSITY OF SCIENCE AND
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REQUIREMENTS FOR THE AWARD DEGREE OF**

DOCTOR OF PHILOSOPHY IN PLANT BREEDING

FEBRUARY, 2025

DECLARATION

I hereby declare that this submission is my own work and that, to the best of my knowledge and belief, it contains no material previously published or written by another person nor material which to a substantial extent has been accepted for the award of any other degree or diploma at Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology, Kumasi or any other educational institution, except where due acknowledgment is made in the thesis

RICHARD YAW AGYARE
(Student ID, 20785044)	Signature Date

Certified by:

PROF. RICHARD AKROMAH
(Supervisor)	Signature Date

DR. ALEXANDER WIREKO KENA
(Supervisor)	Signature Date

DR. JOSEPH ADJEBENG-DANQUAH
(Supervisor)	Signature Date

DR. ADELIN BARNAUD
(Supervisor)	Signature Date

DR. CLAIRE BILLOT
(Supervisor)	Signature Date

PROF. VINCENT LOGAH
(Head of Department)	Signature Date

ABSTRACT

Fonio (*Digitaria exilis* (Kippist) Stapf), a vital cereal in West Africa, can mitigate food and nutrition insecurity under climate change but remains under-researched. In Ghana, limited information exists on the genetic diversity and agronomic performance of fonio accessions, with farmers relying on unimproved landraces that result in low yields. This study was undertaken to identify fonio accessions with superior agronomic properties for cultivation and crop improvement. Specifically, it assessed (a) genetic diversity using simple sequence repeat (SSR) markers, (b) phenotypic diversity through agro-morphological traits, and (c) genotype-by-environment interaction (GEI) effects on grain yield and other agronomic traits. Surveys and germplasm collection in major fonio-producing communities yielded 176 accessions, of which 140 were genotyped using 14 SSR markers. Population structure analysis identified six ancestral populations, with 45% classified as admixtures. Twenty-one (21) farmer-named fonio cultivars were identified with greater genetic diversity within ethnic groups (58.5%) than between them (16.8%). Phenotypic diversity analysis of 151 white fonio accessions revealed significant genotypic variability in quantitative traits, justifying selection. Grain weight, raceme length, and plant height were strongly correlated with yield. Genetic advance estimates indicated a potential reduction of 15 days to flowering and maturity through selection, while grain weight exhibited the highest genetic gain (47.74%). GEI analysis of 20 accessions across five locations showed significant effects on yield and other traits, identifying genotypes like *Nfonikpa* and C031702 for specific adaptation and others, such as C070402, S080401, C070301, S040101 and C070301 for broad adaptation due to their high yield and stability. These findings underscore the genetic diversity and agronomic potential of Ghanaian fonio accessions and highlight traits critical for breeding programs. Future studies should evaluate these genotypes in more environments, assess pest and disease resistance, and analyze nutritional and sensory properties to support the development of climate-resilient, high-yield fonio varieties.

DEDICATION

I dedicate this thesis to the Almighty God, my family and everyone who has made a positive impact on my life.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AFLP	Amplified Fragment Length Polymorphism
AGAP Institut	Genetic Improvement and Adaptation of Mediterranean and Tropical Plants
AMMI	Additive Main effects and Multiplicative Interaction
AMOVA	Analysis of Molecular Variance
ANOVA	Analysis of Variance
Ar	Allelic Richness
ARCAD	Agropolis Resource Centre for Crop Conservation, Adaptation and Diversity
BIC	Bayesian Information Criterion
BLUEs	Best Linear Unbiased Estimators
bp	Base pairs
CI	Confidence Interval
CIRAD	French Agricultural Research Centre for International Development
CSIR	Council for Scientific and Industrial Research
CV	Coefficient of Variation
DAPC	Discriminant Analysis of Principal Components
DArTseq	Diversity Array Technology SNP markers
DFP	Number of days to 50% Flowering
DFM	Number of days to 50% Maturity
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic Acid
dNTP	Deoxynucleotide Triphosphate
ECV	Environmental Coefficient of Variation
EDTA	Ethylene Diamine Tetra Acetic Acid
FAOSTAT	Food and Agriculture Organization Statistics
F_{IS}	Inbreeding Coefficient
FLL	Flag Leaf Length
FLW	Flag Leaf Width
F_{ST}	Fixation Index

G×E×S	Genotype × Environment × Social factors
G×E	Genotype by Environment
GA	Genetic Advance
GAM	Genetic Advance as Percentage of the Mean
GCV	Genotypic Coefficient of Variation
GEI	Genotype × Environment Interaction
GGE	Genotype Main Effects plus Genotype by Environment Interaction
GPS	Global Positioning System
GWAS	Genome-Wide Association Studies
GWP	Grain Weight per Plant
H ²	Broad-sense Heritability
H _e	Expected Heterozygosity
H _o	Observed Heterozygosity
IBD	Isolation By Distance
INRAE	French National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and Environment
KCl	Potassium Chloride
LAI	Leaf Area Index
LBL	Leaf Blade Length
LBW	Leaf Blade Width
MAF	Major Allele Frequency
MATAB	Mixed Alkyl Trimethyl Ammonium Bromide
MC3	Wash buffer, MC3
MC4	Wash buffer, MC4
MC6	Elution buffer MC6
MgCl ₂	Magnesium chloride
MSE	Error Mean Square
MSG	Genotype Mean Square
NA	Not Applicable
N _a	Number of alleles per locus

NLP	Number of Leaves per Plant
N _o :	Number of accessions
NRP	Number of Racemes per Panicle
NSR	Number of Seeds per Raceme
PC	Principal Components
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
PCR	Polymerase Chain Reaction
PCV	Phenotypic Coefficient of Variation
PH	Plant Height
PIC	Polymorphism Information Content
QTL	Quantitative Trait Loci
RAPD	Random Amplified Polymorphic DNAs
RCV	Relative Coefficient of variation
RFLP	Restriction Fragment Length Polymorphism
RL	Raceme Length
SARI	Savanna Agricultural Research Institute
SCMR	SPAD Chlorophyll Meter Reading
Sd	Standard Deviation
SE	Standard Error of the Mean
sNMF	sparse Non-negative Matrix Factorization
SNP	Single Nucleotide Polymorphism
SVD	Singular Value Decomposition
Tris-HCl	Tris Hydrochloric acid
TSW	1000 Seed Weight

CHAPTER ONE

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Fonio (*Digitaria exilis* (Kippist) Stapf), a traditional cereal crop belonging to the family Poaceae, is a small-sized grain native to West Africa (Adoukonou-Sagbadja *et al.*, 2007a; Ayenan *et al.*, 2018; Barnaud *et al.*, 2022; Cruz *et al.*, 2016; Hilu *et al.*, 1997; Portères, 1976). The domestication of fonio is believed to have happened several centuries ago and it is cultivated across many countries in West Africa from Senegal to the Lake Chad region under varying environmental conditions (Gari, 2002; Portères, 1976). Commonly referred to as hungry rice, hunger crop or the grain of life, fonio is fast growing with some cultivars maturing as early as 60 days and as such tends to fill the hunger gap mostly experienced during before the harvest of the main crop (Barnaud *et al.*, 2022; Clottey *et al.*, 2006a; Enyiukwu & Bassey, 2020; Sonko *et al.*, 2022).

Fonio is considered a food security crop and is commonly cultivated in the dry savannas of West Africa with no use of agro-chemicals such as fertilizers and other pesticides (Ayenan *et al.*, 2018; Gari, 2002). It thrives well on poor and marginal soils where other cereals may fail to produce grain (Ayenan *et al.*, 2018; Gari, 2002). Fonio cultivation can improve sustainable land use and improve the living conditions of resource-poor rural communities. In an era of climate change and variability, coupled with serious challenges in cultivating major staple cereal crops such as maize, sorghum, rice, and millet, fonio, a climate-resilient crop, could be produced on a large scale for food security and crop diversification (Adoukonou-Sagbadja *et al.*, 2007a; Barnaud *et al.*, 2022; Diop *et al.*, 2018). This is particularly important since fonio is compatible with the food systems of many traditional households in West Africa (Adoukonou-Sagbadja *et al.*, 2006). In Ghana, fonio is used in many food preparations including porridge, fonio Tuo zaafi, fonio jollof, fonio balls etc. The grains are highly nutritious with high swelling ability and have an attractive aroma when cooked (Clottey *et al.*, 2006a).

In recent times, the crop has gained popularity in the world food industry as a raw material for food preparations such as bread, cookies and sour dough. Fonio is also used in the brewing industry for producing all kinds of alcoholic and non-alcoholic

drinks (Jideani & Jideani, 2011). Abrouk *et al.* (2020) reiterated that the increasing popularity of fonio on the global scale has resulted in increased demand for fonio grains.

The grains of fonio are rich in protein, carbohydrates and essential amino acids. White fonio grains contain about 8% protein, 6.8% dietary fibre and 75% carbohydrate per 100 g of edible grains (Koroch *et al.*, 2013). Fonio grains are considered the most nutritious whole grain cereal compared to sorghum, rice, maize, barley, wheat and rye due to its high content of cysteine, methionine, lysine and essential amino acids (Ballogou *et al.*, 2014; Koroch *et al.*, 2013). Fonio grains are poor in gluten and come in handy for gluten-intolerant people with coeliac disease. Furthermore, fonio has a very low glycemic index compared to other cereals which makes it a suitable substitute for people with high blood sugar levels (Traore *et al.*, 2009; Vodouhe *et al.*, 2007). Fonio is not only good for human consumption, but the straw and grains are suitable for feeding livestock and poultry (Clottey *et al.*, 2006a).

The global fonio production in 2022 stood at 658,707.96 tons from a total production area of 884,744 ha averaging 0.74 ton/ha (FAOSTAT, 2022). Guinea is the largest producer and exporter of fonio grains with a total production of 487,533.12 tons from 594,555 ha (FAOSTAT, 2022). Nigeria is the second largest producer of fonio (84,170 tons) followed by Mali (37,833 tons) whilst Côte d'Ivoire (18,912 tons) is the fourth largest producer of fonio in West Africa. Countries like Burkina Faso, Senegal, Niger, Benin, Togo and Guinea Bissau respectively completed the top ten fonio producing countries in the world in 2022 (FAOSTAT, 2022). Although fonio is cultivated in northern Ghana, there are no official statistics on the production levels as well as land area attributed to fonio cultivation. However, fonio yield on farmers' fields is projected to range between 300 and 500 kg/ac (Amaati Company, 2024 unpublished).

In Ghana, fonio is mostly grown in the north-eastern corridor of the country and is commonly cultivated by the Anufor, Konkomba, Kabre, Bassare and Dagomba ethnic groups (Addai *et al.*, 2022; Clottey *et al.*, 2006a). Although fonio is not ranked among the most important staples in Ghana, it is regarded as an important crop for addressing food insecurity in these areas. Notwithstanding the importance of fonio to address food and nutrition insecurity on the continent, little research attention has been given to fonio by national governments and donor agencies. These have resulted in the neglect

of the crop, hence its designation as a neglected and underutilized species. The absence of adequate information on fonio genetic diversity in Ghana presents a major setback in its genetic improvement. Earlier studies have indicated that the level of improvement of any species is hinged on the extent of diversity present in the germplasm. However, there is very scanty information on the extent of genetic diversity and adaptability among fonio accessions in Ghana. Even though Clottey *et al.* (2006b) collected and characterized 13 fonio accessions using agro-morphological traits, their study revealed limited diversity owing to the low discriminatory power of morphological traits as a result of environmental influence. They therefore recommended extensive diversity analysis at the phenotypic, biochemical and molecular levels. Again, no formal breeding programme has been carried out to develop and release improved fonio varieties. Clottey *et al.* (2006a) further noted the possibility of loss of fonio genetic resources in Ghana and therefore recommended the preservation of fonio genetic resources through *ex situ* conservation in National gene banks and other research institutes to prevent the crop from going extinct.

It is therefore imperative to assemble genetic resources of fonio from the notable producing localities of the country to examine the level of genetic diversity within the crop. Assembling genetic resources of fonio will be a step towards preserving this crop from extinction. Studies have shown that genetic diversity assessment within a species is a fundamental pre-breeding activity aimed at developing efficient conservation strategies for effective utilization of the genetic resources (Adjebeng-Danquah *et al.*, 2020; Govindaraj *et al.*, 2015). The assessment of genetic diversity and associated ethnobotanical data reveals the genetic diversity patterns among the accessions and the biological, social and environmental factors that contribute to genetic structuring of crop species over time (Diop *et al.*, 2023; Leclerc & Coppens d'Veckenbrugge, 2011; Salgotra & Chauhan, 2023).

Crop genetic diversity can be analysed at molecular, biochemical (enzymes) and morphological levels. Studies have shown that the use of molecular markers for genetic diversity analyses are more reliable, independent of the growth stage of the crop, have no environmental influence, and produce consistent results across laboratories (Govindaraj *et al.*, 2015; Meena *et al.*, 2023; Nadeem *et al.*, 2018). Molecular markers such as Restriction Fragment Length Polymorphism (RFLP), Random Amplified Polymorphic DNAs (RAPDs), Amplified Fragment Length

Polymorphism (AFLP), Simple Sequence Repeats (SSR) and Single Nucleotide Polymorphism (SNP) markers have been applied in studying the genetic diversity of numerous crops including fonio (Hasan *et al.*, 2021). Among the molecular markers, SSR markers have been the most commonly used molecular marker in analyzing genetic diversity in fonio because they are polymerase chain reaction (PCR) based markers and can be deployed in most laboratories across West Africa. Vietina *et al.* (2011) reported that SSR markers being codominant and multi-allelic are able to distinguish between closely related individuals and also separate homozygous from heterozygous individuals. Dossett *et al.* (2012) indicated that SSR markers are highly polymorphic and abundantly distributed in the genome making them highly useful markers for evolutionary and genetic diversity studies, phylogenetic analysis, marker-assisted breeding and genetic fingerprinting. Fonio genetic diversity and population structure were successfully analyzed using SSR markers (Diop *et al.*, 2023; Kaczmarek *et al.*, 2023).

The importance of agro-morphological characterization in crops cannot be overemphasized. Although the use of morphological markers or traits in assessment of diversity can be confounded by environmental factors (Govindaraj *et al.*, 2015), it has been used to analyse morphological diversity and taxonomic classification in many crops (Tamiru *et al.*, 2011). Also crop domestication and selection of desirable cultivars with superior agronomic traits by farmers were based on morphological traits. Agro-morphological characterization of genetic resources is essential to determine the extent of diversity and identify useful traits of agronomic importance that can be targeted for breeding new varieties for cultivation. Badu-Apraku *et al.* (2021) and Mitsuhashi (2024) indicated that diversity analysis at the morphological level aids in the selection of accessions with superior agronomic characteristics as parental lines for initiating tailored product profiles that meet the needs of farmers and different market segments. Ultimately, such an in-depth analysis of the genetic diversity of fonio will provide the framework for the efficient utilization of the crop and unearth its full potential to ensure food and nutrition security in Ghana.

Fonio cultivation is hampered by low productivity (compared to yields in other cereals like maize, sorghum and rice per hectare) which arises from cultivation of low yielding unimproved varieties, incidence of pests such as birds and poor agronomic practices including spacing and nutrients amendments (Konate *et al.*, 2021). Konate *et al.*

(2021) further reported that the average yield of fonio was 50% less than the yield of millet, about 30% less than that of sorghum, 25% less than maize and 20% less than that of rice. This sometimes compels farmers to prioritise other cereals ahead of fonio. Additionally, the use of marginal soils for the cultivation of fonio has limited its yield potential compared to other crops. Sonko *et al.* (2022) also noted that a huge yield gap exists between the potential yield and attainable yield of fonio due to paucity of information regarding the agronomy of the crop and cropping systems which have hampered its cultivation on large scale. Though Konate *et al.* (2021) reported positive responses of fonio to application of mineral fertilizer and organic manure, farmers seldom apply these inputs to improve the growing environments placed under fonio cultivation. Studies have shown that yield and agronomic performance of fonio like most crops is highly affected by environmental conditions and genotype \times environment interaction (GEI) which affect the productivity of the crop if adaptable cultivars are not used (Addai *et al.*, 2022; Konate *et al.*, 2021).

Even though fonio is reported to be very adaptable in diverse environments (Gari, 2002), different studies on the agronomy, cropping systems and the impact of different environments on the performance of the crop have revealed some interesting outcomes. Isong *et al.* (2022) studying 13 fonio accessions in nine environments in Nigeria observed significant genotype \times environment interaction for grain yield and other agronomic traits and identified stable and superior accessions among the test genotypes. Kanlindogbè *et al.* (2023) in a two-year study of the effect of cropping system on four fonio genotypes in Benin found significant genotype \times sowing and genotype \times year interactions effect on some morpho-phenological traits studied. Isong *et al.* (2022) again attributed a greater portion of the total variability observed in grain yield of 13 fonio genotypes to the environment effect. This buttresses the point that in-depth studies regarding genetics, agronomy and the effect of genotype \times environment interaction effect on the crop. In Ghana, information concerning different adaptable environments of the crop beside the areas of intensive cultivation and implications of genotype \times environment effect is lacking. However, genotype \times environment effect has been found to be significant in important cereal crops such as millet (Asungre *et al.*, 2022), sorghum (Swaray, 2015), maize (Adu *et al.*, 2013; Haruna *et al.*, 2017) and rice (Abebrese *et al.*, 2021; Katsura *et al.*, 2016). As such, estimation of genotype \times environment interaction effect on the performance of crops

is important for varietal recommendation since its effect can result in differential performances of genotypes in different environments which slows down the process of varietal development (Osei *et al.*, 2019; Waters *et al.*, 2023).

The insufficient information on fonio cultivation locally raises many questions. Is there genetic diversity among the Ghanaian fonio accessions? What role has farmers played in maintaining the diversity among the fonio landraces over time? What factors contribute to the genetic diversity and structure of the Ghanaian fonio accessions? Is there morphological diversity among the Ghanaian fonio accessions? Do changes in environmental conditions impact on the growth, yield and nutritional properties of fonio? Therefore, an attempt to provide answers to these pertinent questions will provide a better insight into the genetic diversity patterns of the Ghanaian fonio for their effective conservation and utilization.

The main objective of this study was to exploit genetic variability through selection for genotypes with superior agronomic performance for production and also with the potential for being used for developing improved varieties of fonio.

The specific objectives of the study were to:

- i. Evaluate the genetic diversity and population structure among the fonio accessions using Simple Sequence Repeat (SSR) markers.
- ii. Study morphological diversity and agronomic performance among the fonio accessions.
- iii. Evaluate the effect of genotype \times environment interaction on fonio grain yield and other agronomic traits.

CHAPTER TWO

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 The biology and morphology of fonio

Fonio (*Digitaria* sp. Stapf) is an annual herbaceous cereal belonging to the family Poaceae. It is a small-sized grain native to West Africa (Adoukonou-Sagbadja *et al.*, 2007a; Ayenan *et al.*, 2018; Barnaud *et al.*, 2022; Cruz *et al.*, 2016; Gari, 2002; Hilu *et al.*, 1997). The genus *Digitaria* consists of several species ranging from annual to perennial grasses (Clayton & Renvoize, 1986). However, the two most important species, white fonio (*Digitaria exilis* (Kippist) Stapf) and black fonio (*Digitaria iburua* Stapf) have been domesticated in West Africa with white fonio being the most widely cultivated for food (Adoukonou-Sagbadja *et al.*, 2007a; Cruz *et al.*, 2016; Gari, 2002; Hilu *et al.*, 1997). Adoukonou-Sagbadja *et al.* (2007b) established the ploidy level of the cultivated fonio as an allotetraploid ($2n = 4x = 36$) with nine (9) sets of chromosomes. The two cultivated species *D. exilis* (Kippist) Stapf and *D. iburua* Stapf are genetically closely related to the wild species *D. longifora* and *D. ternata* respectively suggesting them as their wild ancestors (Adoukonou-Sagbadja *et al.*, 2007b). Fonio species have C4 metabolism with profuse tillering ability. It has slender culms and grows to a height of between 30 – 80 cm. Both the leaves and culms are glabrous with or without anthocyanin pigmentation on nodes, internodes and leaves (Cruz *et al.*, 2016; Gari, 2002). Fonio is a highly self-pollinating cereal with a negligible outcrossing rate of 1.7% (Barnaud *et al.*, 2017). The seed of fonio like other cereals is a caryopsis with two protective coverings, lemma and palea (Cruz *et al.*, 2016; Fliedel *et al.*, 2004). The seed is one of the smallest among cereals (Plate 2.1) measuring 1.0 mm in length and 0.75 mm in girth while the weight of 1000 seeds ranges between 0.4 – 0.7g (Cruz *et al.*, 2016; Fliedel *et al.*, 2004). Although, the two cultivated species are genetically close, there is significant differences between them. Morphologically, *D. iburua* grows taller reaching a height of about 90-100 cm while *D. exilis* is slightly shorter. The grains of *D. iburua* have fine pubescence and are heavier than *D. exilis* grains which are glabrous (Cruz *et al.*, 2016). The husk color is also a major distinguishing feature between the species. *D. iburua* has a dark-brown husk while *D. exilis* has light or pale brown husk (Portères, 1976). In terms of

threshability, *D. exilis* is easy to thresh unlike *D. iburua* which is difficult to thresh (Cruz *et al.*, 2016).

Plate 2.1 Grain size of fonio compared to other cereal grains

Source: Cruz *et al.* (2016)

2.2 The origin and geographical distribution of fonio

Fonio is regarded as one of the oldest grain cereals cultivated for food in West Africa. Although the domestication of fonio remains debatable among the research community, historical evidence of its domestication suggests the central delta of River Niger as the likely center of domestication (Portères, 1976). This region is believed to hold the greatest diversity of fonio. Linguistically, ‘fonio’ which means ‘something to eat’ is believed to have originated from the Mande language speakers who occupy the middle belt of River Niger (Portères, 1959, 1976). Across the geographical area, fonio has several vernacular names depending on the ethnic groups. It is referred to as *fini*, *fundi*, *foinye*, *founde*, *ipoaga*, *acha*, etc by many ethnic groups across West Africa (Portères, 1976). In Ghana, the Anufor ethnic group refers to fonio as *Nvoni* or *Nfoni*. The Konkomba people largely refer to the crop as *Ipui* while the Dagomba ethnic group refer to it as *Kabga*.

Among the two cultivated species, *D. exilis* (Kippist) Stapf is the most popular and widely cultivated. Its cultivation extends from Senegal to Lake Chad (Fig 2.1). On the other hand, the cultivation of *D. iburua* Stapf is limited to the northern territories of Nigeria, Benin and Togo (Cruz, 2001; Jideani, 2012; Jideani & Jideani, 2011; Murdock, 1959). In Ghana, fonio is mainly cultivated in the north eastern part of the country along the border with Togo (Clottey *et al.*, 2006a). The crop is widely grown by farmers from the Anufor, Bassare, Kabre, Konkomba, and Dagomba ethnic groups in the Chereponi, Saboba, Zabzugu, Tatale, and Gushegu districts (Addai *et al.*, 2022; Clottey *et al.*, 2006a). Chereponi district in the North East region is the main fonio-producing area in Ghana. Fonio cultivation in the Gushegu and Tatale districts in the Northern region is a more recent development, driven by the increase in commercial fonio production championed by companies involved in fonio marketing and some non-governmental organizations. Fonio cultivation in the Upper East region may not be surprising due to its proximity to the major producing areas and the free movement of tribesmen along this belt.

Figure 2.1 Distribution area of fonio across West Africa
(Cruz, 2001, as reported by R. Porteres)

2.3 Economic importance of fonio

2.3.1 Global fonio production

Fonio production worldwide has seen a significant increase from 610,353.10 metric tons in 2013 to 658,708 metric tons in 2022 (Fig 2.2) (FAOSTAT, 2022). Within the same period, the land area under fonio cultivation has increased from 717,499 ha to 884,744 ha. While the increment in production has increased by 7.9%, the increment in land area harvested has gone up by 23.3%. This shows that the increment in fonio production at the global level has been driven by the increasing area under cultivation rather than increasing production per unit area. On the other hand, yield per unit area has declined from 850 kg/ha in 2013 to 740 kg/ha in 2022. This decline in production could be attributed to the changing climate conditions, reliance on landrace cultivars which have not been improved, inadequate information on good agronomic practices and the use of marginal fields with poor soil fertility for fonio cultivation.

Figure 2.2 Global fonio production from 2013 to 2022

Source: (FAOSTAT, 2022)

Guinea is the largest producer of fonio grains with a total production of 487,533 mt from 594,555 ha land size (Table 2.1). Nigeria is the second largest producer of fonio with 84,170 mt from 170,981 ha land area. Fonio production in Mali stood at 37,833 mt from 63,967 ha in 2022, the third largest in the world. Cote d'Ivoire is the fourth largest producer of fonio with 18,912 mt from 14,977 ha. Burkina Faso, Senegal, Niger, Benin, Togo and Guinea Bissau with production of 8,186 mt, 6,623 mt, 6,050, 4,527 mt, 4,471 mt and 399 mt respectively make up the top ten fonio producing countries in the world in 2022 (FAOSTAT, 2022). The average yield per hectare ranged between 0.49 t/ha to 1.26 t/ha. In terms of fonio productivity per unit area, Cote d'Ivoire is the most productive country with 1.26 t/ha while Nigeria is the least with 0.49 t/ha. Even though Guinea is the highest producer of fonio, average yield on farmers' fields is 0.82 t/ha which is lower than average yield per unit area in Cote d'Ivoire (Table 2.1).

Table 2.1 Fonio production and productivity in 2022 in West Africa

Country	Production (tons)	Area harvested (ha)	Yield (t/ha)
Benin	4,527	8,519	0.53
Burkina Faso	8,186	10,231	0.80
Cote d'Ivoire	18,912	14,977	1.26
Guinea	487,535	594,555	0.82
Guinea-Bissau	399	540	0.74
Mali	37,833	63,967	0.59
Nigeria	84,170	170,981	0.49
Niger	6,050	8,880	0.68
Senegal	6,623	6,894	0.96
Togo	4,471	5,200	0.86
Total	658,708	884,744	0.74

Source: FAOSTAT (2022) accessed on 11 May 2024

Clottey *et al.* (2006a) noted that fonio is grown to enhance food security and bridge the annual hunger gap which typically occurs before harvesting the main staples in Northern Ghana. The crop serves as a crucial source of food during this time in the northeastern part of the country. However, despite the importance of fonio for food and nutrition security, there is no official data on fonio in Ghana. The lack of information on fonio encompasses: the annual production of fonio, the land area dedicated to its cultivation and the average yield on farmers' fields. Additionally, there is no data on local demand and annual consumption rates of fonio, nor the volume and value of fonio in the export market. Addressing these gaps will provide a better overview of the role of fonio in Ghana's agriculture and economic landscape.

2.3.2 Uses of fonio

Fonio is an important food crop in many traditional homes in West Africa. Several households depend on fonio for food and nutrition security (Barnaud *et al.*, 2022; Gari, 2002). It is referred to as the grain of life or hungry rice due to its ability to provide food for many farm-families during periods of scarcity. It is cherished as an important cereal due to the early maturing cycle of some of the landraces to fill the hunger gap mostly experienced before harvesting the main crops (Gari, 2002).

In Ghana, fonio is used in the preparation of various traditional dishes, including porridge, fonio tuo zaafi, fonio jollof, and fonio balls etc (Plates 2.2 - 2.4). The grains are highly nutritious, possess a high swelling capacity, and emit an appealing aroma when cooked (Clottey *et al.*, 2006a). The crop is becoming popular on the local market due to its diverse food applications. Recently, fonio has gained significant recognition in the global food industry, being used in products such as bread, cookies, and sourdough. It is also utilized in the brewing industry to produce a variety of alcoholic and non-alcoholic beverages (Jideani & Jideani, 2011). Cruz *et al.* (2016) indicated that fonio grains are fermented and used in the preparation of local beer called '*tchapalo*' in Togo.

Fonio has both economic and socio-cultural significance in many West African countries. Adoukonou-Sagbadja *et al.* (2006) indicated that fonio is prepared and eaten on festive occasions in southern Togo. They also reported that fonio is a key ingredient used in the initiation of women, traditional baptism of infants and wedding ceremonies

among the Lamba and Tamberma people in Togo. This shows that fonio is not a food security crop but forms a key component of the culture of many West African indigenous homes.

The surge in consumption of fonio products has been attributed to the nutritional content, health benefits and its versatility in the culinary industry. The grains are rich in protein, carbohydrates, and essential amino acids. Specifically, white fonio grains contain approximately 8% protein, 6.8% dietary fibre, and 75% carbohydrate per 100 grams of edible grains (Koroch *et al.*, 2013). Compared to other cereal grains like sorghum, rice, maize, barley, wheat, and rye, fonio is considered the most nutritious due to its high levels of cysteine, methionine, lysine, and other essential amino acids (Ballogou *et al.*, 2014; Koroch *et al.*, 2013). Fonio is also low in gluten, making it an ideal substitute for gluten intolerant people and patients battling with celiac disease. Additionally, it has a very low glycemic index, which makes it a suitable substitute for people managing high blood sugar levels (Traore *et al.*, 2009; Vodouhe *et al.*, 2007). Fonio is not only good for human consumption, but the straw and grains are suitable for feeding livestock and poultry (Adoukonou-Sagbadja *et al.*, 2006; Clottey *et al.*, 2006a). Fonio, the grain of life, believed to possess medicinal and healing properties (Gari, 2002). Adoukonou-Sagbadja *et al.* (2006) indicated that in Togo, fonio is thought to possess medicinal properties and has been used in treating chronic diarrhoea, chicken pox disease, loss of appetite, stomach-ache, asthma and dysentery. In Ghana, it has been noted that fonio consumption helps women recover quickly after childbirth, boost breast milk production and reduces malnutrition in lactating mothers and children (personal communication, Richard Yaw Agyare).

Plate 2.2 Fonio porridge

Source: Amaati Company Ltd

Plate 2.3 Fonio jollof

Source: Amaati Company Ltd

Plate 2.4 Fonio balls with soup

Source: Amaati Company Ltd

2.4 Fonio cultivation and challenges

Fonio is typically produced in the dry savannas of West Africa under rainfed conditions (Adoukonou-Sagbadja *et al.*, 2006; Ayenan *et al.*, 2018; Barnaud *et al.*, 2017; Cruz *et al.*, 2016; Gari, 2002). It performs relatively well on poor and marginal soils that might be unsuitable for other cereals such as maize and sorghum (Gari, 2002). Fonio is a resilient herbaceous plant known for its ability to endure dry spells throughout the growing season, making it drought tolerant (Cruz *et al.*, 2016; Gari, 2002). It is adaptable to different ecologies and can be grown on all soil types except for heavy soils (Adoukonou-Sagbadja *et al.*, 2006; Gari, 2002). Although fonio can withstand flood conditions, it is not grown in wetlands. Fonio seeds are sown by broadcasting on fields ploughed with a tractor or bullock with little or no need for external inputs like fertilizers and pesticides (Gari, 2002). Weed management is one of the key challenges with fonio cultivation. Weeds are controlled by hand pulling 4-5 weeks after sowing for easy identification of the fonio plants (Abdul & Jideani, 2019). Since fonio is not a good competitor with weeds, early weed control is recommended. For effective weed control, some farmers have adopted the use of

spraying glyphosate during land preparation to minimize early weed competition. Planting seeds by drilling in rows facilitates easy movement through the field and can be promoted for easy weed control and carrying out other field operations without trampling the plants.

A notable aspect of fonio cultivation in West Africa is the reliance on traditional landrace cultivars that have been passed down through generations. In Ghana, all the fonio cultivars are landraces which have not seen any genetic improvement (Clottey *et al.*, 2006a). While these landraces are well-adapted to local climatic conditions, they tend to have low yields. In addition to the low yield, fonio faces other cultivation challenges. Seed shattering, which occurs when harvesting is delayed, is a major factor contributing to the low yields of fonio (Abdul & Jideani, 2019; Barnaud *et al.*, 2022; Cruz *et al.*, 2016). This leads to significant grain loss, as seeds fall to the ground before they can be collected. Bird attacks also pose a threat, as birds feed on the grains, further reducing the yield. Another problem is lodging, where the plants fall over at maturity. This is more pronounced in taller landraces compared to shorter cultivars. This not only makes harvesting difficult but also reduces the grain yield and quality of the harvested grains (Abdul & Jideani, 2019; Cruz *et al.*, 2016). These challenges present a major setback for fonio production, making it less attractive compared to other cereals like maize, millet and sorghum. These challenges coupled with tedious postharvest activities such as threshing and husking (Cruz *et al.*, 2016) deter many farmers, particularly the younger generation, from investing in fonio production thereby threatening the sustainability of the crop (Abdul & Jideani, 2019; Adoukonou-Sagbadja *et al.*, 2006). Although fonio is resilient to biotic and abiotic factors, it is susceptible to fungal diseases caused by *Phyllachora sphearosperma* and *Helminthosporium* spp. and leaf spot caused by *Curvularia* spp. (Adoukonou-Sagbadja, 2010; Niaone *et al.*, 2024; Zinsou *et al.*, 2020). Other constraints include rust caused by *Puccinia cahuensis* and parasitism caused by *Striga rowlandi* (Adoukonou-Sagbadja, 2010). Insect pests such as stem borer (*Chilo partellus*), grasshoppers, shoot flies (*Atherigona* spp.) and Thrips have been reported to cause damage to fonio (Kalaisekar *et al.*, 2017).

To address these issues, there is a need for targeted research and development efforts to improve the yield and resilience of fonio. This could include breeding for higher-yielding varieties, non-shattering and lodging resistant cultivars, mechanization of harvesting and processing activities, and strategies to protect the crop from birds and other pests. The use of selective herbicides that are compatible with fonio could be used to control weeds. By addressing these obstacles, fonio could become a more viable and attractive crop for West African farmers, helping to ensure its cultivation and utilization for future generations.

2.5 Nutritional composition of fonio

Fonio has gained higher recognition on the international market due its rich nutrient composition and associated health benefits. Fonio compares favourably with common cereals like maize, sorghum, rice and pearl millet in nutritive value (Table 2.2). The grains of fonio are rich in protein, carbohydrates and essential amino acids. Fonio grains are considered the most nutritious whole grain cereal compared to the other cereals due to its high content of cysteine, methionine and lysine (Abdul & Jideani, 2019; Ballogou *et al.*, 2014; Koroch *et al.*, 2013). Chukwu & Abdul-Kadir (2008) reported that fonio was higher in ash and lipid content compared to the other cereals. However, its fibre content was slightly lower than maize and sorghum. In terms of minerals content, fonio was slightly lower in sodium, manganese and potassium content. On the other hand, it was superior in calcium, copper, iron, zinc and magnesium compared to the common cereals (Chukwu & Abdul-Kadir, 2008). Fonio grains have been found to be poor in gluten and come in handy for gluten-intolerant people with coeliac disease. Furthermore, fonio has a very low glycemic index compared to other cereals which makes it a suitable substitute for people with high blood sugar levels (Traore *et al.*, 2009; Vodouhe *et al.*, 2007).

Table 2.2 Biochemical analysis of husked fonio and common cereals

	Fonio	Rice	Maize	Millet	Sorghum
Carbohydrates (%)	89 - 91	90	88	87	88
Proteins (%)	7 - 9	8	10	11	10
Fat (%)	0.8 – 1.0	0.9	1.0	1.2	1.2
Mineral matter (%)	0.3 - 0.6	0.5	1.0	0.8	0.5
Cysteine	0.08	0.05	0.09	0.04	0.08
Methionine	0.42	0.15	0.22	0.23	0.24
Lysine	0.12	0.21	0.15	0.16	0.14
Calcium	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1
Magnesium	0.03	0.01	0.03	0.08	0.06
Sulphur	0.16	0.08	0.12	0.1	0.11
Iron	27.3	23.4	18.9	59.8	65
Zinc	21.8	18.6	7.4	28.5	13.2
Copper	3.0	1.8	1.5	3.8	2.1

(Fliedel *et al.*, 2004)

Koroch *et al.*, (2013) reported that white fonio grains contain about 8% protein, 6.8% dietary fibre and 75% carbohydrate per 100 g of edible grains. However, Sadiq *et al.* (2015) in comparing the nutritive value of the two species of fonio, indicated that white fonio contain 7.11% protein, 0.79% dietary fibre, and 79.72% carbohydrates per 100 g of grains. The variations in these studies especially for dietary fibre and carbohydrate suggest the effect of genotype \times environment interaction on the nutrient composition of fonio. Additionally, the method of processing the grains can also influence the quality of the grains and nutrient content. Koreissi-Dembélé *et al.* (2013) indicated that traditional processing methods had significant reductions in protein, fat, iron and zinc content of fonio in Mali. Therefore, the use of technological approaches in harvesting and postharvest activities will enhance the quality and nutrient content of the grains.

In Ghana, there is a lack of data on the nutrient composition of the fonio landraces cultivated by farmers. Thus, it is essential to profile the nutrient content of these fonio accessions to determine the extent of nutrient diversity and identify accessions with superior nutrient profiles for breeding purposes. Comparing the nutrient composition

of fonio to that of local cereals could encourage its consumption among the populace. This would not only enhance public health but also boost farmers' incomes and improve the livelihoods of the farmers and other actors in the fonio value chain.

2.6 Assessment of genetic diversity

2.6.1 Importance of genetic diversity analysis

Genetic diversity is defined as the total number of heritable variations or characters within the gene pool of an organism (Ramanatha Rao & Hodgkin, 2002). It encompasses the overall variation in the genes present within a species. Genetic diversity assessment is an important step in plant breeding because crop genetic improvement depends on the level of genetic diversity within a species. Govindaraj *et al.* (2015) and Adjebeng-Danquah *et al.* (2020) indicated that assessment of genetic diversity within a species is a fundamental pre-breeding activity aimed at quantifying the amount of genetic diversity and relatedness within the crop, developing efficient conservation strategies for effective utilization of the genetic resources in a changing world. Through analysis of genetic diversity, crop genetic resources are grouped into core and minicore collections for their effective utilization (Govindaraj *et al.*, 2015). Indeed, the success of a crop improvement program depends on the extent of genetic diversity within the available genetic resources. If there is no variability in a trait within the available germplasm, there would be little or no genetic improvement of the trait. Acquah (2007) indicated that the amount of genetic diversity among base populations informs the breeding strategy to be adopted to increase genetic gain. Assessment of crop genetic diversity and developing conservation techniques is of utmost importance for crops that have the potential to improve food security but have received little or no research attention. Due to this neglect, such crops face extinction arising from lack of interest, poor market systems, no genetic improvement, agronomic challenges and effects of climate change (Muluneh, 2021; Peñuelas *et al.*, 2013). Reif *et al.* (2005) stated that assessment of genetic diversity could reveal the amount of genetic erosion in a crop as a result of human interventions including selection and conservation. This shows that crop genetic diversity is not static; it varies in time and space under changing environmental conditions. Ramanatha Rao & Hodgkin (2002) stated that crop genetic diversity preservation is critical for the survival and well-being of present and future generations. They added that there is the

need for concerted efforts to understand the extent and distribution of genetic diversity especially of neglected species in order to develop inclusive conservation strategies and their efficient utilization. Hence, the amount of genetic diversity with a crop and its distribution would depend on its evolutionary processes, geographical and ecological factors, breeding system as well as human activities such as selection and cropping systems. Therefore, an assessment of genetic diversity and associated ethnobotanical data would deepen the understanding of the genetic diversity patterns and reveal the factors that contribute to genetic structuring of crop species over time. As a prerequisite to crop improvement, assessment of genetic diversity should cover all the important aspects of the crop in order to generate extensive data on the germplasm. Ramanatha Rao & Hodgkin (2002) indicated that a detailed ethnobotanical analysis of a crop will guide plant breeders in addressing “what to conserve”, “who to conserve”, “how to conserve” and “where to conserve” plant genetic resources. Therefore, an in-depth understanding of the genetic variability within the crop will assist gene banks in comprehensive germplasm collection, high throughput characterization, development of efficient protocols for germplasm regeneration and maintenance of genetic purity (Govindaraj *et al.*, 2015; Ramanatha Rao & Hodgkin, 2002). Additionally, having a detailed knowledge on the extent of genetic diversity within the available plant genetic resources will help plant breeders to develop tailored product profiles with the potential to address the needs of farmers and other end-users.

2.6.2 Analyses of crop genetic diversity

Crop genetic diversity within and among populations can be analysed at different levels: phenotypic or morphological characterization, biochemical (enzymes) evaluation and Deoxyribonucleic acid, DNA (molecular technology) marker methods (Govindaraj *et al.*, 2015). These approaches are useful in revealing the diversity patterns among accessions and aid in the selection of desirable genotypes for improvement purposes. However, the robustness and reliability of the observed diversity may depend on the approach used. In general, the use of DNA markers in studying crop genetic diversity is more reliable compared to biochemical and morphological markers. However, an integration of genetic markers such as Single Nucleotide Polymorphisms (SNPs) and morphological markers are effective in

identifying quantitative trait loci (QTLs) controlling agronomically important traits such as drought tolerance, diseases and pests' resistance (Govindaraj *et al.*, 2015; Meena *et al.*, 2023; Nadeem *et al.*, 2018).

2.6.3 Assessment of diversity using agro-morphological traits

The use of morphological characters or traits is the conventional method of visually assessing crop diversity (Govindaraj *et al.*, 2015). This method has been used to analyse morphological diversity and taxonomic classification in many crops (Tamiru *et al.*, 2011). Crop domestication and selection of desirable cultivars with superior agronomic properties by farmers were based on morphological traits. Plant breeders also select desirable genotypes based on plant phenotypes. Agro-morphological traits are categorized into two: qualitative (discrete) and quantitative (continuous) traits (Govindaraj *et al.*, 2015). Examples of qualitative traits include color, size, shape, position or growth habit, attitude of various plant parts etc. These characters are easy to score and are seldom influenced by environmental factors. On the contrary, quantitative traits such as plant height, stem girth, grain weight, seed size etc. have the tendency to be compromised by environmental conditions or factors thereby affecting the consistency of the analysis and their reliability in distinguishing between closely related individuals (Bekele & Bekele, 2014). Govindaraj *et al.* (2015) indicated that the use of morphological characters in diversity assessment can be confounded by environmental factors that interact with the genotype to produce the phenotype resulting in inconsistent grouping of accessions. Another concern with the use of agro-morphological markers is that some traits can only be assessed late in the growth of the crop. This requires the plant to be allowed to grow to full maturity, thereby prolonging the assessment period. In some crops, large tracts of land are required for the phenotyping, which increases the cost of the experiment. Despite the limitations of agro-morphological markers in diversity assessment, Govindaraj *et al.* (2015) highlighted the importance of agro-morphological traits and their extensive use in analysing diversity in various crops. They stated that agro-morphological markers are easy to assess, require less technical know-how and inexpensive technologies. They have been used by farmers in selection of landraces with superior agronomic properties. Badu-Apraku *et al.* (2021) and Mitsuhashi (2024) indicated that diversity analysis at the morphological level aids in the selection of accessions with superior

agronomic characteristics as parental lines for initiating tailored product profiles that meet the needs of producers and different market segments. Furthermore, agronomic traits with implications on crop improvement could be documented for future characterization, evaluation and selection with farmers through morphological diversity studies.

2.6.3.1 Morphological diversity studies in fonio

Several agro-morphological characters have been used in the study of diversity among fonio accessions across West Africa. These studies contributed to an understanding of the morphological variability and grouping of accessions into morphological groups from which desirable cultivars could be selected for improving agronomically important traits. Saidou *et al.* (2014) characterized 67 fonio accessions from Niger using 16 agro-morphological characters. They classified the accessions into four morphological groups with maturity period, plant biomass and grain yield being the key traits that accounted for the grouping of the accessions. They suggested that these traits, which explained a large part of the variance, should constitute the most important traits to consider when distinguishing fonio accessions. Sekloka *et al.* (2016) characterized 20 fonio millet accessions from Benin using 18 qualitative and 21 quantitative variables. They noted significant variability among the accessions for most of the variables. They reported the observation of four morphological groups using cluster analysis. The most important agro-morphological traits that contributed to the structuring were time of flowering, plant height, panicle leaf length, raceme length and grain yield. Nyam *et al.* (2017) also analyzed the diversity of 30 fonio accessions from Benin using seven agronomic traits evaluated over a three-year period. The authors observed high variability among the accessions in plant height, leaf length and width, days to maturity and 1000 seed weight. Using cluster analysis, they classified the fonio accessions into two morphotypes, separating *Digitaria exilis* accessions from *D. iburua* accessions. The phenotypic diversity of 180 fonio germplasm from five West African countries using 20 agro-morphological descriptors was studied (Ibrahim Bio Yerima *et al.*, 2020). They observed significant differences between the fonio germplasm for the majority of the quantitative traits studied. They also observed significant and positive correlation between grain yield and most of the yield related traits. Additionally, they observed three phenotypic groups organized

principally by time of maturity and grain yield. Balma *et al.* (2023) analyzed the morphological diversity of 60 fonio accessions in Burkina Faso using 21 agro-morphological characters. From their analysis, the fonio accessions were grouped into four morphological groups with grain yield, biomass, number of racemes and crop cycle being the most important traits.

In the case of Ghana, the morphological diversity of 13 fonio accessions were studied using 24 agro-morphological parameters (Clottey *et al.*, 2006b). The authors noted five morphological clusters mainly structured by crop phenology. They reported significant variability among the accessions for the number of nodes per tiller, flag leaf area, spikelet length, number of fingers per spike and phenological characters. However, they noted non-significant variability among the accessions for grain yield, plant height, biomass and harvest index. This lack of variability in grain yield and other important traits which is contrary to the observations in the other West African countries could be due to low genetic variability among the accessions or fewer number of accessions used. Therefore, an extensive study involving a large number of accessions and agro-morphological traits would enhance our understanding of the morphological diversity and the key traits that would be important for diversity studies and crop improvement purposes.

2.6.4 Assessment of genetic diversity using biochemical markers

Biochemical markers are genetic markers produced due to allelic variants of enzymes which can be detected through protein electrophoresis (Govindaraj *et al.*, 2015). These co-dominant markers with simple inheritance possess different regulatory properties with varying levels of gene expressions in different individuals. Biochemical markers include isozymes and allozymes. Govindaraj *et al.* (2015) indicated that the use of biochemical markers in genetic diversity analysis remain unpopular due to the limited number of enzymes and their complex structural nature. Additionally, Mondini *et al.* (2009) stated that biochemical markers are less polymorphic (exon regions of DNA are analyzed) and their use is confounded by type of plant tissue, growth stage of plant and extraction method used. These challenges have limited the application of biochemical markers in studying crop genetic diversity.

2.6.5 Assessment of genetic diversity using DNA markers

Govindaraj *et al.* (2015) indicated that DNA markers comprised a range of molecular markers widely distributed in the genome of an organism. Molecular markers are capable of detecting variations in individuals resulting from naturally occurring polymorphism (insertions, deletions, duplications and inversions) of DNA sequence in the chromosome (Bekele & Bekele, 2014). These molecular markers are mostly found in the intron regions of the DNA. Although molecular markers may not directly influence the expression of a trait, they are often found near or closely linked to genes controlling agronomic traits and can be used for selecting desirable genotypes (Hasan *et al.*, 2021). Hasan *et al.* (2021) indicated that genetic markers such as Restriction Fragment Length Polymorphism (RFLP), Random Amplified Polymorphic DNAs (RAPDs), Amplified Fragment Length Polymorphism (AFLP), Simple Sequence Repeats (SSR) and Single Nucleotide Polymorphism (SNP) markers have been applied to numerous aspects of plant breeding. Studies have reported the use of DNA markers in genetic diversity assessment, selection of parental genotypes, hybrid authenticity, marker assisted selection, gene pyramiding and genomic selection (Collard & Mackill, 2008; Meena *et al.*, 2023). Nadeem *et al.* (2018) and Meena *et al.* (2023) highlighted that DNA markers have no environmental influence, are independent of growth stage of the crop, are unlimited in number, are stable and produce consistent results. Also, Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR) based molecular technologies and recent advancement in sequencing technologies have drastically reduced the cost and time of acquiring high quality molecular data, making DNA markers the preferred markers for genetic diversity assessment and related analysis (Nadeem *et al.*, 2018). This shows that the application of molecular markers in genetic diversity analysis of crops are indispensable. In general, DNA markers are categorized into hybridization-based markers, PCR-based markers and DNA sequence-based markers. Mondini *et al.* (2009) stated that an ideal DNA marker is well distributed in the genome of the organism, co-dominant in nature, highly polymorphic and reproducible.

2.6.5.1 Types of DNA markers

There are several types of molecular markers which have been employed in assessing crop genetic diversity in crops. Hasan *et al.* (2021) stated that the molecular markers that have been widely applied to agricultural research include Restriction Fragment Length Polymorphism (RFLP), Random Amplified Polymorphic DNA (RAPD), Amplified Fragment Length Polymorphism (AFLP), Simple Sequence Repeats (SSR) and Single Nucleotide Polymorphism (SNP). The differences among the DNA markers, advantages and limitations are discussed below.

2.6.5.2 Restriction Fragment Length Polymorphism (RFLP) markers

Restriction Fragment Length Polymorphism (RFLP) markers are hybridization-based markers which have been applied extensively in genetic diversity analysis of crops including cereals particularly maize, sorghum, rice and wheat (Ajmone Marsan *et al.*, 1998; Cui *et al.*, 1995; Liu & Tsunewaki, 1991; Zaharleva *et al.*, 2001). As codominant markers, RFLP markers are robust, reliable and useful in detecting an unlimited number of loci across the genome of crops. On the contrary, Collard & Mackill (2008) indicated that RFLP markers require high amounts of DNA, are expensive, labour intensive and time consuming. They noted that RFLP markers are deficient in detecting polymorphism in closely related individuals.

2.6.5.3 Rapid Amplified Polymorphic DNA (RAPD)

Collard & Mackill (2008) indicated that Rapid amplified polymorphic DNA (RAPD) markers, a PCR-based molecular marker, were among the first to be developed for genetic diversity analysis. RAPD markers are random primers, usually oligonucleotides (10 base pairs) used for amplifying segments of genomic DNA using the PCR machine. Although RAPD markers are less expensive compared to RFLP markers, require less time and small amounts of plant material for DNA extraction, they are dominant markers, and the results are often not reproducible between laboratories (Collard & Mackill, 2008).

2.6.5.4 Amplified Fragment Length Polymorphism (AFLP) markers

Mohan *et al.* (1997) defined Amplified fragment length polymorphism (AFLP) markers as dominant genetic markers that utilize restriction enzymes to digest specific segments of the DNA sequence followed by PCR amplification of the digested DNA fragments. AFLP markers produce highly reproducible results within a short time, relatively inexpensive and can distinguish between closely related individuals. However, Mohan *et al.* (1997) stated that AFLP markers are not able to distinguish between individuals in a heterozygous state from homozygotes.

2.6.5.5 Simple Sequence Repeat (SSR) markers

Simple sequence repeat (SSR) markers have been noted as the most used PCR-based molecular markers (Carvalho *et al.*, 2021). They are also referred to as microsatellite markers or short tandem repeat markers. SSR markers are short DNA sequences ranging from 2-10 base pairs that are highly polymorphic and widely distributed in the genome of plants and animals (Zane *et al.*, 2002). They are highly variable among individuals (Carvalho *et al.*, 2021; Dossett *et al.*, 2012). Unlike AFLP markers, SSR markers are codominant and multi-allelic, able to distinguish between closely related individuals as well as separate homozygous from heterozygous individuals (Vietina *et al.*, 2011). SSR marker assays require less time, are highly reproducible with good analytical resolution (Carvalho *et al.*, 2021; Dossett *et al.*, 2012; Vietina *et al.*, 2011). Dossett *et al.* (2012) indicated that due to the highly polymorphic nature and abundant distribution in the genome, SSR markers are ideal for evolutionary and genetic diversity studies, marker-assisted breeding, genetic fingerprinting, phylogenetic analysis, genome mapping, genome-wide association studies (GWAS). Wan *et al.* (2004) and Thakur *et al.* (2018) indicated that SSR markers may be useful across different species because of the highly conserved nature of the DNA sequences flanking the SSR regions. Notwithstanding the importance of SSR markers, their development requires adequate knowledge of the genome of the species to design the forward and reverse primers required for amplifying the SSR loci (Mondini *et al.*, 2009; Zane *et al.*, 2002). Gupta *et al.* (2003) also stated that generating genomic libraries for detecting SSR loci is expensive and time consuming.

2.6.5.6 Single Nucleotide Polymorphisms (SNPs) markers

Single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) refer to variations in DNA sequences among individuals arising from changes in single nucleotide positions in the genome (Bekele & Bekele, 2014; Morgil *et al.*, 2020). Among the DNA markers, SNPs are the most abundant and occur frequently in the genome (Morgil *et al.*, 2020; Vallejos-Vidal *et al.*, 2020). The application of SNP marker technology in marker assisted breeding is more effective since SNP markers are closer to genes or sometimes part of the genes of interest than any other molecular markers (Bekele & Bekele, 2014; Morgil *et al.*, 2020). They are also useful for constructing genetic maps, genetic diversity studies, association mapping and genomic selection. Meena *et al.* (2023) and Morgil *et al.* (2020) indicated that next generation sequencing approaches have revolutionized the application of SNP marker technologies in plant genetic diversity analysis by particularly reducing the cost, time of acquisition and quality of sequence data. Additionally, the growing availability of whole-genome sequences for most species have enhanced population genetic diversity studies (Govindaraj *et al.*, 2015; Morgil *et al.*, 2020).

2.6.5.7 Diversity Array Technology (DArTseq) SNP markers

Diversity array technology (DArTseq) SNP markers are high-density molecular markers developed through microarray hybridization technology (Semagn *et al.*, 2012). They are less expensive and require no previous sequence data on the crop before they are used. DArTseq SNP markers are highly reproducible and are useful in genetic diversity studies and identifying quantitative trait loci (QTLs) for agronomic traits (Amponsah Adjei *et al.*, 2023; Semagn *et al.*, 2012).

2.6.6 Molecular data analysis

The application of the molecular data generated through the DNA marker technologies described above for genetic diversity studies is categorized into two (Govindaraj *et al.*, 2015). Firstly, the data generated could be used for estimation of population genetics parameters such as allele frequencies (major and minor alleles), heterozygosity (observed and expected), polymorphism information content (PIC), differentiation statistics (F_{ST}) and inbreeding coefficient etc. Analysis of molecular

variance within and between populations can be calculated. The second part of the analysis focuses on assessing the genetic relationships amongst the individuals through principal component analysis (biplots), cluster analysis (dendrogram), and population structure (Abrouk *et al.*, 2020; Kaczmarek *et al.*, 2023).

2.6.7 Genetic diversity studies in fonio

The assessment of genetic diversity in fonio using molecular markers have been reported by many authors. Hilu *et al.* (1997) reported the genetic diversity and evolution of *Digitaria* spp. using Random Amplified Polymorphic DNA (RAPD) markers. They noted that *Digitaria exilis* and *Digitaria iburua* are genetically distinct and confirmed the hypothesis that the two species are genetically related to wild species *Digitaria longiflora* and *Digitaria ternata*. Adoukonou-Sagbadja *et al.* (2007a) studied the genetic diversity and population structure of 122 fonio accessions from five West African countries using Amplified Fragment Length Polymorphism (AFLP) markers. They reported the identification of four distinct clusters with a clear separation of *D. exilis* accessions from *D. iburua* despite being morphologically similar. They added that geographical origin of the fonio accessions contributed to the differentiation pattern observed. Abrouk *et al.* (2020) studied the genetic diversity, population structure and domestication of fonio through deep re-sequencing of 183 fonio accessions. The authors highlighted that the genetic diversity of fonio was organized by geographic, climatic and ethnolinguistic factors. Furthermore, they noted the development of high-quality genomic resources to facilitate molecular breeding of fonio. The genetic diversity and population structure of 259 fonio accessions from six West African countries was analyzed using DArTseq-derived SNP markers (Ibrahim Bio Yerima *et al.*, 2021). They found out that substantial genetic diversity existed among the fonio accessions, and the clustering observed was organized according to the geographical origin or distribution of the fonio accessions. Diop *et al.* (2023) studied the genetic diversity, population structure and evolutionary history of fonio landraces in Senegal using SSR markers and social anthropology. They noted spatial organization of fonio genetic diversity at two levels: genetic differentiation among ethnic groups and demographic history among linguistic families. Again, they noted that selection of desirable fonio landraces and seed exchange practices among farmers contributed to the structuring of fonio genetic diversity in Senegal. Kaczmarek *et al.*

(2023) analyzed the genetic diversity of the largest collection of fonio accessions (1539) using 14 SSR markers. They indicated that the 14 SSR markers were polymorphic with a mean of 13.92 alleles per locus. Population structure analysis grouped the accessions into six genetic clusters with spatial organization of genetic diversity.

2.7 Germplasm collection, characterization and management

Plant genetic resources (germplasm), which comprise wild relatives, landraces, advance lines and improved varieties and genetic stocks constitute the entire genetic resources of a crop through which agricultural productivity and crop improvement is hinged on (Bhattacharjee *et al.*, 2007; van Hintum *et al.*, 2000). Germplasm collection is important to enhance crop genetic diversity for food and nutrition security and future crop improvement activities (Ifeanyi *et al.*, 2016). Germplasm collection is the process of collecting genetic resources of a crop from different sources with the aim of preserving them for future use (Quazi *et al.*, 2021). Crop germplasm can be collected from local sources to broaden the genetic base of a crop to enhance plant breeding. However, if a trait of interest cannot be found in the local germplasm, exploring germplasm from exotic sources is inevitable. It has been reported that assembling germplasm from both local and exotic sources improves within and between population variations and increases their resilience to the changing climate (Adjebeng-Danquah *et al.*, 2020; Birhan *et al.*, 2022). Ifeanyi *et al.* (2016) noted that no country has within its borders the entire genetic resources of a crop to address the challenges with food production, hence the need to exchange germplasm among countries to ensure global food security.

Quazi *et al.* (2021) defined germplasm conservation as the protection of crop genetic diversity from extinction. Germplasm conservation has become more important than ever due to human activities, climate change and the rate at which some crop species have become endangered or threatened with time (Govindaraj *et al.*, 2015; Ifeanyi *et al.*, 2016). Alcorn (1991) stated that crop germplasm can be managed in either *ex-situ* or *in-situ* conservation strategies. However, the strategy to adopt often depends on the crop and the available resources. *In-situ* conservation of plant genetic resources encompasses the maintenance of crops under natural field conditions where the crop is well adapted (Quazi *et al.*, 2021). However, *ex-situ* preservation encompasses the

collection of seeds or plant propagules for storage in gene banks and the use of botanical gardens and field farms. Quazi *et al.* (2021) indicated that conservation of genetic resources under *ex-situ* conservation reduces the risk of extinction of crops, particularly threatened and endangered species. Germplasm conservation in gene banks under controlled conditions help maintain the viability of seeds for prolonged periods. Additionally, germplasm conservation in gene banks results in improved seed health and may reduce the risk of genetic erosion in *in-situ* conservation due to crop failure (Yadav *et al.*, 2024). Also, for effective conservation, seeds should be preserved in multiple gene banks, either in local gene banks or international gene banks with the capacity for long-term storage.

Germplasm characterization is an important step in the breeding process aimed at generating and documenting the attributes and characteristic features on the assembled germplasm for effective utilization (Govindaraj *et al.*, 2015; Quazi *et al.*, 2021). Germplasm characterization can be done at the phenotypic, molecular or biochemical level. Germplasm characterization helps in the identification and selection of genetically distinct individuals with desirable agronomic traits which could be further evaluated or selected as parents for improvement purposes (Govindaraj *et al.*, 2015). Through germplasm characterization, potential duplicate accessions can be identified and eliminated. This is essential as germplasm conservation comes at a cost and becomes expensive if large collections are involved. Additionally, management of germplasm in gene banks has several limitations including high cost of electricity and inadequate cold facilities (Panis *et al.*, 2020). This necessitated the development of a subset of the entire collection for efficient management.

Frankel (1984) recommended the development of core collection of germplasm to manage the challenges associated with dealing with large collections of germplasms in gene banks and improve utilization efficiency. Phenotyping a large number of accessions is time-consuming and expensive resulting in under-characterization of germplasm in most gene banks. However, with a subset of accessions that encompasses the total diversity, germplasm characterization and documentation become less cumbersome and in-expensive. Core collections or diversity panels comprise genetically distinct accessions that represent the total diversity within the assembled germplasm of a crop (Bhattacharjee *et al.*, 2007; Egan *et al.*, 2022). Brown (1995) indicated that a core collection should be genetically, geographically and

ecologically diverse in order to capture the highest diversity in the collection. (Sharma *et al.*, 2012a) indicated that a core collection is usually 10% of the entire germplasm collection. They noted that for some germplasm, a core collection may still be too large to effectively characterize and manage, therefore the development of a mini-core collection. A mini-core collection is generally made up of 10% of the core collection (Sharma *et al.*, 2012a). Sun *et al.* (2021) revealed that core collections have been used in evolutionary and ecological studies of species, development and management of germplasm for their efficient utilization by plant breeders. Upadhyaya *et al.* (2013) also stated that the establishment of core and mini-core collections of crops have improved crop improvement through enhanced germplasm utilization. Egan *et al.* (2019) indicated that, although the development of core and mini core collections have the potential to enhance germplasm utilization, the mode of evaluation, which traits to be phenotyped and the handling of the germplasm not included in the list raises concerns about the overall utilization.

In Ghana, the germplasm of many crop species has been conserved in the national gene bank, the CSIR-Plant Genetic Resources Research Institute, Bunsu, which can be accessed by plant breeders and researchers for improvement purposes. This is not the case for fonio, a grain cereal with the potential to address food insecurity in the face of global changes. Fonio genetic resources have been conserved by farmers who produce the crop year after year and conserve their landraces through mass selection. This means that fonio germplasm have not been assembled and conserved at the national genebank. The farmers who are the custodians of genetic resources have maintained the genetic integrity of the different landraces of fonio over time. This is as a result of the limited seed mediated gene flow as occasioned by the highly autogamous nature of fonio (Barnaud *et al.*, 2017). However, the uncertainties with crop production caused by climate change shows that the over reliance on farmers in conserving fonio genetic diversity could potentially lead to loss of genetic resources. Clottey *et al.* (2006a) noted a potential loss of genetic resources of fonio in Ghana due to climate changes. It is therefore imperative to assemble the local fonio germplasm for conservation in gene banks to complement the role of the farmers. This will ensure fonio genetic resources are safeguarded for future agricultural development. To achieve this, a large-scale germplasm collection is essential. The assembled germplasm should be characterized extensively and conserved at the gene bank to

enhance their utilization in future fonio breeding programmes. Additionally, a core collection for fonio should be established, through international collaboration and germplasm exchange using standard material transfer agreement, to capture the geographical distribution and ecological diversity of the crop across West Africa. Additionally, the core collection should be preserved in an international gene bank with the capacity for long-term preservation. This can be done at the Institute for Research and Development or CIRAD, Montpellier, France where the global fonio genetic resources are being conserved.

2.8 Indigenous knowledge and socio-cultural factors on crop genetic diversity

Farmers who are the custodians of crop genetic resources play a crucial role in the maintenance of genetic diversity (Puneeth *et al.*, 2024). Farmers' traditional knowledge, cultivation practices and socio-cultural factors contribute to the structuring and differentiation of crop species over time (Leclerc & Coppens d'Eeckenbrugge, 2011). Farmers have immense knowledge on the attributes of their landraces which aid them in selecting for traits that are of significance to local conditions and food needs (Puneeth *et al.*, 2024). For example, Ibrahim Bio Yerima *et al.* (2020) reported that farmers in drier areas of Niger, Mali and Burkina Faso, have selected for early maturing fonio landraces while late maturing fonio landraces were more preferred in relatively wet areas in Benin and Nigeria. Selection based on maturity is also influenced by labor requirements. In Ghana, for instance, some farmers cultivate late maturing cultivars so that the demand for labor at the peak fonio season does not coincide with the demand for labor on the main cereals (Richard Yaw Agyare, 2021, unpublished). Farmers also consider traits such as grain color, seed size, ease of threshing and dehusking, lodging resistance, aroma, cooking qualities, swelling ability and other pasting properties in distinguishing between landraces. The application of farmers' ethnobotanical knowledge on the landraces has led to the selection and conservation of distinct crop genetic resources that have the potential to change Africa's agriculture. Adoukonou-Sagbadja *et al.* (2006) reported that farmers' traditional knowledge and cultivation practices contributed to the conservation of 42 distinct fonio landraces in Togo even though the majority of the farmers had no formal education. This shows that the farmers had deep knowledge on the characteristics of the fonio landraces which aided them in the selection processes. Similarly, Ballogou

et al. (2014) documented 35 farmer-named fonio landraces in Benin signifying the role of traditional knowledge in landrace diversity preservation. They further indicated that the farmers had good knowledge on how to identify, classify and utilize their fonio landraces. The local names given to fonio landraces also contribute to the identification, selection and conservation of landraces. Sambatti *et al.* (2001) indicated that the value of folk nomenclature in plant genetic resources conservation cannot be overemphasized. Even though landrace naming varies among ethnic groups, the names given may reflect some morphological features such as growth habit, pericarp color, phenology and seed characteristics (Adoukonou-Sagbadja *et al.*, 2006; Balma *et al.*, 2022).

Other indicators farmers use to describe crop species include the origin of the landrace or description of its usage or sometimes the person who introduced the landrace into a community. For example, Adoukonou-Sagbadja *et al.* (2006) indicated that fonio landrace names such as *Ova* (Akposso ethnic group) and *Ipibim* (Bassar ethnic group) means ‘a new food from the bush’ and ‘bush grains for birds’ respectively in Togo. Similarly, among the Konkomba ethnic group in Ghana, some fonio landraces are named based on the pericarp color of the grain where *Ipui maln*, *Ipui bolne* and *Ipui piln* refers to red, black and white skin fonio respectively (Richard Yaw Agyare, 2021, unpublished). Also, some of the names given to fonio landraces describe the growth cycle of the cultivar. For instance, the fonio landrace name, *Fefeke*, by the Anufor ethnic group in Ghana means an early maturing cultivar. In effect some of the landrace names may serve as identity marks for the cultivars and contribute to the maintenance of genetic diversity over time. Therefore, an understanding of the cultivar naming systems and traditional practices which have been passed on to the current generation may better our knowledge on fonio cultivation.

The practice of cultivating multiple landraces of crops is a deliberate strategy by farmers to minimize crop failure and ensure food security. Adoukonou-Sagbadja *et al.* (2006) reported that in Togo fonio landraces are cultivated as pure cultures (sole cropping) in most of the communities or are mixed with other cereals like sorghum and millet. In situations where a farmer cultivates more than one fonio cultivar, different fields are allocated for each landrace thereby maintaining the genetic purity of the landraces. This practice is common among Ghanaian farmers who cultivate

more than on fonio landrace. By doing so, they avoid varietal mixtures and preserve the physical purity and maintain the genetic diversity of the fonio landraces.

Traditional seed exchange practices among farmers also contribute to maintenance of genetic diversity. Socio-cultural factors such as ethnicity, gender, age, educational status and social class can influence the movement and spread of fonio landraces. Diop *et al.* (2023) reported that fonio genetic diversity in Senegal was structured by the ethnicity of farmers. They revealed that while the Balante ethnic group cultivated late cycle cultivars, the Fulani people cultivated early maturing cultivars. They emphasized that fonio seed exchange within ethnic groups was higher than between ethnic groups resulting in genetic differentiation of the landraces. Similarly, Labeyrie *et al.* (2014) reported that sorghum genetic diversity in Kenya was organized according to farmers ethnicity. They indicated that different ethnic groups were associated with specific sorghum landraces while improved varieties were even distributed across the ethnic groups. Orozco-Ramírez *et al.* (2016) ascribed the genetic diversity of maize in Mexico to the lack of seed exchange between farmers in two adjacent communities due to cultural differences.

In Ghana, fonio genetic resources have not been conserved in a Genebank, *ex-situ* conservation. Fonio genetic resources are maintained by farmers through traditional methods of cultivating and selecting seeds to plant year after year. The farmers are the sole repository of fonio genetic resources and play a key role in the maintenance of genetic diversity within a crop. While the farmers have played a critical role in preserving these genetic resources over time, there could be loss of genetic resources if deliberate efforts are not put in place for *ex-situ* conservation to complement the role of the farmers. Since fonio genetic resources have not been collected and conserved in Ghana, there is no ethnobotanical data on the fonio landraces. Leclerc and Coppens d'Eeckenbrugge (2011) indicated that crop genetic diversity is influenced by the interaction between the genotype (G), environment (E) and social (S) factors. These factors interact at different scales, contributing to crop genetic diversity and differentiation (Leclerc & Coppens d'Eeckenbrugge, 2011). Therefore, it is imperative that a full-scale ethnobotanical study be conducted to document farmers' knowledge on genetic diversity, cultivation practices, socio-cultural and environmental factors and strategies for conserving genetic diversity of fonio in Ghana. This information would enhance our understanding of the evolutionary processes which may have

contributed to fonio genetic diversity in Ghana. Also, farmers' traditional practices could influence the development of efficient germplasm conservation strategies for fonio genetic resources for crop diversification and food security in the face of global changes.

2.9 Fonio breeding and challenges

Crop improvement is the art of introducing traits of agricultural importance into existing varieties with the objective of improving yield and quality (Aswini *et al.*, 2023). Plant breeders have over the years made significant progress with developing new varieties of crops to improve food and nutrition security and enhance the livelihoods of farmers. These have been achieved through the use of conventional breeding and the application of molecular marker technologies such as marker assisted breeding, genetic engineering etc. However, very little or not much has been achieved in terms of developing new varieties of fonio. Over the years, fonio research across West Africa has focused basically on describing the genetic diversity and structure among the accessions using agro-morphological characters (Clottey *et al.*, 2006b; Ibrahim Bio Yerima *et al.*, 2020; Sekloka *et al.*, 2016) and molecular markers (Abrouk *et al.*, 2020; Adoukonou-Sagbadja, 2010; Diop *et al.*, 2023; Ibrahim Bio Yerima *et al.*, 2021; Kaczmarek *et al.*, 2023). Also, understanding the evolutionary history and domestication as well as indigenous knowledge and the role of farmers in preserving the genetic diversity of fonio through ethnobotanical studies (Adoukonou-Sagbadja *et al.*, 2006; Ballogou *et al.*, 2014; Burton *et al.*, 2024; Diop *et al.*, 2018).

Although attempts have been made by plant breeders to improve fonio through conventional breeding in Guinea and other countries, no successful hybridization has been reported (Ayenan *et al.*, 2018; Vodouhe *et al.*, 2007). To date, farmers rely on landrace cultivars which have not been improved, and the seed system is mainly informal (Adoukonou-Sagbadja *et al.*, 2006; Dansi *et al.*, 2010; Kanlindogbe *et al.*, 2020; Sekloka *et al.*, 2016). Even though fonio genetic resources have been conserved in some institutes, breeding programs on fonio are not functional or non-existent in most of the West African countries. This limitation could be due to the inadequate investment in fonio research and breeding, the small-sized floral organs and insufficient knowledge on the floral characteristics (Adoukonou-Sagbadja *et al.*, 2007; Ayenan *et al.*, 2018; Sekloka *et al.*, 2016; Vodouhe *et al.*, 2007). This is compounded

by the highly autogamous nature of fonio, 1.7% outcross rate (Barnaud *et al.*, 2017) making it difficult to achieve successful emasculation and pollination. To address these, research investment should be made to deepen our understanding of the floral biology of the crop to develop efficient strategies for introgressing desirable traits in farmer preferred cultivars. Additionally, investment in high-throughput phenotyping could facilitate accurate selection of superior genotypes.

To overcome the barriers in conventional fonio breeding, biotechnological tools such as somaclonal variation could be employed to create heritable variation to improve traits such as seed size, grain yield, non-shattering, and lodging resistance in fonio (Kuta *et al.*, 2003). Repellin *et al.* (2001) indicated that the transformative capabilities of biotechnological tools in creating heritable genetic variations have overcome traditional crossing barriers in most crops. Cereals such as rice and maize have successfully responded to biotechnological tools, and fonio could potentially respond to these techniques as well. Mutation breeding also offers another opportunity that could be explored to create and select mutants endowed with superior agronomic attributes that meet the breeding objective (Roychowdhury & Tah, 2013). Animasaun *et al.* (2014) reported that the application of different doses of gamma radiation using cobalt 60 was effective in increasing variability in fonio. They concluded that fonio seeds treated with 80 Gy performed optimally in grain yield and other agronomic traits evaluated. Kanlindogbe *et al.* (2020) highlighted that the increasing availability of genomic resources on fonio offers promising opportunities for accelerating the development and release of superior cultivars of fonio with end-user preferred traits. Genomic selection coupled with high-throughput phenotyping for agronomic traits could facilitate identification of desirable genotypes.

2.10 The concept of Genotype × Environment Interaction

Genotype × environment interaction (G×E) refers to the differential response of genotypes evaluated in different environments (De Leon *et al.*, 2016). On the other hand, when the performance of genotypes is independent of the environments in which they were grown, then there is no genotype × environment interaction. Genotype × environment interaction is significant when the performance of genotypes varies across environments. The effects of genotype by environment interaction on crops is often significant due to considerable variations in soil, climatic, environmental

conditions and crop management practices (Adu *et al.*, 2013). When the variations in these factors are large, genotype \times environment interaction effect tends to be larger and significant. Genotype \times environment interaction is an important concept in plant breeding programmes as it affects decision-making processes such as allocation of resources, breeding strategy, identification of appropriate testing locations, scope of evaluation, selection and recommendation of genotypes (De Leon *et al.*, 2016). Yau (1995) reported that genotype \times environment interaction has the tendency to impede the selection of desirable cultivars in multi-environment trials and prolongs the breeding cycle. This is because the response of genotypes may vary between environments and among years. Variations in performances among genotypes in different environments can be predicted if there is spatial heterogeneity in soil conditions and crop management practices. However, genotype by environment interaction effect among years cannot be easily predicted or managed due to the unpredictable and changing climatic conditions (Dabholkar, 1992). Additionally, Yau (1995) stated that the magnitude of this variation may not be the same for all genotypes across the environments. While some genotypes may exhibit higher sensitivity to environmental factors, others may show greater resilience across a diverse range of environments (Yau, 1995).

The effect of genotype \times environment interaction (G \times E) on the selection of genotypes could pose a challenge to plant breeders or not. For example, when genotype \times environment interaction affects the magnitude of the variation without altering the ranking of the genotypes (non-crossover or quantitative G \times E), it is often not a major concern for plant breeders (De Leon *et al.*, 2016). However, in situations where G \times E causes a change in ranking in the performance of the genotypes across environments (crossover or qualitative G \times E), it complicates the selection and recommendation of the best performing genotypes in a given environment (De Leon *et al.*, 2016).

2.10.1 Concept of stability and adaptation

Genotype \times environment interactions have been observed in many crops including maize (Adu *et al.*, 2013; Azrai *et al.*, 2022; Haruna *et al.*, 2017), finger millet (Adugna *et al.*, 2011), pearl millet (Asungre *et al.*, 2022), oat (Kebede *et al.*, 2023), sorghum (Kondombo *et al.*, 2024) cassava (Uchendu *et al.*, 2022), Bambara groundnut

(Olanrewaju *et al.*, 2021) resulting in changes in ranking of genotypes across environments and years. In such situations, cultivar recommendations are not straightforward. This phenomenon brought about the concepts of stability in performance and adaptation. De Leon *et al.* (2016) defined stability as the consistency in performance of a genotype in a given trait across environments and seasons. A genotype is said to have high stability when its environmental variance is low while an unstable genotype has high environmental variance. However, high stability in a trait is considered desirable if it is combined with high performance in that trait (De Leon *et al.*, 2016). Becker & León (1988) indicated that stability can be measured either in the biological (static) or agronomic (dynamic) sense. A genotype is considered to have static stability when it produces similar responses irrespective of changes in environmental factors. This form of stability is ideal for traits such as disease resistance and quality properties (Becker & León, 1988). On the contrary, dynamic stability is observed when a genotype responds positively to changes in the growing conditions resulting in producing above average performance (Sabaghnia *et al.*, 2015). Genotypes with high dynamic stability are of interest to farmers and plant breeders because of their positive returns on investment in inputs such as fertilizers and irrigation facilities. Powell *et al.* (2012) reported that genotypes that combine high yield with high stability and are resilient to climate change are desirable for improving crop production and ensuring food security.

Adaptation, on the other hand, refers both to the condition (genetic make-up) and processes by which plants or organisms become suited to their environment in order to reproduce (Vogt, 2017). Adaptation can be categorized into two: broad or wide and specific or narrow adaptation. In multi-environment trials, the performance of genotypes can be expressed based on the level of stability and adaptation. Genotypes that have high per se performance and are stable across the majority of the test environments are categorized as broadly adapted genotypes. Such genotypes can be recommended for cultivation across a wider geographical area. On the other hand, genotypes that perform well only in certain environments are considered to have specific adaptation and can be recommended for cultivation in such environments (Chapman *et al.*, 1997; Cooper *et al.*, 1997).

Therefore, the identification and selection of fonio landraces or genotypes with high grain yield and adaptable to diverse environmental conditions cannot be overemphasized in fonio breeding programmes. An in-depth analysis of genotype by environment interaction in fonio would establish the sensitivity of the cultivars to different environmental conditions. This would help identify fonio landraces that have specific or wide adaptation for cultivar recommendation and further improvement purposes.

2.10.2 Measurement of G×E

To measure the effect of genotype × environment interaction in multi-environment trials, several statistical models have been developed. The commonest tools include the joint regression analysis (Yau, 1995), the genotype main effects plus genotype × environment interaction effects (GGE) model also known as site regression analysis (Yan & Tinker, 2006) and the additive main effects and multiplicative interaction (AMMI) model (Zobel *et al.*, 1988). However, the two commonly used models are the GGE and AMMI models which combine analysis of variance with singular value decomposition (SVD) i.e. principal component analysis (PCA), of the two-way multi-environment trial data. These statistical models help to quantify the magnitude and pattern of genotype × environment interaction effect using biplots, a limitation in the combined analysis of variance approach (Yan *et al.*, 2000). Yang *et al.* (2009) indicated that biplot analysis has been used in analysing genotype by environment interaction in multi-environment trials. The biplot analysis is a rapid visualization tool for examining the patterns of variation in the genotype by environment complex two-way table (Yang *et al.*, 2009). The biplots are useful for depicting the relationship between the genotypes, environments as well as interaction between the genotypes and the environments to determine the stability and adaptation of genotypes across environments (Yan & Tinker, 2006). The major difference between the GGE model and AMMI model lies in the singular value decomposition. Yang *et al.* (2009) indicated that while the GGE model applied the singular value decomposition on the genotype main effects (G) and genotype × environment (G×E) terms in the environment-centered two-way data, the AMMI model applies the singular value decomposition on only the genotype × genotype (G×E) term in the two-way data. This difference raises concerns about the statistical power of the models in accounting for

the magnitude of the interaction (Yang *et al.*, 2009). Although several studies have cited the suitability of the AMMI model as powerful in explaining the magnitude of the genotype \times environment interaction in large multi-environment trials, it becomes deficient if the interaction component contributes very little to the total variability (Yang *et al.*, 2009).

The suitability of the GGE and AMMI models for genotype \times genotype interaction analysis have been questioned and there has been a long-standing debate on the strengths and weaknesses of these models (Gauch *et al.*, 2008; Yan *et al.*, 2007). However, the visual presentation of genotype \times environment interaction and the availability of user-friendly software have enhanced the analysis of large multi-environment trial data. Yang *et al.* (2009) indicated that the common biplots used for genotype by environment interaction analysis comprise rank-one biplots i.e. AMMI1 (AMMI model with PC1) and GGE1 (GGE model with PC1) and rank-two biplots i.e. AMMI2 (AMMI model with two PCs) and the GGE2 (GGE model with two PCs). Regarding biplot interpretations, Yang *et al.* (2009) revealed that GGE2 and AMMI2 models have similar interpretations whereas the AMMI1 model is similar to the joint-regression analysis or GGE1 model. They however cautioned the over-application of biplots in genotype by environment interaction arguing that biplots may not be able to reveal the nature and causes of the interactions and may have different effects if genotypes and environments were considered random.

Among the methods for examining genotype by environment interaction, the GGE biplot model has been reported to be effective in revealing the discriminativeness and representativeness among test environments, identifying mega environments which can help reduce the number of tests locations (Yan *et al.*, 2000; Yan & Tinker, 2006). They also indicated that the biplot analysis helps in ranking genotypes based on superior performance in the trait of interest across the test locations. Additionally, the stability in performance of genotypes across environments and adaptation to wide or specific environments can be depicted through biplot analysis. The GGE biplot also reveals the “which won where” as well as the ideal genotype which assists breeders in the selection and recommendation of superior genotypes either for localized or broad cultivation. Yan *et al.* (2007) revealed that although the AMMI biplot performs most of the functions of the GGE biplot, it is not a true biplot because it relies on a predictable table in revealing the “which won where” pattern of the analysis. On the

contrary, Gauch *et al.* (2008) revealed that AMMI-2 mega-environment biplot captures a lot of the genotype main effects and decomposes more of the genotype by environment interaction providing an accurate pattern for the “which won where” than the GGE-2 model.

2.10.3 Genotype by environment interaction in cereals

Several studies involving multi-environment trials have been analyzed using the biplot approaches. Adu *et al.* (2013) determined the grain yield and stability of 100 extra-early maturing maize genotypes evaluate in three environments in Ghana using the GGE biplot model. Haruna *et al.* (2017) used the GGE biplot to identify high-yielding and stable intermediate maturing maize hybrids evaluated in eight environments in Ghana. The effect of genotype \times environment interaction on 44 finger millet accessions evaluated in 11 environments in Ethiopia were analyzed using the AMMI 1 model. The biplot revealed four accessions which combined above average grain yield and good stability as the most promising accessions for release (Adugna *et al.*, 2011). Azrai *et al.* (2022) studied genotype by environment interaction effect on 12 maize hybrids evaluated in 14 environments using the GGE biplot model. The biplot revealed two-mega environments and five vertex genotypes. Asungre *et al.* (2022) quantified the magnitude of G \times E in 24 single-cross pearl millet hybrids evaluated in four environments in northern Ghana. They identified three high-yielding and stable hybrids while four hybrids had high grain iron and zinc content using the AMMI model. Kebede *et al.* (2023) used the GGE biplot to analyze genotype by environment interaction in 24 oat genotypes evaluated in nine environments in Ethiopia. The authors identified seven oat genotypes that combined high mean grain yield with high stability and recommended them as broadly adapted genotypes. The GGE biplot was also used by Kondombo *et al.* (2024) to analyze the effect of genotype \times environment interaction in nine sorghum genotypes evaluated in five environments in Burkina Faso. Based on the biplot, they grouped the genotypes into stable and unstable and identified genotypes with specific adaptation.

2.10.4 Genotype × environment interaction in fonio

The effect of genotype × environment interaction on fonio grain yield and other agronomic traits have not been extensively studied compared to cereals such as maize. Addai *et al.* (2022) examined the effect of genotype × environment interaction on fonio grain yield by evaluating five accessions in two test locations in northern Ghana. They found significant genotype × environment interaction effect for some growth components. On the contrary, their study found no significant genotype × environment interaction for grain yield. Since their data was analyzed using analysis of variance (ANOVA) method only, the genotype × environment interaction component, a non-additive term in the model, cannot be decomposed to capture well the response of genotype in the interaction term. To account for this deficiency in using ANOVA to analyze genotype × environment data, the GGE biplot model comes in handy to examine the magnitude of the effect of genotype × environment interaction on fonio grain yield and other agronomic traits to better understand the impact of variations in environmental conditions on fonio cultivation in Ghana.

CHAPTER THREE

3.1 GENETIC CHARACTERIZATION OF FONIO ACCESSIONS USING SIMPLE SEQUENCE REPEAT (SSR) MARKERS

3.1.1 INTRODUCTION

Genetic diversity analysis is an important pre-breeding activity geared towards deployment of efficient conservation strategies and effective utilization of crop genetic resources in a changing world (Adjebeng-Danquah *et al.* 2020; Govindaraj *et al.* 2015). This is particularly important for indigenous species which have been neglected by research although they have the potential to play important roles regarding global changes.

Fonio (*Digitaria exilis* (Kippist) Stapf) stands out among neglected crops as a vital grain cereal, indigenous to West Africa, where millions rely on it for essential food and nutritional security (Adoukonou-Sagbadja *et al.*, 2007b; Cruz *et al.*, 2016, Gari, 2002). This crop plays a pivotal role in the cropping and food systems of numerous West African farm families. Its significance becomes evident in mitigating hunger during food shortages, as most fonio cultivars exhibit early maturation, ensuring a timely food source for farmers while waiting for the harvest of other staple crops (Adoukonou-Sagbadja *et al.*, 2006; Clottey *et al.*, 2006a; Diop *et al.*, 2018; Vodouhe *et al.*, 2007). Fonio's importance transcends its role as a staple; it is recognized as a climate-smart crop, demonstrating resilience in the face of intermittent drought and thriving in environments with marginal soils and poor fertility (Gari, 2002; Vodouhe *et al.*, 2007).

While fonio is acknowledged for its potential to be a crucial asset for smallholder farmers in adapting to global changes, the genetic diversity of this crop remains inadequately understood, especially in Ghana, where comprehensive research is notably lacking. Within the country, fonio production is predominantly concentrated in the northeastern region, where it holds significance as a favored crop among ethnic groups such as Anufor, Konkomba, Kabre, Dagomba, and Bassare (Addai *et al.*, 2022; Clottey *et al.*, 2006a). Fonio is grown for both subsistence and commercial purposes. Generally, fonio production relies on traditional methods such as seed broadcasting and with low external input use. For many farmers, then, fonio is cultivated mainly for

home consumption even though surplus grains are sold for income. In Ghana, commercial fonio production is experiencing a steady rise, driven by the active involvement of companies engaged in the comprehensive cycle of production, processing, and marketing of fonio. These enterprises are strategically positioned to meet both local and international demands for this valuable cereal. The international demand is increasing notably due to the awareness of the high nutrient composition and the numerous uses of the grains (Jideani & Jideani, 2011).

The increasing local and international demands for fonio grains call for new market-oriented breeding programs. But for now, those programs cannot be implemented due to a lack of biological knowledge on fonio and on its genetic diversity. Indeed, there is very little information on the genetic diversity of the Ghanaian fonio accessions and no fonio cultivar has been released and or registered for cultivation in Ghana. An earlier investigation to understand the Ghanaian fonio genetic diversity focussed on 18 accessions only, using agro-morphological markers (Clottey *et al.*, 2006b). Later some accessions from Ghana were either resequenced (Abrouk *et al.*, 2020) or genotyped with SSR markers for large scale characterization of fonio genetic diversity and population structure across West Africa (Kaczmarek *et al.*, 2023). Kaczmarek *et al.* (2023) analyzed the genetic diversity of 1,539 accessions genotyped, of which 118 originated from Ghana. Interestingly, this analysis revealed a distinctiveness of some of these Ghanaian accessions as compared to other producing countries. But to date, no research has specifically focused and analyzed the genetic diversity and associated knowledge of fonio in Ghana. This calls for an in-depth characterization of Ghanaian fonio.

The aim of this experiment is to describe the genetic diversity of Ghanaian fonio. It proposes to explore usual genetic diversity parameters such as the number of alleles, the allele frequencies, the observed (H_o) and expected heterozygosity (H_e). It pays specific attention to the organization of the fonio genetic diversity, considering biological, environmental and social factors. Recently, Diop *et al.* (2023) noted in Senegal that the spatial organization of genetic diversity of fonio was associated with farmers' linguistic family. This is also the case for other crops where recent investigations have highlighted the influence of socio-cultural factors such as ethnicity and farmers' seed exchange systems (Delêtre *et al.*, 2011; Labeyrie *et al.*, 2014;

Leclerc & Coppens d'Eeckenbrugge, 2011; Naino Jika *et al.*, 2017; Orozco-Ramírez *et al.*, 2016).

The local Ghanaian context of fonio cultivation raises many questions. Is fonio genetic diversity structured as a function of ethnic groups? Is it resulting from isolation by distance? Is it partitioned according to farmers' cultivars? This last question is crucial as it is associated with the dynamics of *in-situ* fonio conservation in Ghana. A better understanding of *in-situ* fonio diversity at the local scale considering social factors is crucial to understand the evolutionary social process shaping fonio genetic diversity and thus to define conservation and breeding strategies.

3.1.2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1.2.1 Farmer survey and germplasm collection

Farmer survey and fonio germplasm collection were conducted in the main fonio-growing areas of Ghana, in the North East region in June 2021 (Appendix 1) and the Northern region in December 2021 (Appendix 1), in collaboration with staff of the Department of Agriculture, who served as interpreters and helped to define the sampling strategy. The purposive sampling strategy, a non-probability sampling method where units are selected because they possess characteristics that are needed in the sample, was used to target fonio growing communities in the five districts. Within these five districts, 24 communities actively engaged in fonio cultivation were targeted. Only farmers who cultivated fonio in the previous season, and thus considered to be active growers and could provide seed samples were interviewed (Appendix 2).

Community entry sensitization was carried out with the community leaders to seek their consent before conducting the surveys in the villages. The same approach was performed for each farmer providing information and/or seed samples. The farmers signed an informed consent form for each accession collected enabling their use for research purposes. Personal information and identity of the respondents were anonymized in the database.

A total of 165 farmers were surveyed across 24 communities, in five districts in the area where fonio is a popular crop (Chereponi, Saboba, Zabzugu, Gushegu, and Tatale). Those farmers belong to four ethnic groups, namely Anufor (121 farmers mainly from Chereponi district), Konkomba (30 farmers mainly from Saboba district), Kabre (10 farmers from Zabzugu district), and Dagomba (4 farmers from Gushegu district).

The farms were located at similar elevation above sea level (152 ± 50 m at 0.95 CI). Farmers surveyed represent all the age classes, from 20 to 60, with 15 farmers over 60 years. Mainly men were interviewed (142 men against 34 women). Men oversaw fonio selection, field preparation, seed sowing, harvesting, and threshing while women oversaw dehusking, winnowing and cooking (Personal observation, Richard Yaw Agyare). A semi-structured questionnaire was used to obtain socio-cultural information such as ethnicity, age, gender, marital status, educational level, etc (Appendix 3). Their geographical location was recorded using a hand-held GPS device (Garmin GPSMAP 64X). In addition, knowledge on fonio cultivation, e.g. local cultivar names, phenology, and noteworthy traits and years of cultivation were captured. Origin of the first seed lots for each farmers' cultivar, and source of seed used in the last season were also noted.

Fonio seeds were sampled from the seed stock of the farmers (harvested from the previous season) preserved into zip-lock plastic bags and labeled. A total of 176 accessions were collected from 165 farmers in 24 communities, constituting the largest fonio germplasm collection in Ghana (Table 3.1.1). The accessions were first planted in an observational trial and were thoroughly observed to eliminate off-type plants. Single plant selections were then made per accession from which seeds were harvested and multiplied for other research purposes.

The fonio accessions are conserved at CSIR-Savanna Agricultural Research Institute and duplicates were added to the global collection conserved at the Biological Resource Center, Seeds Adapted to Mediterranean and Tropical conditions, CIRAD-INRAE, ARCAD, Montpellier-France, for long-term conservation.

3.1.2.2 Sample preparation, DNA extraction and SSR genotyping

The 176 fonio accessions were grown in a growth chamber. Fresh leaf samples from fully opened leaves were sampled from a single plant per accession. Total genomic DNA extractions were performed from dried leaves by an automated method adapted from (Risterucci *et al.*, 2009) on Biomek FXP (Beckman Coulter, CA, USA) and using the NucleoMag Plant Kit (Macherey–Nagel, Germany).

The leaves were harvested when the plants were large enough to collect 100 mg of leaves from a single plant. The leaf samples were placed in 96 deep-well plates with 1.0 ml round-bottomed wells into which two 2 mm steel balls were added. The samples were then freeze-dried for 48 hours. Grinding was done by using an automated grinder (Geno Grinder, Spex Sample Prep Company) with a strong vertical clamp movement of 1200 strokes/minute for 3 minutes. The ground samples were kept under room temperature until DNA extraction.

Genomic DNA extraction

Total genomic DNA extractions were performed in 96 deep-well plates by an automated method adapted from Risterucci *et al.* (2009) on Biomek FXP (Beckman Coulter, CA, USA) and using the NucleoMag Plant Kit (Macherey–Nagel, Germany) as described below:

Tissue lysis was carried out in a buffer made up of 100mL/L Tris HCl (1M, pH=8), 280 mL/L NaCl (5M), 40 mL/L EDTA (0.5M, pH=8), 20 g/L MATAB (Mixed Alkyl Trimethyl Ammonium Bromide), 10 g/L PEG6000 and 5 g/L Na₂SO₃. The lysis buffer (400 µl) was added to the leaf samples and incubated at 75°C for 1 hour with intermittent shaking every 10 minutes. After the lysis step, the samples were left to cool to 37-40°C. 2 mg RNase A was added to each well and samples were incubated at 37°C for 30 minutes. The samples were centrifuged at 4000 rpm for 30 minutes to obtain a clear supernatant, free of suspended particles.

Table 3.1.1 Information on accessions and locations of collection

Region	District	Communities	Ethnicity of farmers	Number of Accessions	Accession names
North East	Chereponi	Sangbana	Anufor	15	<i>Yadema</i> (13), <i>Namba</i> (2)
North East	Chereponi	Banjani	Anufor	14	<i>Yadema</i> (11), <i>Namba</i> (3)
North East	Chereponi	Ando Nyamanu	Anufor	19	<i>Yadema</i> (14), <i>Namba</i> (4), <i>Nvonikpa</i> (1)
North East	Chereponi	Tosala-Kombonli	Anufor	11	<i>Yadema</i> (9), <i>Fefeke</i> (2)
North East	Chereponi	Bulasu	Anufor	7	<i>Yadema</i> (7)
North East	Chereponi	Kudani	Anufor	16	<i>Yadema</i> (9), <i>Namba</i> (2), <i>Fefeke</i> (5)
North East	Chereponi	Wonjuga	Anufor	16	<i>Yadema</i> (1), <i>Namba</i> (6), <i>Fieja</i> (2), <i>Namba bieso</i> (5), <i>Namba bala</i> (2)
North East	Chereponi	Ando Nderenu	Anufor	13	<i>Yadema</i> (11), <i>Nvonikpa</i> (1), <i>Kpentike</i> (1)
North East	Chereponi	Naturi	Anufor	9	<i>Yadema</i> (4), <i>Namba</i> (5)
North East	Chereponi	Chombosu Angor	Anufor	2	<i>Nvonikpa</i> (2)
Northern	Gushegu	Nayugu	Dagomba	2	<i>Kabga</i> (2)
Northern	Gushegu	Villi	Dagomba	2	<i>Kabga</i> (1), no idea (1)
Northern	Saboba	Liwalbu	Konkomba	8	<i>Ipui</i> (3), <i>Yadema</i> (1), <i>Ipui piln</i> (1), <i>Ipui bolne</i> (3)
Northern	Saboba	Timbu	Konkomba	2	<i>Ipui maln</i> (2)
Northern	Saboba	Yawbuesu	Anufor	2	<i>Namba</i> (1), <i>Nvonikpa</i> (1)
Northern	Saboba	Nakpel Konkomba	Konkomba	5	<i>Ipui Ukabreja</i> (1), <i>Ukabreja</i> (2), <i>Ipui piln</i> (1), <i>Ipui maln</i> (1)
Northern	Saboba	Gbangbanpong	Konkomba/Anufor	6	<i>Yadema</i> (3), <i>Ukabreja</i> (2), <i>Ipui maln</i> (1)
Northern	Saboba	Sanguli	Konkomba	2	<i>Ukabreja</i> (1), <i>Ipui maln</i> (1)
Northern	Saboba	Tilangbeni	Konkomba	3	<i>Ipui maln</i> (3)
Northern	Saboba	Toma	Konkomba	5	<i>Ukabreja</i> (1), <i>Ipui maln</i> (4)
Northern	Tatale	Kpalbutabu	Konkomba	4	<i>Ipui</i> (1), <i>Ipui piln</i> (3)
Northern	Tatale	Nkalingbani	Konkomba	1	<i>Ipui maln</i> (1)
Northern	Zabzugu	Mangoase	Kabre	8	<i>Kafia</i> (2), <i>Yoona</i> (1), <i>Semiri</i> (4), <i>Senbre</i> (1)
Northern	Zabzugu	Kpalgagbini	Kabre	4	<i>Afiang</i> (3), <i>Yahran</i> (1)

DNA purification

Purification uses the principle of capturing nucleic acids on magnetic beads. The procedure used was as follows:

DNA binding to magnetic silica beads:

Three hundred microlitres of lysis supernatant was dispensed into a new 96 deep-well plate before adding the binding buffer. Add 300 μl of isopropanol + 20 μl beads (NucleoMag® C-Beads Macherey-Nagel) to each well. Ring the magnetic beads on the magnetic support and remove the supernatant.

Three wash cycles with 3 different buffers (MC3, MC4 and 80% ethanol) were performed. Add 80 μl of MC3 buffer and ring on the magnetic beads on the magnetic support for 2 minutes and remove the supernatant. Add 80 μl of MC4 buffer and ring on the magnetic beads on the magnetic support for 2 minutes and pipette the supernatant. Add 80 μl of ethanol buffer and ring on the magnetic beads on the magnetic support for two minutes and remove the supernatant.

DNA elution and quality control

To elute the DNA, 100 μl of MC6 elution buffer was added to the supernatant and heated for 20 minutes at 50°C. The samples were agitated at 700 rpm for 10 minutes. The supernatant (DNA) was recovered into 96-well plates and stored at 4°C. The DNA quantity was checked by fluorometric assay with a standard range from 0 to 250 ng while the DNA quality was checked on 1% agarose gel electrophoresis.

Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR)

A total of 14 simple sequence repeat (SSR) nuclear markers (Barnaud *et al.*, 2012) were used for genotyping the fonio accessions (Appendix 4). PCR amplification was carried out in an ABI PRISM 3730 DNA Analyzer (Applied Biosystems, Foster City, CA, USA). The details of the PCR amplification were as follows:

PCR was performed in 10 μl mixture comprising 2.5 ng (5 μl of 0.5 ng/ μl) DNA, 1X FIREPol® 10x Buffer B (0.8 M Tris-HCl, 0.2 M (NH₄)₂SO₄, 0.2% w/v Tween-20), 1 mM MgCl₂, 200 μM dNTPs, 0.15 μM reverse primer, 0.12 μM M13-tailed forward primer, 0.15 μM M13 primer fluorescently labeled with FAM (blue), VIC (green), PET (red), NED (yellow), 0.04 mg/ml BSA, 1X of 10x Solution S that is an additive

that facilitates the amplification of difficult templates (e.g. GC-rich DNA templates) and 0.6 U/ μ L FIREPol® DNA Polymerase (5 U/ μ L in 20 mM Tris-HCl pH 8.7 at 25°C, 100 mM KCl, 0.1 mM EDTA, 50% glycerol (v/v), and stabilizers).

The PCR amplification was performed with an initial denaturation step at 94°C for 4 min. This was followed by 10 cycles of a touchdown step with denaturation at 94°C for 45 sec, annealing at $T_m+5^\circ\text{C}$ (-0.5°C/cycle) for 60 sec and extension at 72°C for 75 sec. This was followed by 25 cycles of denaturation at 94°C for 45 sec, annealing at T_m for 60 sec, extension at 72°C for 75 sec and final extension for 30 min at 72°C.

Multiplexing of PCR products

The PCR products were multiplexed based on the markers' allelic range and fluorescently labeled markers comprising 2 μ l FAM (blue), 2.5 μ l NED (yellow), 3.5 μ l PET (red) and 2 μ l VIC (green). The final volume for multiplexing was 20 μ l.

Migration of PCR products on fragment analyser

To create denaturing conditions for migration on an ABI 3500xL Prism (Applied Biosystems) 2 μ l of multiplexes were added to 10 μ l of a mixture of formamide and ladder (1 ml of formamide + 12 μ l of DNA ladder GeneScan 600 LIZ size standard for 96 samples, ladder range size: 20 to 600 bp).

The PCR products were migrated on PRISM 3730 DNA Analyzer (Applied Biosystems, Foster City, CA), is a multi-capillary electrophoresis instrument, which separates the PCR products based on their size to charge ratio. An electrical pulse activates the migration and separation of the DNA through the capillary. The DNA fragments had fluorescently labelled primers (FAM, NED, PET and VIC) attached so that a narrow beam of light from the laser excites the dyes after going through the detection window. A CCD detector detects the colour of the light emission based on the wavelength in a form of a peak. In addition to an internal size standard and allelic ladder, a software program analyses the peaks that are detected and assigns specific allele designations to each locus. The combinations of all fluorescent peaks form an electropherogram. The genotyping data were scored and verified twice with the GeneMapper version 6 (Applied Biosystems, Foster City, CA, USA). Appendix 5

shows an electropherogram of fonio accession S040401 genotyped with SSR markers De_19 and De_22. Fonio accessions presenting more than three missing SSR genotypes were removed from the genetic analyses. Genetic analysis was thus based on 140 accessions, whereas farmer and social data analysis was based on 176 accessions.

DNA extraction and genotyping were carried out at the AGAP Institut laboratory, CIRAD, Montpellier, France.

3.1.2.3 Data analysis

Data were analyzed using packages in R software version 4.2.2 (R Core Team, 2022).

3.1.2.3.1 Genetic diversity analysis

To estimate the level of genetic diversity of each SSR locus among the fonio accessions, the *adegenet* v. 2.1.10 (Jombart, 2008) and *pegas* v. 1.2 (Paradis, 2010) R packages were used to compute the number of alleles, the allele frequencies, the observed (H_o) and expected heterozygosity (H_e). Polymorphism information content was computed according to Botstein *et al.* (1980). The number of alleles, the observed and expected heterozygosity and allelic richness (A_r) were again computed according to group level - community and farmers' ethnic group and farmer cultivar - with the *matrixStats* version 0.63.0 (Bengtsson *et al.*, 2023) R package. To account for the variability in group sizes, allelic richness was computed by averaging the calculation of 1000 randomly drawn iterations of 4 accessions and was not calculated for groups fewer than four accessions. Allelic richness was compared using pairwise t-tests (1000 iterations, with Bonferroni p adjusted method). The Mean inbreeding coefficient, F_{IS} , was estimated with *hierfstat* v. 0.5-11 (Goudet *et al.*, 2022) R package and the significant deviation from 0 was assessed using 1000 over loci with the *boot.ppfis* function.

3.1.2.3.2 Genetic structure analysis

Principal component analysis (PCA) was performed with the *dudi.pca* function in the *ade4* v. 1.7-22 (Dray & Dufour, 2007) R package. Data were first scaled with the *scaleGen* function in the *adegenet* v. 2.1.10 (Jombart, 2008) R package and missing

data were replaced with mean allele frequencies. The *ggplot2* v. 3.4.2 (Wickham, 2016) and *factoextra* v. 1.0.7 (Kassambara & Mundt, 2020) R packages were used to plot the PCA.

The sparse Non-negative Matrix Factorization (sNMF) method implemented in the *LEA* v. 3.10.2 (Frichot & Francois, 2015) R package was used for population structure analysis. Ten (10) independent repetitions for each K value (1-10) with a maximal number of iterations of 200 were run. The cross-entropy criterion (lowest cross-entropy) was used to determine the optimal number of ancestral populations (Appendix 6) and membership of groups was based on 0.70 or higher ancestry coefficient. Individuals with less than 0.70 ancestry coefficient for a group were considered as admixed. To validate the population structure among the fonio accessions, the discriminant analysis of principal components (DAPC) method for performing structure analysis was performed with the *dapc* function in *adegenet* v. 2.1.10 (Jombart *et al.* 2010) R package. Structuring was done without a priori grouping (K-means clustering) of the accessions with defined factors. The *find.clusters* function in *adegenet* 2.1.10 (Jombart *et al.* 2010) R package was used to run successive K-means with 100,000 iterations for each run. 50 principal components (PCs) were retained (chosen interactively from the console) based on the graph of cumulative variance explained by the eigenvalues of PCA at the plateau level (Appendix 7A). Also, four linear discriminants were retained based on the Discriminant analysis eigenvalues. The measure of goodness of fit, Bayesian Information Criterion (lowest BIC), computed for each model was used to select the optimal number of K clusters that best describes the population (Appendix 7B). The structuring based on DAPC and sNMF methods were compared using a contingency table (Appendix 8).

A Chi-squared, χ^2 , test with Monte-Carlo simulation was conducted to detect significant associations between genetic clusters inferred with sNMF and social or biological factors. An analysis of molecular variance (AMOVA) was performed with the *poppr* v 2.9.4 (Kamvar *et al.* 2014) R package to analyse how much of the variance was explained by the different social components of fonio accessions (ethnicity of farmer, farmer cultivar). Finally, to avoid confounding factors, the Anufor ethnic group (100 accessions) was focused on and a hierarchical cluster analysis according to neighbor joining clustering of Nei's genetic distance was conducted with the *poppr* v. 2.9.4 (Kamvar *et al.* 2014) R package. The unrooted tree was represented using the *ggtree* v. 3.6.2 (Yu, 2022) R package.

3.1.2.3.3 Isolation by distance

The extent of fonio seed exchange was assessed by testing for isolation by distance (IBD) patterns, *that is*, whether genetic differentiation (F_{ST})/(1- F_{ST}) among communities was correlated with geographical distance (Rousset, 1997). Genetic distance, F_{ST} , was estimated using the hierfstat v. 0.5-11 (Goudet *et al.*, 2022) R package. The genetic distance matrix (F_{ST})/(1- F_{ST}) was plotted against the geographical distance using MASS version 7.3-58.1 (Venables & Ripley, 2010) and geodist version 0.0.8 (Padgham, 2021) R packages. A total of 1,000 Mantel tests were conducted with the adegenet v. 2.1.10 (Jombart, 2008) R package between the two distant matrices to determine whether the relationship between genetic and geographical distances between communities were at random or not.

3.1.2.3.4 Comparison of the Ghanaian fonio germplasm with the global fonio diversity

To compare the genetic diversity of fonio accessions from Ghana to the global fonio diversity, the genetic dataset produced by Kaczmarek *et al.* (2023) consisting of 1539 fonio accessions was retrieved. 118 Ghanaian accessions common in the two investigations were first selected. To have a balanced sampling with Ghana and a representative fonio cultivation area across West Africa, two other sets of 118 accessions were selected with the kenstone algorithm from prospectr v. 0.2.6 (Stevens & Ramirez-Lopez, 2022) R package that allows the sampling of a subset of accessions by maximizing the geographic range of their distribution. The algorithm was run on the Western part (Senegal, Mali, Burkina Faso, Ivory Coast, Guinea) and Eastern part (Togo, Benin, Niger, Nigeria) of Ghana. A principal component analysis was performed on a total of 354 accessions originating from nine countries.

3.1.3 RESULTS

3.1.3.1 Characteristics of the farmer-named cultivars of fonio

In the research area, 21 farmer-named cultivars of fonio were inventoried (Appendix 9). Majority of the 165 farmers surveyed (94 % of farmers) cultivated one cultivar, with a mean of six cultivars per ethnic group. Fonio was mainly grown by men (81 %) irrespective of the age class (Appendix 10). Cultivar richness was higher among Anufor farmers (nine cultivars), as compared to Konkomba (seven cultivars), Kabre (six cultivars) and Dagomba (one cultivar). Each farmer's cultivar belonged almost exclusively to one ethnic group. Anufor and Konkomba farmers have been cultivating fonio for a longer period (average of 20 and 15 years, respectively) than Kabre and Dagomba farmers (average of 3 and 1 years, respectively). About 45 % of the fonio cultivars were considered by farmers to have high yield, 24 % to be easy to dehusk. The nutritional value of fonio as a noteworthy trait in a cultivar was not mentioned, except by a few farmers. The length of the cultivation cycle was 3 months for 56 % of cultivars; 18 % were less and 26 % over three months.

The names of farmers' cultivars were usually motivated (Appendix 11) with an explicit reference to ethnic groups (*Namba* and *Ukabreja* refer to the Namba and Ukabreja ethnic groups in Togo), to people (*Yadema* refers to the name of the former president of Togo, Gnassingbe Eyadema), or to notable morphological features. For instance, among the Konkomba ethnic group, some of the names were based on their distinctive pericarp color such as *Ipui bolne* (black skin fonio), *Ipui maln* (red skin fonio) and *Ipui piln* (white skin fonio). Names such as *Fefeke* and *Kafia* or *Semiri* connotes early maturity in Anufor and Kabre respectively.

Fonio was cultivated mainly for household consumption. 59.5 % of the collected seed lots were produced for food while 36.9 % were produced for both food and income, and 3.6 % solely for sale (Appendix 12). Source of seeds for planting was mainly obtained from the household. Indeed, 89.7 % of seed lots were self produced by farmers, while 7.3 % were obtained from a company, who had previously obtained them from the Chereponi district, and 3 % from friends in neighboring communities (Appendix 12).

By tracing for each cultivar, the origin of the initial seed lots, a diverse range of sources were recorded. The origin of the initial cultivar seed lots corresponded to the sources through which the cultivars that are cultivated today were initially acquired. Among the Anufor, about 56 % of farmers indicated that their initial cultivar seed lots originated from Togo, and 2 % originated from Côte d'Ivoire. 42 % of farmers did not know from which source they initially obtained the cultivar's seed lots (Appendix 12). For Dagomba farmers, the origin of initial seed lots were traced back to a company involved in the production and marketing of fonio in Ghana. The majority of Konkomba farmers (85.2 %) did not know from which source they obtained their first seed lots. 11.1 % were obtained from a company, and 3.7 %, representing only one seed lot, from Togo. Similarly, among Kabre farmers, most of their cultivar seed lots were initially obtained from a company, 11.2% from Togo, and 33.3 % of seed lot origin were unknown.

3.1.3.2 Genetic diversity of fonio

A total of 79 alleles were observed with an average of 3.27 % missing data per locus (Table 3.1.2). The number of alleles per locus ranged from 2 to 24 with a mean of 6.58 alleles per locus. Two markers De_07 and De_22 were monomorphic.

Thirty-three duplicates partitioned in nine groups, i.e. accessions genetically identical according to the marker used, were identified among the accessions (Appendix 13). It ranged from two to ten accessions per group, and six groups were composed of accessions collected from at least two districts.

SSR markers De_15, De_17 and De_38 exhibited the lowest number of alleles per locus (2) while locus De_04 showed the highest (24). The major allele frequency ranged from 0.22 (De_37) to 0.99 (locus De_15). Observed heterozygosity (H_o) varied from 0 to 0.22 with a mean of 0.08 and Expected heterozygosity (H_e) from 0.03 to 0.89 with a mean of 0.37. SSR locus De_24 (0.22) had the highest observed heterozygosity while the highest expected heterozygosity was observed for locus De_37 (0.89). Polymorphism information content (PIC) ranged from 0.03 (De_15, 2 alleles with a MAF of 0.99) to 0.88 (De_37, 19 alleles with a MAF of 0.22) with a mean of 0.35. Locus De_37 (0.88) was the most polymorphic, followed by De_04 (0.68).

Table 3.1.2 Diversity statistics of 12 SSR loci assayed on 140 fonio accessions

Locus	N_a	MAF	H_o	H_e	PIC
De_04	24	0.53	0.21	0.70	0.68
De_05	3	0.89	0.06	0.18	0.17
De_08	3	0.89	0.09	0.20	0.18
De_15	2	0.99	0.00	0.03	0.03
De_17	2	0.92	0.02	0.15	0.14
De_24	7	0.38	0.22	0.71	0.66
De_25	7	0.58	0.10	0.61	0.58
De_29	4	0.91	0.01	0.17	0.16
De_34	3	0.97	0.01	0.07	0.06
De_36	3	0.65	0.10	0.49	0.41
De_37	19	0.22	0.12	0.89	0.88
De_38	2	0.87	0.04	0.23	0.20
Total alleles	79				
Missing data (%)	3.27				
Mean	6.58		0.08	0.37	0.35

N_a = number of alleles per locus; MAF = Major allele frequency; H_o = Observed heterozygosity; H_e = Expected heterozygosity; PIC = polymorphism information content

At the community level, the highest average number of alleles per locus was observed for Ando Nyamanu (3.83 alleles) while the lowest was observed for Sanguli (one allele) (Table 3.1.3). Significant differences (t-test, adj. $p < 0.05$) in observed heterozygosity existed between Gbangbanpong (0.23) and all the communities except Nayugu and Wonjuga with observed heterozygosity of 0.13 and 0.18 respectively. Expected heterozygosity ranged from zero (Sanguli) to 0.43 (Toma). Significant difference (t-test, adj. $p = 0.0278$) in expected heterozygosity existed between only Toma and Sanguli. Allelic richness was computed for communities with at least 4 accessions and ranged between 1.46 (Banjani) and 2.34 (Toma). Significant differences (t-test, adj. $p < 0.001$) in allelic richness existed among most of the communities. Allelic richness between Ando Nderenu and Kudani, Ando Nyamanu and Liwalbu, Bulasu and Liwalbu, Ando Nderenu and Naturi, Kudani and Naturi, Kpalgabini and Sangbana, Gbangbanpong and Tosala Kombonli, Kpalgabeni and Wonjuga, Sangbana and Wonjuga were not significantly different (t-test, adj. $p >$

0.05). In the case of F_{IS} , the lowest average F_{IS} was observed in Gbangbanpong (0.37, confidence interval = 0.95).

At the ethnicity level, the lowest average number of alleles per locus was recorded from farmers belonging to the Dagomba ethnic group (2.08) while the highest was from farmers belonging to Anufor ethnic group (5.75). The average number of alleles per locus among accessions from Konkomba and Kabre ethnic groups were 3.92 and 2.50 respectively. Observed heterozygosity ranged from 0.06 (Konkomba) to 0.09 (Anufor and Kabre). Expected heterozygosity was highest among accessions collected from the Konkomba ethnic group (0.45). However, no significant differences were observed among accessions from the ethnic groups for both observed and expected heterozygosity. Allelic richness significantly differed (t-test, adj. $p < 0.001$) among the ethnic groups except for accessions obtained from Dagomba and Konkomba farmers (t-test, adj. $p > 0.05$). Allelic richness ranged from 1.83 to 2.10 for Anufor and Konkomba ethnic groups respectively. In the case of inbreeding coefficient, higher values were observed within each ethnic group.

At the farmer-named cultivar level, the average number of alleles per locus ranged from 1.00 (*Ipui Ukabreja*, *Kpentike*, *Yahran* and *No idea*) to 5.42 (*Yadema*). No significant differences (t-test, adj. $p > 0.05$) were observed among the farmers' cultivars for observed heterozygosity (Table 3.1.3). It ranged from 0.00 (*Ipui Ukabreja*, *Yahran* and *No idea*) to 0.27 (*Fieja* and *Senbre*). In the case of expected heterozygosity, it varied from 0.00 to 0.45. Significant differences (t-test, adj. $p < 0.05$) in expected heterozygosity were observed among *Ipui maln* and *Ipui Ukabreja* (t-test, adj. $p < 0.01$), *Ipui maln* and *Kafia* (t-test, adj. $p < 0.04$), *Ipui maln* and *No idea* (t-test, adj. $p < 0.01$), *Ipui maln* and *Yahran* (t-test, adj. $p < 0.01$), *Ukabreja* and *Ipui Ukabreja* (t-test, adj. $p < 0.01$), *Ukabreja* and *No idea* (t-test, adj. $p < 0.01$) and *Ukabreja* and *Yahran* (t-test, adj. $p < 0.01$). Allelic richness significantly differed among the farmers' cultivars except between *Ipui piln* (1.83) and *Namba* (1.86). It ranged from 1.13 (*Ukabreja*) to 2.32 (*Ipui maln*). The lowest inbreeding coefficient was observed in *Ipui* (0.52) while the highest (0.94) was observed in *Ipui piln*.

Table 3.1.3 Genetic diversity of 140 fonio accessions using grouping factors

Factor	N_o	N_a	H_o	H_e	Ar (Sd)	F_{IS}
Community						
Sangbana	13	3.50	0.09	0.30	1.93 (0.32)	0.70
Banjani	13	2.00	0.07	0.20	1.46 (0.21)	0.66
Ando-Nyamanu	19	3.83	0.05	0.33	1.84 (0.22)	0.85
Tosala-Kombonli	10	3.08	0.12	0.31	2.07 (0.25)	0.66
Bulasu	6	2.25	0.05	0.31	1.87 (0.14)	0.89
Kudani	9	2.17	0.09	0.25	1.69 (0.13)	0.61
Wonjuga	8	2.50	0.18	0.35	1.94 (0.21)	0.49
Ando-Nderenu	11	2.33	0.08	0.25	1.68 (0.22)	0.69
Naturi	7	2.00	0.06	0.29	1.67 (0.19)	0.82
Nayugu	2	1.75	0.13	0.28	NA	0.75
Villi	2	1.33	0.04	0.16	NA	0.86
Liwalbu	7	2.17	0.07	0.34	1.86 (0.12)	0.81
Timbu	2	1.50	0.00	0.25	NA	1.00
Yawbuesu	2	1.50	0.04	0.22	NA	0.90
Nakpel-Konkomba	3	1.75	0.00	0.30	NA	1.00
Gbangbanpong	5	2.25	0.23	0.36	2.09 (0.12)	0.37
Sanguli	1	1.00	0.00	0.00	NA	NA
Tilangbeni	2	1.42	0.00	0.21	NA	1.00
Toma	5	2.58	0.08	0.43	2.34 (0.15)	0.84
Kpalbutabu	4	1.75	0.10	0.21	1.75 (0.00)	0.52
Mangoase	5	2.17	0.10	0.31	1.98 (0.10)	0.72
Kpalgagbini	4	1.92	0.06	0.34	1.92 (0.00)	0.76
Ethnicity						
Anufor	100	5.75	0.09	0.32	1.83 (0.27)	0.71
Dagomba	4	2.08	0.08	0.31	2.08 (2.71)	0.79
Konkomba	27	3.92	0.06	0.45	2.10 (0.22)	0.85
Kabre	9	2.50	0.09	0.30	1.91 (0.13)	0.77

N_o= Number of accessions; N_a= average number of alleles per locus; H_o= Observed heterozygosity; H_e= Expected heterozygosity; Ar (Sd) = Allelic richness as the mean of 1000 sampling of 4 accessions per group (Standard deviation); F_{IS} = Mean inbreeding coefficient (95% confidence interval). All values significantly differed from 0; NA= not applicable

Table 3.1.3 Continued

Factor	N_o	N_a	H_o	H_e	Ar(Sd)	F_{IS}
Farmer-named cultivar						
<i>Afiang</i>	3	1.67	0.08	0.28	NA	0.69
<i>Fefeke</i>	4	2.00	0.09	0.29	2.00 (0.00)	0.65
<i>Fieja</i>	1	1.17	0.27	0.21	NA	NA
<i>Ipui</i>	4	1.92	0.19	0.31	1.92 (0.00)	0.52
<i>Ipui bolne</i>	3	1.33	0.06	0.15	NA	0.73
<i>Ipui maln</i>	9	3.25	0.06	0.45	2.32 (0.18)	0.87
<i>Ipui piln</i>	4	1.83	0.02	0.25	1.83 (0.00)	0.94
<i>Ipui Ukabreja</i>	1	1.00	0.00	0.00	NA	NA
<i>Kabga</i>	3	1.92	0.11	0.27	NA	0.71
<i>Kafia</i>	1	1.08	0.08	0.04	NA	NA
<i>Kpentike</i>	1	1.00	0.09	0.13	NA	NA
<i>Namba</i>	17	3.17	0.07	0.35	1.86 (0.15)	0.78
<i>Namba bala</i>	2	1.67	0.13	0.28	NA	0.77
<i>Namba bieso</i>	2	1.50	0.18	0.31	NA	0.55
<i>Nvonikpa</i>	3	1.83	0.08	0.33	NA	0.84
<i>Semiri</i>	3	1.75	0.06	0.27	NA	0.86
<i>Senbre</i>	1	1.17	0.27	0.21	NA	NA
<i>Ukabreja</i>	6	2.58	0.11	0.44	1.13 (0.08)	0.74
<i>Yadema</i>	70	5.42	0.08	0.27	1.74 (0.27)	0.69
<i>Yahran</i>	1	1.00	0.00	0.00	NA	NA
<i>No idea</i>	1	1.00	0.00	0.00	NA	NA

N_o= Number of accessions; N_a= average number of alleles per locus; H_o= Observed heterozygosity; H_e= Expected heterozygosity; Ar (Sd) = Allelic richness as the mean of 1000 sampling of 4 accessions per group (Standard deviation); F_{IS} = Mean inbreeding coefficient (95% confidence interval). All values significantly differed from 0; NA= not applicable

3.1.3.3 Genetic structure analysis

3.1.3.3.1 Principal Component Analysis

Principal component analysis (PCA) revealed that 13.8 % of the total variability among the fonio accessions was accounted for by the first two dimensions (Fig 3.1.1). The first dimension of the plot, (8.9 %) differentiated the accessions into two groups. The first group was dominated by accessions collected from farmers belonging to the Anufor ethnic group (Fig 3.1.1a). Majority of these accessions mainly corresponded to the *Yadema* farmers' cultivar (Fig 3.1.1b). The second group consisted of accessions mainly from both Konkomba and Anufor ethnic groups (Fig 3.1.1a). The second dimension of the plot (4.9 %) separated this second group into two sub-groups: accessions mainly grown by Konkomba farmers, predominantly the *Ipui* farmer cultivar, and accessions from Anufor farmers, predominantly the *Namba* farmer cultivar (Fig 3.1.1b).

3.1.3.3.2 Population structure analysis

The population structure analysis using sparse non-negative matrix factorization (sNMF) method revealed an optimized sub-structured of $K = 6$ subpopulations (Appendix 6). The Discriminant analysis of principal components (DAPC) also revealed the optimal number of K clusters to be six (lowest Bayesian Information Criterion, BIC after retaining 50 principal components and 4 linear discriminants) (Appendix 7 C and D). The Chi-squared test with 2000 iterations and the Monte-Carlo test revealed significant (p value = 0.0004) association between the two clustering methods and confirmed the population structure of the 140 fonio accessions. The bar plots from $K = 2$ to $K = 6$ revealed that clustering of the accessions was mainly associated with genetic attributes of the accessions rather than the geographical location (Fig 3.1.2).

Figure 3.1.1 Principal component analysis of the 140 fonio accessions

a. Individuals are differentiated according to the farmer's ethnicity. **b.** Individuals are colored according to the farmer-named cultivar. All the farmer-named cultivars bearing *Ipui* names were grouped together and also for *Namba* farmer cultivar. Farmer-named cultivars that were minor were grouped together as *Other* and colored in grey

At $K = 2$, one subpopulation (pink color) was made up of 50 members with 50% of them collected from farmers belonging to the Anufor ethnic group. Farmers belonging to the Konkomba ethnic group supplied 34 % of the accessions while Kabre and Dagomba farmers provided 10 % and 6 % of the accessions respectively. Majority (72 %) of the accessions in this subpopulation were early maturing while 28 % of them were late maturing. A mixture of farmer-named cultivars composed this group. Subpopulation two (blue color) consisted of 90 accessions of which majority (83.4 %) were associated with farmers belonging to the Anufor ethnic group cultivating mostly the *Yadema* farmer cultivar, with early maturing cycle (Appendix 14). Other accessions of this group belonged to Konkomba (11.1 %) and Kabre (4.4 %) ethnic groups and are all early maturing. Only 1.1 % of accessions in this subpopulation was collected from a farmer belonging to the Dagomba ethnic group.

At $K = 3$, the accessions belonging to the blue subpopulation divided mainly into two groups. The first group consisted of 33 accessions (orange color) of which 79 % were associated with early maturity while 21% were late maturing cultivars. Apart from one accession from the Dagomba ethnic group, all the late maturing accessions in this subpopulation were associated with farmers belonging to the Anufor ethnic group. The second group had the highest number of individuals (60 accessions, blue color). Similarly, 75 % of these accessions were early maturing while 25 % were late maturing.

The pink cluster at $K = 3$ with 47 accessions largely divided into two clusters at $K = 4$. The first subpopulation (pink color) was composed of 20 individuals most of which were early maturing and associated with Anufor farmers cultivating the *Namba* cultivar. The second subpopulation (green color) had a total of 24 accessions. However, this subpopulation was composed of individuals with mixed maturity classes and majority of these accessions were associated with Konkomba farmers cultivating the *Ipui* cultivar.

At $K = 5$, the most significant is the division of the cluster with blue bar plots (67 accessions) at $K = 4$ into two to form the two largest subpopulations, blue and orange colored bar plots. It is also worthy to note the appearance of the cluster with the sky-blue bar plots with majority of them associated with Anufor farmers. All but one of these accessions were early maturing.

The fonio accessions subdivided into six ancestral populations at $K = 6$. To account for admixtures and determine the actual number of individuals within the six ancestral population, a membership coefficient of ≥ 0.70 was applied at $K = 6$. Sixty-four accessions constituting 45 % of the total population were classified as admixtures (Appendix 15). Subpopulation 1 consisted of three early maturing accessions (yellow bar plots). Subpopulation 2 had the largest number of accessions (28, blue bar plots) most of which were associated with Anufor farmers cultivating the *Yadema* farmers' cultivar. Subpopulation 3 comprised 25 accessions (orange bar plots) which predominantly correspond to the *Yadema* farmers' cultivar. Subpopulation 4 consisted of seven accessions (pink bar plots). These accessions were associated with farmers belonging to Anufor and Kabre ethnic groups cultivating the *Namba* farmer cultivar. Subpopulation 5 was made up of two accessions (sky blue bar plots) collected from farmers belonging to the Anufor ethnic group. In the case of subpopulation 6, majority of the accessions (green bar plots) were collected from Konkomba farmers cultivating the *Ipui* cultivar with heterogeneous maturity classes.

There was no significant association between the six clusters inferred at $K = 6$ and maturity (χ^2 test, p value = 0.40). However, there was significant association with the ethnicity of the farmers (χ^2 test, p value < 0.05, Appendix 16) and the farmer-named cultivar (χ^2 test, p value < 0.001). When conducting the hierarchical analysis of molecular variance (AMOVA) with ethnicity and farmer-named cultivar within ethnicity, 2.80 % of the genetic variation was due to the difference between ethnicity, while 16.83 % was due to the farmer cultivar within ethnicity (16.40 % without taking account of ethnicity). A large variation pertained between samples within farmers' cultivar with 58.52 %.

Figure 3.1.2 Population structure of 140 fonio accessions

The plot is based on sparse non-negative matrix factorization clustering with $K = 2$ (top plot) to $K = 6$ (bottom plot). Each bar plot on the X-axis represents an individual fonio accession. The Y-axis shows the ancestry proportions of the individuals

3.1.3.3.3 Hierarchical cluster analysis for Anufor ethnicity

Focusing on the main ethnic group cultivating fonio in Ghana, the farmer-named cultivar accounted for 17.52 % of the genetic variation, while 56.67 % of the variation remained between samples within farmers' cultivar (AMOVA). The neighbor-joining tree (unrooted) identified three main groups predominantly differentiating the two main cultivars cultivated by the Anufor: *Namba* and *Yadema* (Fig 3.1.3).

Figure 3.1.3 Genetic similarity of Anufor farmers' cultivar.

The plot was according to the neighbor-joining clustering of Nei's genetic distance and visualized with an unrooted tree

3.1.3.3.4 Isolation by Distance (IBD)

There was no IBD pattern detected between communities (Fig 3.1.4a, Mantel tests, $p = 0.48$, $R = -0.05$). The correlation between genetic differentiation (F_{ST})/(1- F_{ST}) and geographical distance is presented in Fig 3.1.4b. From the plot, the highest density of comparison among the fonio accessions was within a 20 km radius (Fig 3.1.4b). This shows that most of the accessions were collected in communities within districts less than 20 kilometres apart.

Figure 3.1.4 Isolation by distance analysis among 24 communities.

a. Histogram of permuted values obtained with 1,000 Mantel tests assessing correlation between geographical distance and genetic distance under absence of spatial structure. The dot represents the actual value of the correlation. **b.** IBD plot showing the relationship between genetic distance and geographical distance of fonio accessions. The dashed red line represents a linear regression

3.1.3.3.5 Genetic diversity of Ghanaian fonio germplasm in relation to the West African fonio diversity

To relate the genetic diversity among the Ghanaian fonio accessions to the global diversity in West Africa, a principal component analysis was performed. The first two principal component (PC) axes accounted for 7.07 % of the total variation (Fig 3.1.5). From PC1, fonio accessions from Togo, Nigeria, Mali and Guinea clustered separately from Ghanaian accessions. The Ghanaian accessions separated into two with one group clustering with accessions from other West African countries while the other group mainly accessions from the Chereponi district clustered alone. These accessions with PC1 values greater than 3% were nearly all homozygous (93%) for the De_36 marker with size 186 bp. This allele was almost exclusively present in Ghana, although it was found four times in Benin and Togo. The second PC axis separated accessions from Mali and those from Ghana, Nigeria, Togo and Benin. PC 3 axis accounted for 2.37 % of the total variability among the accessions (Appendix 17). This axis separated the Ghanaian accessions collected from Chereponi district from those of Benin and Guinea.

Figure 3.1.5 Principal component analysis of 354 fonio accessions.

The PC plot depicts the genetic relationship among the accessions from Ghana and other West African countries

3.1.4 DISCUSSION

In the studied area, 21 farmer-named fonio cultivars were cultivated mainly for household consumption. Each farmer-named cultivar belonged almost exclusively to one ethnic group, and the source of seeds for planting was mainly obtained from the household, i.e. farmer saved seeds. The diversity statistics observed in the research were lower than those of Diop *et al.* (2023) who reported a total of 132 alleles with a mean of 9.43 alleles per locus, mean observed heterozygosity of 0.05 and expected heterozygosity of 0.43 among 158 Senegalese fonio accessions using SSR markers. The higher average number of alleles per locus and mean expected heterozygosity from their research compared to the findings of the current research could be as a result of the higher number of fonio accessions used and the wider geographical distribution area of fonio in Senegal. The level of allelic richness among the ethnic groups observed in this research is similar to results obtained by Diop *et al.* (2023) who detected 1.49 to 2.01 unique alleles among eight ethnic groups in Senegal.

Crop genetic diversity has been found to be influenced by human activities such as selection and dissemination of desirable cultivars and long-term interaction with environmental factors (Leclerc & Coppens d'Eeckenbrugge, 2011). These factors interact at different scales to shape the genetic diversity observed in most crop species. Fonio *in-situ* varietal diversity is socially organized in Ghana, and this directly influenced its genetic diversity organization. Each farmer-named cultivar belonged almost exclusively to one ethnic group, suggesting the existence of a social barrier between the ethnic groups. This suggests that seed exchanges among communities are not frequent. This observation is relevant with the farmer-saved seed practices, and with the fonio genetic variability observed between ethnic groups (8.8 %), and between cultivars (16.4 %). Because fonio is an autogamous crop, the large proportion of seeds that is self produced by farmers imply that genetic diversity within and between cultivars remain every season. Farmer-saved seed practices induced interethnic variability of a crop as a result of selection and limited seed mediated gene flow between ethnic groups (Leclerc & Coppens d'Eeckenbrugge, 2011).

The F_{ST} calculated between the ethnic groups revealed significant differences between some of the ethnic groups. For instance, the F_{ST} calculated between the Anufor and Konkomba ethnic groups was significant ($F_{ST} = 0.079$, $p < 0.001$) while the F_{ST} between Anufor and Kabre ethnic groups was not significant ($F_{ST} = 0.028$, $p > 0.05$). Furthermore, structure analysis among the 140 Ghanaian fonio accessions revealed six ancestral populations. A higher number of the fonio accessions (64 individuals) in this research was classified as admixed at an ancestry coefficient of 70%. The presence of an admixed population could be an indication of gene flow among the ancestral populations. The admixed population comprised fonio accessions from all the four ethnic groups. A greater number of the admixed population were collected from the Anufor farmers. This could be as a result of the higher number of accessions collected from this ethnic group. Although significant F_{ST} was observed among some of the ethnic groups, the social organization of fonio genetic diversity in Ghana was largely influenced by farmers' cultivars, which have contributed to maintaining fonio genetic diversity over time. This observation agrees with Diop *et al.* (2023) who found that the genetic diversity of fonio in Senegal was influenced by the ethnicity of farmers. The F_{ST} calculated between the Mande and Atlantic families was low but significant ($F_{ST} = 0.031$, $p = 0.001$). They observed that Fulani people cultivated early maturing accessions while late maturing accessions were cultivated by farmers belonging to the Balante ethnic group. Other studies have also reported the influence of ethnicity on genetic diversity patterns of crops such as sorghum (Labeyrie *et al.*, 2014), maize (Orozco-Ramírez *et al.*, 2016) and pearl millet (Naino Jika *et al.*, 2017).

Social factors such as age, gender and educational level of farmers were not directly linked to the genetic diversity observed in this research as well as biological factors such as maturity period of the fonio accessions. This was evident in the PCA analysis where both early and late maturing fonio accessions clustered together respective of the community of collection and ethnicity of the affiliated farmers. In addition, there was no significant isolation by distance among the Ghanaian fonio accessions. This result is contrary to the observation of Adoukonou-Sagbadja *et al.* (2007b) who reported clustering of white fonio accessions based on geographic distance. As there was no isolation by distance, some fonio accessions clustered together irrespective of the geographical locations from where they were collected. Again, some accessions

collected from different communities were identified to be duplicates based on the SSR markers used. This could be associated with the recent commercial fonio production characterized by provision of seeds and other incentives to farmers who produce and sell to the companies. For example, fonio cultivation in the Gushegu district of the Northern Region is a recent phenomenon through a company and the crop is solely cultivated for sale to the company.

This research revealed significant genetic variability among fonio cultivars cultivated by farmers in Ghana, with farmer-named fonio cultivars playing substantial role in shaping the genetic diversity of fonio in Ghana. The findings underscore the pivotal role of farmers' practices in preserving fonio genetic diversity over time. Moreover, the distinctiveness of Ghanaian fonio accessions, particularly those from the Chereponi district, stands out in comparison to the genetic diversity observed in West African collections. Although the fonio accessions from Ghana are cultivated close to Togo, there is a unique genetic diversity in the Ghanaian accessions.

3.2 AGRO-MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERIZATION AND EVALUATION OF FONIO (*Digitaria exilis* (Kippist) Stapf) ACCESSIONS IN GHANA

3.2.1 INTRODUCTION

Fonio is a small-sized grain cereal which contributes to food and nutrition for millions of people in West Africa (Adoukonou-Sagbadja *et al.*, 2007b; Cruz *et al.*, 2016; Porteres, 1976). It encompasses two species, the white fonio (*Digitaria exilis* (Kippist) Stapf) largely cultivated in the Sahelian region of West Africa, from Lake Tchad to Senegal and the black fonio (*D. iburua*) probably nowadays mainly cultivated in Nigeria, both having been domesticated in West Africa (Cruz *et al.*, 2016; Gari, 2002; Hilu *et al.*, 1997; Porteres, 1976). It is considered a hunger-alleviating crop due to the short duration of some of the landraces, less than 3 months between sowing and harvesting, and its ability to bridge the hunger gap mostly experienced prior to the harvest of major staples (Barnaud *et al.*, 2022; Clottey *et al.*, 2006a; Enyiukwu & Basse, 2020; Vodouhe *et al.*, 2007). Fonio grains are rich in vitamins, minerals, and essential amino acids such as cysteine and methionine, which are lacking in most cereals such as maize, sorghum, and rice (Ballogou *et al.*, 2014). Based on the nutrient content of the grain, fonio is classified as the most nutritious whole-grain cereal (Ballogou *et al.*, 2014). Besides, its grains have a low glycemic index and contain little gluten, making it suitable for people with hyperglycemia or gluten intolerance (Vodouhe *et al.*, 2007). In Ghana, fonio cultivation is localized in the north-eastern part of northern Ghana, where it serves as an important cereal for many traditional households (Addai *et al.*, 2022; Agyare *et al.*, 2024; Clottey *et al.*, 2006a). In this area, it is mainly cultivated on a subsistence basis for home consumption, even though some grains are sold to meet other household expenses.

Due to the lack of research focus on fonio (Adoukonou-Sagbadja *et al.*, 2006; Dansi *et al.*, 2010), there is limited information on the morphological diversity of fonio accessions, which is essential for improving the crop. Farmers rely on cultivars that have not been improved, and no formal seed systems have been developed for the crop. Additionally, farmers' criteria for selecting desirable fonio cultivars are poorly understood. Again, not much has been done to conserve the genetic resources of fonio, especially in *ex-situ* conservation systems in Ghana and no breeding programs are

currently underway in the face of climate change. Agyare *et al.* (2024) found significant genetic diversity among Ghanaian fonio accessions using simple sequence repeat (SSR) nuclear markers. This genetic diversity was structured mainly due to farmer-specific cultivars which have been cultivated over time. Furthermore, the genetic diversity of the Ghanaian fonio accessions was found to be unique compared to the diversity within the global fonio collection in West Africa (Agyare *et al.*, 2024; Kaczmarek *et al.*, 2023). There is thus a need to examine the diversity patterns among the fonio landraces cultivated in Ghana at the phenotypic level to be closer to farmers' perceptions and to harness the observed genetic diversity.

Dansi *et al.* (2010) and Govindaraj *et al.* (2015) indicated that the assessment of genetic diversity is an important pre-breeding activity to generate information with implications on germplasm conservation and efficient utilization. Badu-Apraku *et al.* (2021) and Mitsuhashi (2024) noted that assessment of diversity also provides a basis for selecting superior genotypes for further evaluation and crop improvement. Therefore, an understanding of the diversity patterns of fonio would be vital for decision-making on efficient genetic resources management and conservation strategies. Also, characterizing fonio resources will provide valuable information on the accessions and thus facilitate the selection of superior candidates for developing market-oriented product profiles for fonio breeding in Ghana. Agro-morphological traits or markers have been used in germplasm characterization and evaluation in many cereals including fonio (Balma *et al.*, 2023; Ibrahim Bio Yerima *et al.*, 2020; Sekloka *et al.*, 2016), rice (Islam *et al.*, 2018), sorghum (Bouargalne *et al.*, 2022), foxtail millet (Sapkota *et al.*, 2016) and maize (Ezin *et al.*, 2022). These morphological traits are important distinguishing features that are easy to score and most of them are expected to be criteria farmers have been using to distinguish and improve the cultivated form.

Earlier attempts targeting morphological characterization of fonio in Ghana considered only a limited number of accessions. Clotey *et al.* (2006b) who studied morphological diversity of 13 fonio accessions, found non-significant differences in the grain yield and other related traits. This observation could be due to the small number of accessions they used. New and pertinent questions can thus be addressed such as a) What is the extent of morphological diversity among a larger number of the Ghanaian fonio accessions? b) What are the key morphological traits that influence

the structuring of diversity in fonio? c) How heritable are these traits and what level of progress can be made through selection? d) Is there a link between morphological diversity and molecular diversity? Answering these questions will improve our understanding of the diversity patterns in fonio and help develop strategies for the conservation and use of fonio genetic resources in Ghana. Identifying key agro-morphological traits that drive diversity in fonio and associations between morphological diversity and genetic diversity based on SSR markers are important preliminary steps for future fonio breeding programmes. The study sought to evaluate the morphological diversity and agronomic performance of fonio accessions in Ghana.

3.2.2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.2.2.1 Description of experimental site

The study involved characterizing 151 fonio accessions collected from farmers in the Chereponi district of the North East Region (106 accessions) and Saboba (23 accessions), Zabzugu (11 accessions), Tatale (4 accessions), Gushegu (4 accessions) and Tolon (3 accessions) districts of the Northern Region of Ghana (Appendix 18) in 2022.

The experiment was established at the research field (N 9° 23' 25.6", W 1° 00' 06.8") of the Savanna Agricultural Research Institute of the Council for Scientific and Industrial Research (CSIR-SARI), Nyankpala in the Northern Region of Ghana during the 2022 cropping season (Appendix 19). It is located in the Guinea Savanna agro-ecological zone, characterized by high temperatures, low humidity, and a unimodal rainfall pattern (May to October). A total rainfall amount of 1313.2 mm was recorded during the 2022 calendar year. Average temperature and relative humidity recorded during the year ranged from 23.4°C to 33.0°C and 62.8% to 81.0%, respectively, with monthly fluctuations (Fig 3.2.1). The soil texture was sandy loam with a pH of 6.27, classified as Acrisols.

Figure 3.2.1 Weather data recorded during the 2022 calendar year

3.2.2.2 Experimental design and data collection

The experiment was laid out in an alpha lattice design, consisting of 17 blocks with 9 entries per block. The trial was replicated three times. Single-row plots measuring 2 m long and an inter-block spacing of 1 m wide were used. Plots within a block were spaced 1 m apart. Ridges were created manually after the field had been ploughed and harrowed with a tractor. Fonio seeds were sown on raised beds and transplanted 4 weeks later. The seedlings were transplanted onto ridges at an intra-row spacing of 0.2 m, with one seedling per stand. Each experimental plot contained a total of 10 plants. Weeds were controlled manually using the hand hoe when needed. At maturity, the fonio plants were harvested with a hand sickle, threshed by hand, and winnowed.

Agro-morphological variability was assessed on 32 traits (17 qualitative and 15 quantitative) adapted from standard rice trait ontology (<https://alliancebioiversityciat.org/tools-innovations/crop-ontology>).

For all qualitative traits, visual observations were made on a plot basis, and the major observation was assigned to the plot (Appendix 20). In the case of the quantitative traits, measurements were recorded on five randomly selected plants as described as follows:

Leaf blade length (cm)

Length of the leaf blade was measured from the base to the tip of the leaf with a meter rule. Measurements were recorded on the leaf below the flag leaf on five randomly selected plants.

Leaf blade width (cm)

Leaf blade width (cm) was measured at the widest portion of the leaf with a meter rule. Measurements were recorded on the leaf below the flag leaf on five randomly selected plants.

Plant height (cm)

Plant height (cm) was measured with a meter rule from the base of the plant to the tip of the longest raceme. This was measured on five plants randomly selected from the middle row of each plot at 50% flowering.

Flag leaf length (cm)

Length of the flag leaf was measured from the base to the tip with a meter rule. Measurements were recorded on five randomly selected plants from the middle row of each plot.

Flag leaf width (cm)

Flag leaf width was measured at the widest part with a meter rule. Measurements were recorded on five randomly selected plants from the middle row of each plot.

Number of leaves per plant

Number of leaves per plant was counted for five randomly selected plants from each plot and the mean value was calculated. Number of leaves per plant was counted for five randomly selected plants for each plot and the average value was calculated.

Number of days to 50 % flowering

Number of days to 50 % flowering was estimated from the date the seeds were nursed to the date 50 % of the plants on a plot flowered.

Number of days to 50 % maturity

Number of days to 50 % maturity was estimated from the date of nursery to the date 50 % of the plants on a plot had matured.

SPAD Chlorophyll Meter Reading (SCMR)

SPAD chlorophyll (a proxy measurement for estimating the chlorophyll content of the leaves), was measured with a handheld SPAD 502 Plus Chlorophyll Meter (Spectrum Technologies, Inc). Measurements were recorded on the flag of five randomly selected plants from the middle row of each plot.

Leaf area index (LAI)

Leaf area index (LAI) was measured with the AccuPAR LP-80 PAI/LAI Ceptometer (Decagon, Inc. USA) device by placing the device under the crop canopy. The measurement was recorded on a plot basis.

Number of racemes per panicle

The number of racemes on a panicle was counted from three randomly selected plants from the middle row of each plot. The average of the five values were computed for each plot.

Raceme length (cm)

Raceme length was measured from the base of the raceme to the tip with a meter rule. Measurements were recorded from five randomly selected plants from the middle row of each plot.

Number of seeds per raceme

Number of grains on a raceme was counted from five randomly selected plants in the middle row of each plot.

Grain weight (g/plot)

Fonio grains harvested from each plot were air dried for one week before weighing with an electronic scale. Number of plants harvested from each plot was recorded at the time of harvesting.

Weight of 1000 grains (g)

One thousand fonio grains were counted manually and the weight was recorded with an electronic scale.

3.2.2.3 Data analysis

Data summary was done using `data.table` (Barrette *et al.*, 2023) R package. Trait-specific analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed using the `agricolae` v 1.3-7 (de Mendiburu, 2023) R package. Downstream analysis was done using the best linear unbiased estimators (BLUEs). Variance components: genotypic variance (σ^2_G), environmental variance (σ^2_E), phenotypic variance (σ^2_P), genotypic coefficient of variation (GCV), environmental coefficient of variation (ECV), relative coefficient of variation (RCV), broad-sense heritability (H^2), genetic advance (GA) and genetic advance as percentage of the mean (GAM) were estimated according to Shukla *et al.* (2006) and Sie *et al.* (2022) as indicated below. GAM was classified into three: low for < 10%, moderate for 10-20%, and high for >20% (Johnson *et al.*, 1955).

$$\sigma^2_E = \frac{MSE}{R} \quad (1)$$

$$\sigma^2_G = MSG - \left(\frac{MSE}{R}\right) \quad (2)$$

$$\sigma^2_P = \sigma^2_G + \sigma^2_E \quad (3)$$

Where σ^2_E = environmental variance, MSE = error mean square, R= number of replications, σ^2_G = genotypic variance, MSG= genotype mean square and σ^2_P = phenotypic variance

$$GCV (\%) = \left(\frac{\sqrt{\sigma^2_G}}{\pi}\right) \times 100 \quad (4)$$

$$PCV (\%) = \left(\frac{\sqrt{\sigma^2_P}}{\pi}\right) \times 100 \quad (5)$$

$$ECV (\%) = \left(\frac{\sqrt{\sigma^2_E}}{\pi}\right) \times 100 \quad (6)$$

$$RCV = \frac{GCV}{ECV} \quad (7)$$

Where GCV= genotypic coefficient of variation, PCV= phenotypic coefficient of variation, ECV= environmental coefficient of variation, σ^2_E = environmental variance and π = grand mean, and RCV= relative coefficient of variation.

$$H^2 = \frac{\sigma_G^2}{\sigma_P^2} \quad (8)$$

$$GA = K\sigma_p H^2 \quad (9)$$

$$GAM = \left(\frac{GA}{\pi}\right) \times 100 \quad (10)$$

Where H^2 = broad sense heritability, GA= genetic advance, K= selection differential (2.06 at 5% selection intensity), σ_P = phenotypic standard deviation.

Pearson's correlation analysis was performed with the *corr_coef* function in the *metan* v. 1.18.0. (Olivoto & Lucio, 2020) R package. A hierarchical cluster analysis based on Euclidean distance with Ward minimum variance test was performed to assess the morphological clustering using the quantitative traits. The quantitative traits were normalized to range between 0 and 1 (Al Shalabi *et al.*, 2006) before distances were computed. Distance computation and cluster groupings were done using the *dist* and *hclust* functions respectively. In contrast, visualization with a tree was done using the *factoextra* v. 1.0.7 (Kassambara & Mundt, 2020) R packages. Principal component analysis (PCA) was carried out after trait-specific centering and scaling using the grand mean and standard deviation, respectively, to identify the most important quantitative traits contributing to diversity. Principal components with eigenvalues greater than one were retained. The PCA was implemented using *FactoMiner* (Lê *et al.*, 2008) and visualized using *factoextra* v. 1.0.7 (Kassambara & Mundt, 2020) R packages. Qualitative traits association with quantitative traits was performed using the *d3heatmap* v. 0.9.0 (Cheng & Galili, 2021) R package. ANOVA was performed among the morphological clusters considering the key quantitative traits that contributed to the clustering of the accessions. Morphological cluster means were estimated using the *emmeans* v. 1.10.2 (Lenth, 2024) R package. Box plots were created using the *ggplot2* (Wickham, 2016) R package for trait visualization among the morphological clusters.

To test the association between morphological clusters and genetic grouping, the genetic clustering of 140 fonio accessions inferred from sparse non-Negative Matrix Factorization (sNMF) method using 12 simple sequence repeat (SSR) markers was retrieved. Clustering in both methods was compared using a contingency table. The admixed accessions (< 70% ancestry coefficient) in the genetic grouping were removed from the contingency table. A chi-squared test with 2000 simulations was performed and the standardized residuals (Haberman residuals) were used to plot a correlation matrix which was visualized using the `corrplot` v. 0.92 (Wei & Simko, 2021) R package.

All the data were analyzed using R software v. 4.2.2 (R Core Team, 2022).

3.2.3 RESULTS

3.2.3.1 Phenotypic variability based on qualitative traits

Phenotypic assessment of qualitative traits among 151 fonio accessions is presented in Table 3.2.1. There was no variation in basal leaf sheath color, type of flag leaf, anthocyanin pigmentation on nodes and internodes, and anther colors over the whole set of accessions. Most of the accessions (92%) had no anthocyanin coloration on the leaf sheath. Regarding leaf blade anthocyanin, 84.8% of the accessions had no pigmentation, while 15.2% had pigmentation either on the leaf blade tips (11.3%) or on leaf blade margins (3.9%). Leaf blade color ranged from green (83.4%) to dark green (16.6%). Leaf blade attitude varied among the accessions, with the majority having erect (94%) leaves, while 6% had horizontal leaves. Culm internode anthocyanin intercity ranged from weak (63.6%) to sharp (36.4%) pigmentation. Two types of plant growth habit were observed among the accessions: erect (85.4%) or spreading (14.6%). Racemes were either semi-erect (28.5%) or spreading (71.5%) on panicles without secondary branching. All the accessions had well-exserted panicles, while seed color varied between brown (89.4%) and dark brown (10.6%).

Table 3.2.1 Classification of 151 fonio accessions using 17 qualitative traits

Traits	Observations (no. accessions; percentage)		
Basal leaf sheath color	Green (151; 100%)		
Leaf sheath anthocyanin coloration	Absent (139; 92%)	Weak (10; 6.6%)	Medium (2; 1.4%)
Leaf blade anthocyanin coloration	Absent (128; 84.8%)	Present (23; 15.2%)	
Leaf blade anthocyanin distribution	Absent (128; 84.8%)	On tips only (17; 11.3%)	On margins only (6; 3.9%)
Leaf blade color intensity	Green (126; 83.4%)	Dark green (25; 16.6%)	
Leaf blade attitude	Erect (142; 94%)	Horizontal (9; 6%)	
Leaf blade pubescence	Glabrous (151; 100%)		
Flag leaf attitude	Erect (151; 100%)		
Culm anthocyanin coloration on nodes	Purple (151; 100%)		
Culm internode anthocyanin	Purple (151; 100%)		
Culm internode anthocyanin intensity	Weak (96; 63.6%)	Strong (55; 36.4%)	
Plant growth habit	Erect (129; 85.4%)	Spreading (22; 14.6%)	
Anther color	Purple (151; 100%)		
Raceme attitude on branches	Semi erect (43; 28.5%)	Spreading (108; 71.5%)	
Raceme secondary branching	Absent (151; 100%)		
Panicle exertion	Well exerted (151; 100%)		
Seed color	Brown (135; 89.4%)	Dark brown (16; 10.6%)	

3.2.3.2 Phenotypic variability in quantitative traits among 151 fonio accessions

The analysis of variance revealed significant ($P < 0.05$) genotypic differences among the fonio accessions for plant height, flag leaf length, number of days to 50 % flowering, leaf blade length, number of days to 50 % maturity, number of leaves per plant, number of racemes per panicle, number of seeds per raceme, raceme length, grain weight per plant and 1000 seed weight. In the case of SPAD chlorophyll meter reading (SCMR), flag leaf width, leaf area index and leaf blade width, no significant ($P > 0.05$) genotypic variability was observed among the fonio accessions (Appendix 21).

Plant height ranged from 58.33 cm to 93.10 cm with a mean of 69.07 ± 5.44 cm (Table 3.2.2). SCMR varied from 29.07 to 52.80 with a mean of 41.51 ± 4.48 . A minimum of 4.96 cm and a maximum of 9.76 cm were recorded for flag leaf length with a mean of 7.17 ± 0.85 cm. The number of days to 50 % flowering varied from 59 to 103 days with a mean of 72 ± 7.56 days after sowing. Mean flag leaf width was 0.38 ± 0.05 cm and ranged from 0.28 cm to 0.54 cm. Leaf area index ranged between 0.79 and 3.24 with a mean of 1.78 ± 0.43 . Leaf blade length ranged from 5.74 cm to 14.09 cm with a mean of 8.30 ± 1.40 cm. For the width of the leaf blade, it ranged from 0.3 cm to 0.5 cm with a mean of 0.39 ± 0.04 cm. Number of days to 50% maturity ranged between 96 and 135 days after sowing. Average number of days to 50% maturity was 109 ± 7.65 days after sowing. Mean number of leaves per plant was 87 ± 18.55 leaves and ranged from 48 to 152 leaves per plant. Number of racemes per panicle ranged from 2.56 to 4.11 with a mean of 3.30 ± 0.31 while the number of seeds per raceme ranged between 74 and 274 with a mean of 115 ± 23.82 seeds per raceme. Raceme length ranged from 9.73 cm to 13.95 cm with a mean of 12.09 ± 1.00 cm. Grain weight per plant significantly varied among accessions and ranged from 4.8 g to 17.93 g with a mean of 10.41 ± 2.86 g. 1000 seed weight ranged from 0.31 g to 0.61 g with a mean of 0.49 ± 0.04 g. Mean performance of the fonio accessions for growth and yield components are presented in Appendix 22.

Table 3.2.2 Summary statistics of 15 quantitative traits in fonio

Trait	Minimum	Maximum	Mean \pm SD	CV (%)
Plant height (cm)	58.33	93.10	69.07 \pm 5.44	6.68
SPAD chlorophyll meter reading (SCMR)	29.07	52.80	41.51 \pm 4.48	18.21
Flag Leaf length (cm)	4.96	9.76	7.17 \pm 0.85	13.87
Days 50% flowering	59.00	103.00	72.00 \pm 7.56	3.36
Flag leaf width (cm)	0.28	0.54	0.38 \pm 0.05	19.65
Leaf area index	0.79	3.24	1.78 \pm 0.43	39.44
Leaf blade length (cm)	5.74	14.09	8.30 \pm 1.40	21.37
Leaf blade width (cm)	0.30	0.50	0.39 \pm 0.04	16.67
Days to 50% maturity	96.00	135.00	109.00 \pm 7.65	3.69
Number of leaves/plant	48.00	152.00	87.00 \pm 18.55	22.49
Number of racemes/panicle	2.56	4.11	3.30 \pm 0.31	11.36
Number of seeds/raceme	74.00	274.00	115.00 \pm 23.82	26.71
Raceme length (cm)	9.73	13.95	12.09 \pm 1.00	6.95
Grain weight/plant (g)	4.80	17.93	10.41 \pm 2.86	32.84
1000 seed weight (g)	0.31	0.61	0.49 \pm 0.04	8.55

SD= Standard deviation; CV= Coefficient of variation

3.2.3.3 Variance components and heritability of traits

For all the studied traits, the genotypic variance was large compared to the environmental variance (Table 3.2.3). The lowest genotypic variance (0.004) was recorded for leaf blade width and 1000 seeds weight whilst the highest genotypic variance was recorded for number of seeds per raceme (1395.96). Genotypic coefficient of variation (GCV) ranged from 11.96 (number of days to 50% flowering) to 43.87 (grain weight per plant). Similarly, number of days to 50% flowering (12.15) had the lowest phenotypic coefficient of variation (PCV), while the highest was recorded for grain weight per plant (47.80). In the case of environmental coefficient of variation (ECV), the lowest was recorded for number of days to 50% flowering (1.94) while the highest was recorded for leaf area index (22.77). The relative coefficient of variation (RCV) ranged from 1.48 for SCMR to 9.3 for the number of days to 50% flowering. Traits with relative coefficients of variation greater than one (1) indicate that such traits were largely influenced by genetic factors. This was the case for the number of days to 50 % flowering, number of days to 50 % maturity (5.61), raceme length (3.45) and plant height (3.4). SCMR had the lowest broad-sense

heritability (69%) while the highest broad-sense heritability was observed in the number of days to 50 % flowering (99%). Estimates of genetic advance (5% selection intensity) revealed that fonio plant height can be increased by 10.31 cm and SCMR can be increased by 6.33. Number of days to 50 % flowering and maturity can be reduced by 15.39 and 15.28 days respectively. Genetic advance for flag leaf length and flag leaf width were 1.49 cm and 0.07 cm respectively. Also, grain weight per plant can be increased by 4.97 g, leaf area index can be increased by 0.63, leaf blade length and leaf blade width can be increased by 2.37 cm and 0.06 cm respectively. Number of leaves per plant, number of racemes per panicle and number of seeds per raceme can be increased by 34 leaves per plant, 1 raceme per panicle and 40 seeds per raceme respectively. Genetic advance for raceme length and 1000 seed weight were 1.90 cm and 0.07 g respectively. Genetic advance as a percentage of the mean (GAM) varied between 13.96% (number of days to 50 % flowering) and 47.74% (grain weight per plant). Most of the traits can be improved moderately. However, significant improvement can be achieved in traits such as grain weight per plant, number of leaves per plant, leaf area index and the number of seeds per raceme with high GAM of 47.74%, 38.58%, 35.42% and 34.63% respectively.

Table 3.2.3 Variances, broad-sense heritability, genetic advance for 15 traits

Traits	σ^2_G	σ^2_E	σ^2_P	GCV (%)	PCV (%)	ECV (%)	RCV (%)	H² (%)	GA	GAM (%)
Plant height (cm)	82.16	7.10	89.26	13.12	13.68	3.86	3.40	92	10.31	14.92
SCMR	41.55	19.05	60.60	15.53	18.75	10.51	1.48	69	6.33	15.24
Flag leaf length (cm)	1.87	0.33	2.20	19.04	20.65	8.00	2.38	85	1.49	20.81
Days 50% flowering	170.59	1.97	172.57	18.06	18.17	1.94	9.30	99	15.00	21.29
Flag leaf width (cm)	0.005	0.002	0.007	18.78	21.94	11.35	1.65	71	0.07	19.16
Grain weight/plant (g)	20.84	3.89	24.74	43.87	47.80	18.96	2.31	84	4.97	47.74
Leaf area index	0.40	0.16	0.56	35.47	42.15	22.77	1.56	71	0.63	35.42
Leaf blade length (cm)	4.86	1.05	5.91	26.57	29.29	12.34	2.15	82	2.37	28.57
Leaf blade width (cm)	0.004	0.001	0.005	15.35	18.12	9.62	1.60	80	0.06	15.35
Days to 50% maturity	171.36	5.45	176.81	11.96	12.15	2.13	5.61	97	15.00	13.96
Number of leaves/plant	911.85	127.33	1039.19	34.75	37.09	12.98	2.68	88	34.00	38.58
Number of racemes/panicle	0.23	0.05	0.28	14.71	16.11	6.56	2.24	82	1.00	15.92
Number of seeds/raceme	1395.96	316.97	1712.93	32.36	35.84	15.42	2.10	81	40.00	34.63
Raceme length (cm)	2.79	0.24	3.03	13.82	14.40	4.01	3.45	92	1.90	15.73
1000 seed weight (g)	0.004	0.001	0.005	13.12	14.02	4.94	2.66	80	0.07	14.47

SCMR= SPAD chlorophyll meter reading; σ^2_G = Genotypic variance; σ^2_E = Environmental variance; σ^2_P = Phenotypic variance; GCV= Genotypic coefficient of variation; ECV= Environmental coefficient of variation; RCV= Relative coefficient of variation; H²= Broad sense heritability; GA= Genetic advance; GAM= Genetic advance as percentage of the mean

3.2.3.4 Pearson's correlation among 15 quantitative traits

Pearson's correlation analysis between the observed quantitative traits is presented in Fig. 3.2.2. Considering only the significant correlations, most of the traits were highly positively correlated and some were negatively correlated. Grain weight per plant, as a measure of the yield, is the most important trait. It was highly significant and positively correlated with plant height, leaf area index, leaf blade length, leaf blade width, flag leaf length, number of leaves per plant, number of racemes per panicle, number of seeds per raceme and raceme length. It also exhibited a highly significant and positive correlation with the number of days to 50% flowering and number of days to 50% maturity. However, grain weight per plant was negatively correlated with 1000 seed weight. SPAD chlorophyll meter reading (SCMR) had a non-significant correlation with all the traits except for raceme length.

3.2.3.5 Hierarchical clustering of 151 fonio accessions using 15 quantitative traits

Hierarchical clustering analysis using the 15 quantitative traits is presented in Fig. 3.2.3. The 151 fonio accessions grouped into three clusters at a distance of 0.5. The clustering of the accessions was independent of geographical location of the accessions. Clustering among accessions was mainly influenced by traits such as number of days to flowering and maturity, number of seeds per raceme, number of leaves per plant, raceme length and plant height (Fig 3.2.4 and Appendix 23 for details). Cluster A (orange color in Fig 3.2.3) was made up of 36 accessions, characterized by early maturing (100 days), short plants (63 cm on average), an average of 97 seeds per raceme and an average of 69 leaves per plant. The morphological traits clusters correlated with some qualitative traits (Appendix 24) with the crossing of clusters based on quantitative traits and qualitative characters.

Figure 3.2.2 Pearson's correlation analysis among 15 morphological traits

GWP= Grain weight per plant (g); DFM= Days to 50% maturity; RL= Raceme length (cm); NRP= Number of racemes per panicle; NLP= Number of leaves per plant; FLL= Flag leaf length (cm); FLW= Flag leaf width (cm); LBL= Leaf blade length (cm); LBW= Leaf blade width (cm); SCMR= SPAD chlorophyll meter reading; TSW= 1000 seed weight (g); NSR= Number of seeds per raceme; LAI= Leaf area index; DFF= Days to 50% flowering; PH= Plant height (cm).

The accessions in this cluster had erect growth habit with green leaves, weak culm internode anthocyanin color intensity and semi-erect racemes (Appendix 24). Cluster B (green color) contained 92 accessions with an erect plant growth habit, green leaves and brown seed color (Appendix 24). Accessions in this cluster had an intermediate maturity, producing an average of 112 seeds per raceme with 87 leaves per plant. Cluster C (blue color) consisted of 23 accessions with late maturing (> 120 days) cycle. Accessions in this cluster were characterized by tall plants (> 70 cm), long racemes, a higher mean number of leaves per plant, and an average of 146 seeds per raceme. In addition, these accessions had a spreading growth habit, dark green leaves with high intensity of anthocyanin coloration in the culm internode and dark brown seed color.

3.2.3.6 Principal Component Analysis (PCA) of 15 quantitative traits

Principal component analysis (PCA) showed that the first three principal components accounted for 58.77% of the total variability observed among the fonio accessions (Table 3.2.4, Appendix 25 plotting the three clusters on the PCA). PC 1 axis accounted for 43.70% of the total variation. Traits that explained the observed variability on the PC1 axis were number of days to 50% flowering, number of days to 50% maturity, number of leaves per plant, plant height, number of racemes per panicle, flag leaf length, flag leaf width, raceme length, number of seeds per raceme, leaf blade length, leaf area index, grain weight per plant and leaf blade width (Table 3.2.4). The second PC axis explained 7.73% of the variability and was largely contributed by 1000 seed weight (TSW). The third PC axis explained 7.34% of the total variation and the key trait was SPAD chlorophyll meter reading (SCMR).

Figure 3.2.3 Cluster analysis of 151 fonio accessions using 15 quantitative traits.

The prefixes of the accession codes refer to the district of collection where C = Chereponi district, S= Saboba district, T= Tatale district, Z= Zabzugu district. The number after the accession code/name represents the morphological cluster

Relationship and discriminatory of the traits

Leaf blade length and the number of leaves per plant had the highest discriminatory power while SPAD chlorophyll meter reading was the least variable trait among the accessions as revealed by the length of the trait vectors from the biplot origin (Appendix 26). However, traits such as grain weight per plant, number of racemes per plant, number of seeds per raceme and raceme length had moderate discriminatory power. A strong and positive correlation was observed between grain weight per plant, number of seeds per raceme, number of racemes per panicle, number of leaves per plant, plant height, raceme length, number of days to 50% flowering and maturity as depicted by the angles between the trait vectors. A similar correlation was observed between flag leaf width, leaf blade width, flag leaf length and leaf blade length. On the contrary, SPAD chlorophyll meter reading was negatively correlated with flag leaf width, leaf blade width, flag leaf length and leaf blade length.

Table 3.2.4 Principal component analysis of 15 quantitative traits

Traits	PC 1	PC 2	PC 3
Plant height	0.774	-0.242	-0.081
SPAD chlorophyll meter reading	-0.162	-0.222	0.769
Flag Leaf length	0.707	0.290	0.293
Days 50% flowering	0.927	-0.036	-0.037
Flag leaf width	0.503	0.432	0.355
Grain weight/plant	0.558	-0.072	0.143
Leaf area index	0.450	-0.271	0.379
Leaf blade length	0.614	0.495	0.084
Leaf blade width	0.546	0.456	-0.168
Days to 50% maturity	0.909	-0.075	-0.054
Number of leaves per plant	0.819	-0.279	0.031
Number of racemes per panicle	0.732	-0.115	-0.084
Number of seeds per raceme	0.645	-0.061	-0.210
Raceme length	0.768	-0.219	-0.178
1000 seed weight	-0.300	0.364	0.049
Eigenvalue	6.55	1.16	1.10
Percentage of variation	43.70	7.73	7.34
Cumulative % of variation	43.70	51.43	58.77

Note: numbers in bold represent the traits that were selected for each principal component (PC) axis

3.2.3.7 Performance in key quantitative traits among morphological traits clusters

Mean performance of the accessions based on the traits that contributed most to the clustering, is shown in Appendix 23. There was highly significant variability among the clusters for the number of days to 50% flowering, number of days to 50% maturity, plant height, number of leaves per plant, number of racemes per panicle, raceme length, number of seeds per raceme and grain weight per plant. The clustering significantly identified three phenological groups ($P < 0.05$). Accessions in Cluster A flowered early (63 ± 1.62 days) while accessions in Cluster C flowered late (85 ± 7.08 days), and those in Cluster B were intermediate (73.00 ± 2.17 days, Fig 3.2.4a). A similar trend was observed for number of days to 50% maturity. Accessions in Cluster A matured in 100 ± 2.65 days while accessions in Cluster C matured in 122 ± 6.01 days (Fig 3.2.4b). Considering the overall morphology, significant differences were observed among all the clusters for plant height, which ranged from $63.08 (\pm 2.74$ cm, Cluster A) to $73.01 (\pm 7.41$ cm, Cluster C) (Fig 3.2.4c) and number of leaves per plant which ranged from 69 ± 11.01 leaves for cluster A to 112 ± 17.38 for cluster B (Fig 3.2.4d). The longest racemes were found in Cluster C accessions (12.75 ± 0.61 cm) while accessions with the shortest racemes (10.60 ± 0.51 cm) belonged to Cluster A (Fig 3.2.4e). Number of seeds per raceme ranged from 97 ± 16.00 seeds (Cluster A) to 143 ± 36.56 seeds (Cluster C) with significant differences among all the clusters (Fig 3.2.4f). The accessions in Cluster A produced the lowest grain weight per plant (7.71 ± 1.78 g) while accessions in Cluster C produced the highest grain weight per plant (13.05 ± 3.06 g) with significant differences among all the clusters (Fig 3.2.4g). Number of racemes per plant ranged from 3.01 ± 0.22 in Cluster A to 3.64 ± 0.24 in Cluster C (Fig 3.2.4h).

Figure 3.2.4 Variability in key quantitative traits among morphological clusters.

Cluster A = 36 accessions, Cluster B = 92 accessions and Cluster C = 23 accessions
 a) number of days to 50% flowering, b) number of days to 50% maturity, c) plant height, d) number of leaves per plant, e) raceme length, f) number of seeds per raceme, g) grain weight per plant and h) number of racemes per plant

3.2.3.8 Association between morphological traits clusters and genetic groups

The Chi-squared test with 2000 simulations and the Monte-Carlo test using a contingency table (Appendix 27) showed significant association between morphological clusters based on 15 quantitative traits and genetic groups at $K = 6$ (Appendix 28, $\chi^2 = 29.22$, p value < 0.0019). Morphological Cluster A which consisted of early maturing accessions strongly overlapped with genetic Group 6 (Fig 3.2.5), Cluster B with genetic group 4, and Cluster C, which contains the late maturing accessions, with groups 1 and 5. Genetic groups 2 and 3 were not significantly associated with any morphological clusters (χ^2 critical value of 1.96, $p = 0.05$)

Figure 3.2.5 Chi-squared residuals between genetic and morphological clusters.

Size of the grey circles shows the magnitude of the association; values above the critical value of 1.96 (0.05 significance level) show positive association between the genetic groups and morphological clusters.

3.2.4 DISCUSSION

The level of morphological diversity among the accessions in this study based on qualitative traits was low. This result is similar to the observations of Balma *et al.* (2023) who reported low diversity in qualitative traits among 60 fonio accessions characterized in Burkina Faso. For traits that were variable among the accessions, the variation was skewed with many of the accessions having one predominant character. This was evident for plant growth habit where 85% of the accessions were erect while 15% had a spreading growth habit. Similarly, about 90% of the fonio accessions possessed a brown grain color while only 10% had dark brown grain color. Balma *et al.* (2023) reported a ratio 60/40 of pale yellow/brown grain color. They also observed stem color diversity with 90/10 green/purple. Also, Ibrahim Bio Yerima *et al.* (2020) reported two grain colors among 180 fonio accessions in Benin where 84% exhibited brown color and 16% a greyed orange color.

All the fonio accessions in this study possessed well-exserted panicles. This is different from the findings of Ibrahim Bio Yerima *et al.* (2020) who observed three forms of panicle exsertion: slightly exserted, moderately exserted and well-exserted panicles among 180 fonio accessions from five West African countries. Similarly, erect flag leaf was observed in this study, although Ibrahim Bio Yerima *et al.* (2020) reported three different flag leaf traits: erect, intermediate and horizontal. These variations could be attributed to diverse germplasm from different countries used in their study compared to Ghanaian accessions which were collected from a small geographical area.

Significant differences were observed among the accessions for quantitative traits. Results of the present study are similar to those reported by Ibrahim Bio Yerima *et al.* (2020) and Nyam *et al.* (2017) who reported greater morphological diversity in quantitative traits among fonio accessions. The three morphological clusters observed based on the 15 quantitative traits in the current study were mainly influenced by traits such as crop cycle (flowering and maturity period), plant biomass (height and number of leaves), raceme length and the number of seeds per raceme. The contribution of these traits to total variability based on the principal component analysis underlines their importance in structuring the observed diversity. Raceme length is an important trait to breed for since it is highly correlated with the number of seeds per raceme and

grain yield. The average raceme length recorded in this study (12.09 cm) was higher than the mean of 4.82 cm reported by Ibrahim Bio Yerima *et al.* (2020). This indicates that the Ghanaian accessions have longer racemes and could be differentiated from other West African accessions based on this trait. Meanwhile, the number of seeds per raceme in this study ranged from 74 to 274 with a mean of 115. This was higher than the mean number of seeds per raceme (88 grains) reported in their study. This variation could be attributed to the unique characteristics of the Ghanaian accessions with longer racemes. The results of our study showed a wide variation in flowering and maturity times among the accessions. This result is in agreement with Clottey *et al.* (2006b) who reported the clustering of 13 Ghanaian fonio accessions based on flowering and maturity period. The fonio accessions in the current study could be classified into maturity groups as: early (≤ 90 days), intermediate (91 – 110 days) and late (> 110 days). This result is in accordance with earlier studies by Saidu *et al.* (2014) and Sekloka *et al.* (2016) who identified fonio cultivars with different maturity classes in Niger and Benin respectively. However, the average number of days to maturity (109 days) observed in this study was longer compared to an average of 95 days to maturity among the accessions from five West African countries reported by Ibrahim Bio Yerima *et al.* (2020). This is an indication that farmers in the drier regions especially in Burkina Faso (98 days), Mali (85 days) and Niger (84 days) have over the years selected for early maturing fonio cultivars compared to Benin and Guinea with 105 days to maturity. These fonio cultivars with an early maturing cycle may be insensitive to photoperiodism with good adaptability to low soil moisture (Aliero & Morakinyo, 2005).

In this study, high broad-sense heritability was observed for all the traits except SPAD chlorophyll meter reading which had a moderate broad-sense heritability. This result is similar to the findings of Umar *et al.* (2020) who observed high broad-sense heritability estimates for number of days to maturity and grain yield in 12 fonio accessions in Nigeria. On the contrary, they observed low broad-sense heritability estimates for plant height (12.23%), number of racemes per panicle (20%) and raceme length (25%). The higher genotypic coefficient of variation observed for most of the traits in this study suggests that these traits may be under genetic control with minimal environmental influence. Genetic advance (GA) for number of days to 50% flowering and maturity indicated that these two traits could be reduced by 15 days after selection.

This could have a significant impact on fonio production in areas where rainfall patterns have changed. The moderate (10-20%) to high (>20%) genetic advance as percentage of the mean (GAM) and the high broad-sense heritability estimates for most of the traits suggest that significant progress could be made on these traits through selection. These traits could be used in a selection index to identify superior accessions as parents in future fonio breeding programmes.

Correlation analysis revealed highly significant and positive relationships between grain weight and most of the traits. Correlations between most of the traits in this study was consistent with an earlier report by Ibrahim Bio Yerima *et al.* (2020). However, grain yield and 1000 seed weight which were negatively correlated in our study, were positively correlated in their study. In this study a significant and negative correlation between number of seeds per raceme and 1000 seed weight was observed. This relationship is expected since the more seeds there are during grain filling, the less carbohydrates are distributed to each grain which accounts for the lower seed weight. A highly significant and positive correlation between grain weight and crop cycle (flowering and maturity) was observed in this study. Although this observation contradicted Ibrahim Bio Yerima *et al.* (2020), it was corroborated by the results of Clottey *et al.* (2006b) and Addai *et al.* (2022) who reported highly significant and positive correlation between grain yield and flowering and maturity times in fonio in Ghana. Other studies have also reported highly significant and positive correlation between grain yield and crop phenology in finger millet Chavan *et al.* (2020) and sorghum (Wang *et al.*, 2020). Grain weight was positively correlated with plant height in this study. However, lodging may be more pronounced in taller plants than in moderately tall plants. Susceptibility to lodging is an undesirable trait in fonio breeding. Abdul & Jideani (2019) stated that lodging makes harvesting difficult, increases post-harvest losses and reduces the quality of the fonio grains. Therefore, breeding for cultivars that are resistant to lodging is essential to improve grain yield and quality of fonio.

The results of this study showed a significant association between the morphological clusters and some of the genetic groups based on SSR markers. This association would help in selecting accessions possessing distinct traits from the different morphological clusters for improvement purposes. However, the association was not perfect as some genetic groups were not associated with any morphological clusters. These

observations could be attributed to the uneven number of accessions used in each analysis, the lack of genetic data for some of the accessions and the high number of accessions classified as admixed in the genetic grouping which were excluded from the correlation analysis. Finally, the relatively low number of SSR markers used in the genetic groupings and their low density with limited genetic coverage of the genome could have resulted in the weak association between the morphological clusters and the genetic groups. The uniqueness of the Ghanaian fonio accessions compared to the global diversity based on SSR analysis was confirmed by the morphological diversity. The Ghanaian fonio accessions had longer racemes and higher number of seeds per raceme compared to the observation of Ibrahim Bio Yerima *et al.* (2020). The presence of diversity in these key traits in a rapidly changing environment provides an opportunity to select superior fonio accessions with which farmers can respond to climate change and ensure food and nutritional security.

Farmers' knowledge in maintaining diversity and conserving fonio genetic resources cannot be overemphasized (Agyare *et al.*, 2024). Some of the observations from this study correlated strongly with farmers' knowledge of their accessions documented during the farmer surveys and germplasm collection. The phenological cycle of the fonio accessions observed in the current study ranged from early to late maturing cultivars which highly correlated with farmers' knowledge of maturity of the fonio accessions. From the survey, fonio accessions C031701, C031702 and C031703 had maturity periods of 4 months, 3 months and 2.5 months respectively. Results for the current study revealed accession C031701 flowered in 84 days while accessions C031702 and C031703 flowered in 73 days and 64 days respectively. Similarly, classification of some fonio accessions based on grain color (husk color) particularly by some farmers in the Saboba district correlated with grain color observed in this study. Fonio accessions S010502, S020101, S060201, S080201, S080302 and S080401 which were identified as *Ipui maln* (red skin fonio) cultivar from the surveys were found to have dark brown grain color from our phenotyping. These observations underline the importance of harnessing the wealth of experience and knowledge of farmers to develop effective conservation strategies and cultivar development profiles.

3.3 GENOTYPE × ENVIRONMENT INTERACTION EFFECT ON GRAIN YIELD AND AGRONOMIC TRAITS OF FONIO (*Digitaria exilis* (Kippist) Stapf) IN GHANA

3.3.1 INTRODUCTION

Fonio is cultivated in diverse agro-climatic conditions across West Africa (Jideani & Jideani, 2011). In Ghana, fonio production is concentrated in the northern eastern part of the country with the Chereponi district serving as the hub for fonio production. However, to increase the production of the crop and expand the country's capacity with increasing demand for fonio grains, it is important that cultivars with high grain yield and stable across different agro-ecological zones are identified and recommended to farmers. Though fonio grows well in diverse environments, its grain yield varies among cultivars and environments (Dachi & Gana, 2008). This is because grain yield, a quantitatively inherited trait, is sensitive to changes in soil and climatic conditions. Acquah (2007) indicated that performance of field crops is often influenced by prevailing environmental conditions. This variation in performance is due to inherent genetic properties, environmental conditions and the interaction between genotype and environment (Falconer & MacKay, 1996). As a result, it is imperative to assess the performance of crop cultivars in diverse environments to determine the effect of genotype × environment interaction.

Genotype × environment interaction refers to the differential responses of genotypes in different environments (De Leon *et al.*, 2016) and is an important consideration in plant breeding programmes because it affects decision-making process such as allocation of resources, breeding strategy, appropriate testing locations and scope of evaluation (De Leon *et al.*, 2016). Genotype × environment interaction impedes selection of desirable cultivars in multi-environment trials and prolongs the breeding cycle (Enyew *et al.*, 2021; Kang, 2002). This is because response of genotypes may vary from one location to another, and the magnitude of the variation may not be the same for all genotypes. Additionally, some genotypes may be highly sensitive to environmental factors while others show greater resilience across different range of environments (Waters *et al.*, 2023; Yau, 1995). When genotype × environment interaction affects the magnitude of the variation without altering the ranking of the

genotypes, it is often not a major concern to plant breeders. However, if genotype \times environment interaction causes a change in ranking in performance of genotypes across environments, it makes selection and recommendation of best performing genotypes complicated (De Leon *et al.*, 2016). Genotype \times environment interactions effects have been observed in many crop species including maize (Adu *et al.*, 2013; Haruna *et al.*, 2017), groundnut (Okori *et al.*, 2019), cassava (Uchendu *et al.*, 2022) and Bambara groundnut (Olanrewaju *et al.*, 2021) resulting in changes in ranking of genotypes across environments and years. This phenomenon brought about the concept of stability in performance which is defined as consistency in performance of a genotype in a given trait across environments and seasons (De Leon *et al.*, 2016). However, high stability in a trait is desirable if it is combined with high performance. Powell *et al.* (2012) reported that crop varieties that combine high yield potential with stability and resilience to climate change are more desirable for improving crop production and ensuring food security. Genotypes that have high per se performance and are stable across environments and years are categorized as broadly adapted genotypes and can be recommended for cultivation across a wider geographical area (Gangashetty *et al.*, 2023; Matesanz & Sultan, 2013). On the other hand, genotypes that perform well only in certain environments are considered to have specific adaptation and are therefore recommended for cultivation in such environments (Chapman *et al.*, 1997; Cooper *et al.*, 1997).

Therefore, a deeper understanding of the effects of genotype \times environment interaction and its implication on cultivar selection and recommendation to end-users is vital in ensuring progress from selection (Yan & Tinker, 2006).

Though fonio cultivation in Ghana is predominant in the north eastern part of the country, a recent study has reported significant genotype \times location interaction possibly due to variability in the soil, climatic and environmental conditions. This has the potential to affect selection and recommendation of fonio genotypes for cultivation by farmers. However, there is limited understanding of genotype \times environment interaction effect on fonio in different agro ecologies in Ghana as compared to maize, rice, pearl millet and sorghum. Though Addai *et al.* (2022) examined the effect of genotype \times location interaction on grain yield in five fonio accessions in two test locations in northern Ghana, they found significant genotype \times location interaction only for some growth components but found no significant genotype \times location

interaction for grain yield. There is therefore the need to thoroughly investigate the effect of genotype \times environment interaction on grain yield and other agronomic traits in fonio in more test locations to gain a better understanding of the effect of genotype \times environment on fonio and select superior cultivars. When variations in environmental conditions are large, genotype \times environment interaction effect tends to be larger.

With changing climatic conditions and the need to expand fonio cultivation into new environments and agro ecologies, an in-depth and continued study of genotype \times environment in fonio cannot be overemphasized. To this, there is a need to expand the evaluations to include a large number of diverse fonio genotypes and testing sites. This will provide information on performance of genotypes in various test environments. Also, it will assist plant breeders in recommending suitable genotypes for cultivation by farmers. Additionally, evaluation of fonio in different locations across northern Ghana will also serve as an opportunity to promote fonio cultivation in such locations. This study was conducted to examine the effect of genotype \times environment interaction on fonio grain yield and other agronomic traits and to select genotypes with high and stable yield across environments. Specifically, the study sought to analyze the pattern of grain yield and stability in performance of fonio genotypes using genotype main effect and genotype \times environment (GGE) interaction biplot method.

3.3.2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.3.2.1 Description of study sites

The fonio genotypes were evaluated in five locations across the Guinea and Sudan Savanna agro ecologies of Ghana (Appendix 29). The geographical locations of the experimental sites are presented in Table 3.3.1. In general, these areas are characterized by a unimodal rainfall pattern which begins in May-June and ends in October. However, the amount of rainfall, average temperature, relative humidity and soil type are variable among the locations. Soil samples were taken from each trial location at a depth of 20 cm using soil auger to determine physico-chemical properties of the soils (Table 3.3.2). The pH of the soil was determined in a distilled water at a soil: water ratio of 1:2.5 (m:v) using a glass electrode and pH meter (EUTECH pH 700) (Thomas, 1996). Soil organic carbon was estimated using the Titrimetric chromic acid wet oxidation method (Walkley & Black, 1934) with slight modification as described by Nelson & Sommers (1982). Total nitrogen (N) was determined using the Kjeldahl method as described by Bremner (1996). Phosphorus (P) was determined using the Bray No. 1 method (Bray & Kurtz, 1945). The soil available potassium was determined by flame photometry (Genway PFP7 Flame Photometer) as described by Motsara (2015). Soil particle size (sand, clay and silt) was determined using the standard Bouyoucos hydrometer method (Bouyoucos, 1962).

Table 3.3.1 Geographical location of trial sites (environments)

Region	District	Environment	Ecology
Northern	Tolon	Nyankpala	Guinea Savanna
Northern	Savelugu	Challam	Guinea Savanna
North East	West Mamprusi	Tinguri	Guinea Savanna
Upper East	Talensi	Ageadone	Guinea Savanna
Upper East	Binduri	Manga	Sudan Savanna

Table 3.3.2 Physico-chemical properties of soil samples at the trial sites

Site	pH (1:2.5 H₂O)	OC (%)	N (%)	P (mg/kg)	K (Cmol+/kg)	% Sand	% Clay	% Silt	Texture
Nyankpala	5.86	0.69	0.03	6.98	0.15	69.92	2.20	27.88	Sandy loam
Challam	6.33	0.87	0.04	8.66	0.19	86.04	3.24	10.72	Loamy sand
Tinguri	6.96	0.68	0.03	7.86	0.17	85.80	7.32	6.88	Loamy sand
Ageadone	6.42	1.17	0.05	12.24	0.20	86.72	5.32	7.96	Loamy sand
Manga	6.34	0.72	0.03	10.64	0.18	86.84	5.20	7.96	Loamy sand

pH= Soil acidity or alkalinity; OC= Organic carbon; N= Nitrogen; P= Available phosphorus; K= Potassium

3.3.2.2 Plant materials and experimental conditions

Twenty fonio accessions (Table 3.3.3) selected from a preliminary evaluation conducted in 2022 were used for this study. The fonio accessions were selected according to the gradient of flowering time (crop cycle) and grain yield. The experiments were laid out using the row column design with three replications in each location. A replication consisted of 10 rows \times 2 columns. The fields were ploughed with a tractor and harrowing was done manually with the hoe. Fonio seeds were nursed and transplanted four weeks after nursing. Plot dimensions were 2 m x 2.4 m giving an area of 4.8 m². Seedlings were transplanted at an inter-row spacing of 0.8 m and an intra-row spacing of 0.2 m with a plant population of 30 seedlings per plot (Appendices 30 and 31). A compound fertilizer NPK (15-15-15), was applied two weeks after transplanting at a rate of 30 kg/ha in a single dose. Each plant was fertilized with 3.2 g of fertilizer which was applied to holes 5 cm deep and 7 cm away from each plant and covered. Weeds were manually controlled with hoe as and when necessary.

3.3.2.3 Data collection

Data were collected on plant height (cm), SPAD chlorophyll meter reading (SCMR), number of days to 50% flowering, flag leaf length (cm), flag leaf width (cm), number of racemes per panicle, raceme length (cm), number of seeds per raceme, grain weight (g/plot) and 1000 seed weight (g) as described in Chapter 3.2.2.

3.3.2.4 Data analyses

Data were analysed using packages in R statistical software v. 4.2.2 (R Core Team, 2022). An analysis of variance (ANOVA) was first performed on the data per environment using the agricolae v 1.3-7 (de Mendiburu, 2023) R package. A combined ANOVA was performed on data from all five environments using lmerTest (Kuznetsova *et al.*, 2017) R package. The main effects of genotype and environment as well as genotype \times environment interaction effects were fixed while the effect of row and column in the environments were considered random. For traits such as number of racemes per panicle and number of grains per raceme, the data was transformed using the square root transformation method.

The model employed for the single environment analysis was:

$$Y_{ijkl} = \mu + G_i + \text{Row}_{k(j)} + \text{Col}_{l(j)} + \epsilon_{ijkl}$$

Where, Y_{ijkl} is the mean yield of the i th genotype in the k th row and l th column; μ is the grand mean; G_i is the i th genotype effect; $\text{Row}_{k(j)}$ is the effect of the k th row nested in a replication; $\text{Col}_{l(j)}$ is the effect of the l th column nested in replication and ϵ_{ijkl} is the experimental error.

The model employed for the combined analysis considering all the five environments was:

$$Y_{ijkl} = \mu + G_i + E_j + \text{GE}_{ij} + \text{R}_{k(ij)} + \text{C}_{l(ij)} + \epsilon_{ijkl}$$

where, Y_{ijkl} is the mean yield of the i th genotype ($i = G_1, G_2, \dots, G_{20}$) in the j th environment ($j = \text{Ageadone, Challam, Manga, Nyankpala and Tinguri}$); μ is the grand mean, G_i is the i th genotypic effect; E_j is the j th environment effect; GE_{ij} is the interaction effect of the i th genotype of the j th environment, $\text{R}_{k(ij)}$ is the effect of row nested in environment, $\text{C}_{l(ij)}$ is the effect of column nested in environment and ϵ_{ijkl} is the experimental error.

The analysis of the effect of genotype main effects and genotype \times environment interactions on grain yield of fonio was performed using the GGEbiplots v. 0.1.3 (Dumble, 2022) R package. Before plotting the graphs on grain yield, data scaling was performed by dividing each value by the highest value. This was done to harmonize the scale to ensure that grain yield ranged between 0 and 1 (Al Shalabi *et al.*, 2006).

Principal component analysis was performed using the FactoMineR (Lê *et al.*, 2008) R package and the factoextra v. 1.0.7 (Kassambara & Mundt, 2020) R package was used to plot the PCA. Pearson's linear correlation analysis was performed with the *corr_coef* function in the metan v. 1.18.0. (Olivoto & Lucio, 2020) R package

Table 3.3.3 List of 20 fonio accessions evaluated in five environments

Accession name	Accession code	Morphological cluster	Community of collection	Days to 50% flowering	Grain weight/plant (g)
C031702	G1	Cluster B	Ando Nyamanu	73	6.3
C031703	G2	Cluster A	Ando Nyamanu	64	5.7
C060801	G3	Cluster B	Kudani	67	14.4
C080101	G4	Cluster B	Ando Nderenu	72	11.2
S010101	G5	Cluster C	Liwalbu	76	17.4
S040101	G6	Cluster B	Nakpel Konkomba	75	15.8
S080301	G7	Cluster A	Toma	62	6.2
<i>Wagadoga</i>	G8	Cluster A	NA	59	9.3
Z010601	G9	Cluster B	Mangoase	73	15.9
Z020102	G10	Cluster B	Kpalgagbini	73	10.3
C031701	G11	Cluster C	Ando Nyamanu	83	11.0
C070301	G12	Cluster C	Wonjuga	91	11.2
C070402	G13	Cluster C	Wonjuga	87	7.6
<i>Nfonikpa</i>	G14	Cluster C	NA	82	14.7
S040401	G15	Cluster C	Nakpel Konkomba	84	17.9
S050102	G16	Cluster C	Gbangbanpong	87	15.6
S080302	G17	Cluster C	Toma	93	7.9
S080401	G18	Cluster C	Toma	91	17.4
Z010701	G19	Cluster C	Mangoase	102	7.8
Z020101	G20	Cluster C	Kpalgagbini	100	7.4

NA= accessions were received from Kundok Development Consult and the community of collection could not be traced.

3.3.3 RESULTS

The combined analysis of variance indicated a significant ($P < 0.05$) genotype and environment effects for all the traits measured (Table 3.3.4). The interaction effect of genotype \times environment was significant for plant height, number of days to 50% flowering, number of racemes per panicle, flag leaf length, flag leaf width, grain yield and 1000 seed weight. On the contrary, genotype \times environment interaction effect was not significant ($P > 0.05$) for SPAD chlorophyll meter reading (SCMR), number of seeds per raceme and raceme length. The analysis of variance for each environment is presented in Appendices 32 to 34.

Table 3.3.4 Mean squared estimates for growth and yield components

Source of variation	Genotype (DF=19)	Environment (DF=4)	G×E (DF=76)
Plant height (cm)	508.340 ***	971.310 ***	56.750 **
SCMR	60.304 ***	252.623 ***	20.300 ns
Days 50% flowering	2226.880 ***	163.000 **	38.230 **
Number of racemes per panicle	0.103 ***	0.278 ***	0.026 ***
Number of seeds per raceme	12.048 ***	2.321 *	0.654 ns
Flag leaf length (cm)	6.358 ***	14.359 ***	248.927 ***
Flag leaf width (cm)	0.005 ***	0.007 *	0.002 *
Raceme length (cm)	15.205 ***	7.922 **	1.081 ns
Grain yield (kg/ha)	217798.000 ***	280313.000 **	55702.000 ***
1000 seed weight (g)	0.019 **	0.031 *	0.012 *

* = significant at 0.05, ** = significant at 0.01, *** = significant at 0.001 and ns= non significant; SCMR=SPAD chlorophyll meter reading; G×E= Genotype \times environment interaction; Number of racemes per panicle and Number of seeds per raceme were transformed using the Square Root transformation.

3.3.3.1 Mean performance of fonio genotypes across environments

Significant differences ($P < 0.05$) were observed among genotypes for all traits measured across test environments. Plant height ranged from 66.60 cm to 95.50 cm with a mean of 80.30 ± 1.62 cm (Table 3.3.5). Genotype Z010701 (95.50 cm) produced the tallest plants while the shortest plants were produced by genotype S080301 (66.60 cm). SPAD chlorophyll meter reading ranged from 31.50 to 39.20 with a mean of 34.23 ± 1.14 . Genotype S080301 had the highest SCMR value which was followed by genotype C031703 (37.60) while genotype Z020101 had the least (31.50).

Number of days to 50% flowering was significantly influenced by the effect of genotypes across test environments. It ranged between 64 days and 104 days with an average of 83 ± 1.23 days to flowering. Genotype S080301 (64 days) was the earliest to flower whilst genotype Z020101 (104 days) took the longest days to flowering. The length of the flag leaf varied from 6.06 cm to 8.36 cm with a mean of 7.20 ± 0.28 cm. Genotype Z020102 (8.36 cm) produced plants with the longest flag leaf, and this was significantly longer than flag leaf in most of the genotypes except genotypes Z020101 (8.02 cm), Z010601 (8.06 cm), Z010701 (7.80 cm), S040101 (7.77 cm), S010101 (7.73 cm), C031702 (7.70 cm) and C060801 (7.90 cm). Flag leaf width ranged from 0.30 cm to 0.37 cm with a mean of 0.35 ± 0.01 cm. Genotypes *Nfonikpa*, Z010701 and Z020102 had plants with the widest flag leaf (0.37 cm) while genotype S080301 produced plants with the smallest flag leaf (0.30 cm).

Number of racemes per panicle ranged from 3.11 to 4.27 with a mean of 3.76 ± 0.11 . Genotype C070301 (4.27) produced the highest number of racemes per panicle across environments while the genotype, *Wagadoga* (3.11), had the least number of racemes per panicle. Raceme number per panicle in genotype C070301 was significantly different from all the genotypes except genotypes S050102 (4.16) and S080401 (4.18). The longest raceme was observed in genotype Z010701 (12.70 cm) which significantly differed from all the genotypes except genotype Z020101 (12.60 cm). Significant differences were also observed among most of the genotypes for raceme length which ranged between 8.70 cm and 12.70 cm with a mean of 11.22 ± 0.24 cm (Table 5.5). Number of seeds per raceme ranged from 80 to 151 with a mean of 123 ± 4.60 . Significant genotypic differences were observed among most of the genotypes. Genotype C070402 had the highest number of seeds per raceme followed by S080302

(145 grains) while genotype S080301 (80 grains) produced the least number of seeds per raceme. The weight of 1000 seeds ranged between 0.48 g to 0.65 g with a mean of 0.53 ± 0.03 g. The genotype, *Wagadoga*, produced the heaviest seed weight which significantly differed from all the genotypes except for genotype Z020102 which had 1000 seed weight of 0.59 g.

3.3.3.2 Grain yield of fonio across environments

Mean grain yield of the genotypes across the different environments is presented in Table 3.3.6. The grain yield of fonio ranged from 283.9 kg/ha to 782.9 kg/ha with a mean of 560.7 ± 40 kg/ha. Genotype C070402 produced the highest grain yield which was significantly higher than most of the genotypes except genotypes C031702 (587.9 kg/ha), C031701 (645.8 kg/ha), C070301 (707.3 kg/ha), *Nfonikpa* (603.1 kg/ha), S010101 (642.1 kg/ha), S040101 (686.9 kg/ha), S040401 (636.7 kg/ha), S080302 (617.5 kg/ha) and S080401 (718.5 kg/ha).

Interaction of effect of genotype and environment was significant for grain yield. Grain yield of fonio at Ageadone ranged from 303.2 kg/ha to 652.5 kg/ha with a mean of 456.2 ± 50 kg/ha. The highest yielding genotype in this environment was S050102 while the least performing genotype for grain yield was genotype Z010601 (303.2 kg/ha). At Challam, fonio grain yield ranged from 183.3 kg/ha to 867.0 kg/ha with a mean of 500.6 ± 90 kg/ha. Genotype C070402 produced the highest grain yield followed by S040101 (819.2 kg/ha) while Z020101 produced the lowest. The grain yield of fonio observed at Manga varied from 272.4 kg/ha to 838.7 kg/ha with a mean of 567.1 ± 104 kg/ha. The highest performance was observed in genotype C031702 (838.7 kg/ha) followed by C080101 (787.9 kg/ha) while the least grain yield was produced by genotype Z010701 (272.4 kg/ha). Genotype, C070402 (1053.1 kg/ha), produced the highest grain yield in Nyankpala while S080301 (315.7 kg/ha) produced the least. Average grain yield recorded in this environment was 678.6 ± 140 kg/ha.

Table 3.3.5 Performance of 20 fonio genotypes in five environments

Genotype	Accession code	PH	SCMR	DFF	FLL	FLW	NRP	RL	NSR	TSW
C031702	G1	82.20	34.10	73.00	7.70	0.35	3.62 (1.90)	10.27	104.00 (10.19)	0.55
C031703	G2	69.60	37.60	65.00	6.23	0.31	3.15 (1.77)	9.24	87.00 (9.34)	0.52
C060801	G3	82.80	34.30	74.00	7.90	0.36	3.64 (1.91)	10.90	108.00 (10.38)	0.53
C080101	G4	78.70	35.60	72.00	7.14	0.34	3.95 (1.99)	10.74	104.00 (10.21)	0.54
S010101	G5	77.20	33.00	80.00	7.73	0.34	3.56 (1.89)	11.72	135.00 (11.60)	0.55
S040101	G6	78.40	34.30	77.00	7.77	0.36	3.85 (1.96)	10.80	120.00 (10.95)	0.54
S080301	G7	66.60	39.20	64.00	6.06	0.30	3.25 (1.80)	8.70	80.00 (8.93)	0.53
<i>Wagadoga</i>	G8	70.30	37.40	65.00	6.38	0.31	3.11 (1.76)	9.92	99.00 (9.94)	0.65
Z010601	G9	83.80	35.90	77.00	8.06	0.35	3.65 (1.91)	11.12	113.00 (10.62)	0.54
Z020102	G10	83.90	33.30	75.00	8.36	0.37	3.85 (1.96)	10.81	106.00 (10.29)	0.59
C031701	G11	79.00	33.50	89.00	6.16	0.35	3.64 (1.91)	11.87	133.00 (11.55)	0.55
C070301	G12	82.30	32.30	96.00	6.98	0.35	4.27 (2.07)	12.05	141.00 (11.86)	0.48
C070402	G13	82.10	32.40	94.00	7.34	0.35	3.91 (1.98)	11.92	151.00 (12.29)	0.52
<i>Nfonikpa</i>	G14	81.10	31.90	91.00	7.08	0.37	4.00 (2.00)	11.50	134.00 (11.58)	0.54
S040401	G15	80.10	34.90	90.00	7.07	0.36	3.84 (1.96)	11.90	136.00 (11.67)	0.50
S050102	G16	79.90	34.30	89.00	6.90	0.36	4.16 (2.04)	11.97	134.00 (11.56)	0.51
S080302	G17	80.70	32.90	94.00	6.48	0.34	3.87 (1.97)	12.06	145.0 (12.05)	0.49
S080401	G18	81.30	34.30	94.00	6.77	0.35	4.18 (2.04)	11.63	141.00 (11.86)	0.49
Z010701	G19	95.50	31.80	103.00	7.80	0.37	3.71 (1.93)	12.70	141.00 (11.86)	0.49
Z020101	G20	90.50	31.50	104.00	8.02	0.36	3.89 (1.97)	12.60	140.00 (11.85)	0.51
Mean		80.30	34.23	83.00	7.20	0.35	3.76 (1.94)	11.22	122.53 (11.03)	0.53
SE		1.62	1.14	1.23	0.28	0.01	0.11 (0.33)	0.24	4.60 (2.14)	0.03

SE= standard error of the mean; PH= plant height (cm); SCMR= SPAD chlorophyll meter reading; DFF= days to 50% flowering; FLL= flag leaf length (cm); FLW= flag leaf width (cm); NRP= number of racemes per panicle (transformed); RL= raceme length (cm); NSR= number of seeds per raceme (transformed); TSW= 1000 seed weight (g).

At Tinguri, the grain yield of fonio ranged between 266.1 kg/ha and 908.1 kg/ha with a mean of 601.2 ± 90 kg/ha. Similarly, the highest grain yield was produced by genotype C070402 while genotype S080301 produced the lowest. Among environments, the highest grain yield was obtained at Nyankpala (678.6 kg/ha) while the least grain yield was observed at Ageadone (456.2 kg/ha). The mean grain yield across the environments was 560.7 kg/ha.

Table 3.3.6 Grain yield of 20 fonio genotypes evaluated in five environments

Genotype	Code	Ageadone	Challam	Manga	Nyankpala	Tinguri	Mean
C031702	G1	526.3	510.7	838.7	662.9	401.1	587.9
C031703	G2	509.2	230.3	474.5	342.5	444.7	400.3
C060801	G3	330.2	466.5	673.5	480.6	556.4	501.4
C080101	G4	451.0	440.9	787.9	443.9	463.6	517.5
S010101	G5	521.8	622.2	688.5	553.1	824.7	642.1
S040101	G6	596.9	819.2	663.3	677.4	678.0	686.9
S080301	G7	318.0	225.5	294.0	315.7	266.1	283.9
<i>Wagadoga</i>	G8	320.0	355.0	414.5	536.7	327.3	390.7
Z010601	G9	303.2	457.6	770.4	481.3	489.2	500.3
Z020102	G10	310.2	601.9	656.7	442.9	625.5	527.4
C031701	G11	506.1	552.7	536.6	849.3	784.3	645.8
C070301	G12	577.2	791.6	518.7	813.1	836.0	707.3
C070402	G13	403.7	867.4	682.1	1053.1	908.1	782.9
<i>Nfonikpa</i>	G14	642.0	498.6	394.7	983.7	496.5	603.1
S040401	G15	592.1	567.1	592.9	683.7	747.5	636.7
S050102	G16	652.5	420.9	284.4	870.1	571.5	559.9
S080302	G17	456.1	521.9	574.5	865.8	669.2	617.5
S080401	G18	352.2	677.7	692.1	1009.1	861.1	718.5
Z010701	G19	345.0	200.1	272.4	717.0	443.6	395.6
Z020101	G20	410.0	183.3	531.3	789.9	628.8	508.7
Mean		456.2	500.6	567.1	678.6	601.2	560.7
SE		97.01	96.92	97.06	96.91	97.12	

SE= standard error of the mean

3.3.3.3 GGE biplot analysis

The first two principal component axes of the GGE biplot accounted for 81.89% of the total variation in grain yield of fonio with PC1 and PC2 contributing 57.29% and 24.60% respectively (Fig 3.3.1). The biplot showed variable relationships among the fonio genotypes and the environments as depicted by angles between the environment vectors. From the biplot, a positive correlation was observed between Ageadone and Nyankpala (similar environments) while Nyankpala and Manga were negatively correlated (an obtuse angle between the vectors). However, both Challam and Tinguri were positively correlated to Manga (acute angle between the environment vectors).

Figure 3.3.1 GGE biplot between 20 fonio genotypes and environments.

G1= C031702; G2= C031703; G3= C060801; G4= C080101; G5= S010101; G6= S040101; G7= S080301; G8= *Wagadoga*; G9= Z010601; G10= Z020102; G11= C031701; G12= C070301; G13= C070402; G14= *Nfonikpa*; G15= S040401; G16= S050102; G17= S080302; G18= S080401; G19= Z010701; G20= Z020101

3.3.3.3.1 Discriminativeness and representativeness

The environment-vector view of the GGE biplot for the grain yield across the five test environments showed the discriminatory power (informativeness) of the different test environments (Fig 3.3.2). Nyankpala had the highest discriminatory power followed by Manga, Challam and Tinguri. Ageadone had the lowest discriminatory ability for grain yield due to the length of the environment vectors from the biplot. This shows that the magnitude of the variation in grain yield among the genotypes was higher in Nyankpala compared to the other test environments. Although Tinguri had moderate discriminatory power, it was more representative based on its smaller angle with the average environment coordination (AEC) axis.

Figure 3.3.2 GGE biplot of discriminatory and representative environments.

G1= C031702; G2= C031703; G3= C060801; G4= C080101; G5= S010101; G6= S040101; G7= S080301; G8= *Wagadoga*; G9= Z010601; G10= Z020102; G11= C031701; G12= C070301; G13= C070402; G14= *Nfonikpa*; G15= S040401; G16= S050102; G17= S080302; G18= S080401; G19= Z010701; G20= Z020101

3.3.3.3.2 Ranking of environments

Figure 3.3.3 shows the comparison biplot depicting the relationship between the test environments and the hypothetical ideal environment (centre of the concentric circles) which is highly discriminatory and representative of all the environments. Tinguri was ranked as the best environment due to its proximity to the centre of the concentric circles. Challam was the next ranked environment followed by Ageadone. However, Nyankpala and Manga were the least ranked environments since they are farther from the centre of the concentric circles.

Figure 3.3.3 Ranking environments relative to the ideal test environment.

G1= C031702; G2= C031703; G3= C060801; G4= C080101; G5= S010101; G6= S040101; G7= S080301; G8= *Wagadoga*; G9= Z010601; G10= Z020102; G11= C031701; G12= C070301; G13= C070402; G14= *Nfonikpa*; G15= S040401; G16= S050102; G17= S080302; G18= S080401; G19= Z010701; G20= Z020101

3.3.3.3 Mean performance and stability of genotypes

The average-environment coordination (AEC) view of the GGE biplot shows the mean performance and stability of the 20 fonio genotypes for grain yield across the environments (Fig 3.3.4). The single-arrowed line (average environment coordination abscissa) which points to direction of higher mean grain yield showed G13 (C070402) as having the highest mean grain yield. This was followed by G18 (S080401) and G12 (C070301) with G7 (S080301) having the lowest mean yield. The perpendicular line (AEC ordinate) to the AEC abscissa line separated genotypes into below average performance (left side of the AEC ordinate axis) and above average performance (right side of the AEC ordinate axis). Genotypes G14 (*Nfonikpa*), G17 (S080302), G15 (S040401), G5 (S010101), G11 (C031701), G6 (S040101), G12 (C070301), G18 (S080401) and G13 (C070402) all had above average grain yield. On the contrary, genotypes G1 (C031702), G10 (Z020102), G16 (S050102), G3 (C060801), G9 (Z010601), G20 (Z020101), G4 (C080101), G19 (Z010701), G8 (*Wagadoga*), G2 (C031703) and G7 (S080301) had mean grain yield below average yield across environments. The plot also shows stability in grain yield of genotypes across environments. The biplot identified G16 (S050102) as the most unstable genotype based on its long projection onto the AEC abscissa line. This was followed by G14 (*Nfonikpa*) whilst G7 and G15 had very stable grain yield across environments due to their short projection onto the AEC abscissa line. Whereas G15 combined high stability with above-average grain yield, G7 consistently had below average below-average grain yield which makes it undesirable.

Figure 3.3.4 GGE biplot of mean performance and stability in grain yield.

G1= C031702; G2= C031703; G3= C060801; G4= C080101; G5= S010101; G6= S040101; G7= S080301; G8= *Wagadoga*; G9= Z010601; G10= Z020102; G11= C031701; G12= C070301; G13= C070402; G14= *Nfonikpa*; G15= S040401; G16= S050102; G17= S080302; G18= S080401; G19= Z010701; G20= Z020101

3.3.3.3.4 “Which won where”

The polygon view of the GGE biplot (which won where) showing the performance of the genotypes in each environment is presented in Fig 3.3.5. The vertex genotypes are the outermost genotypes through which the polygon was connected. Vertex genotypes associated with environments in sectors are the winning genotypes in those environments. From the biplot, although fonio genotypes G4 (C080101), G7 (S080301) and G19 (Z010701) were vertex genotypes, they were not associated with any environment and were consistently poor across all the environments. All the five environments almost fell into one sector signifying the presence of a single mega-environment. Vertex genotype G13 (C070402) had the highest mean grain yield and was the winning genotype in Nyankpala, Tinguri and Challam. Although G16 (S050102), a vertex genotype, produced the highest grain yield in Ageadone, its average yield across environments was lower than the overall average.

3.3.3.3.5 Ranking of genotypes (Ideal genotype)

The GGE biplot showing the ranking of the genotypes in relation to the ideal genotype is presented in Fig 3.3.6. An ideal genotype should combine high mean grain yield with high stability across environments. The ideal genotype is located on the AEC abscissa line in the center of the concentric circle. From the biplot fonio genotype G13 (C070402) is the closest genotype to the ideal genotype. It had the highest mean performance across the test environments, and it was highly stable. Other desirable genotypes included G18 (S080401), G12 (C070301) and G6 (S040101) which combined high grain yield with good stability. Genotype G7 (S080301) was the least desirable since it the outermost genotype with consistently poor grain yield across environments.

Figure 3.3.5 GGE biplot showing the “which won where” for grain yield.

G1= C031702; G2= C031703; G3= C060801; G4= C080101; G5= S010101; G6= S040101; G7= S080301; G8= *Wagadoga*; G9= Z010601; G10= Z020102; G11= C031701; G12= C070301; G13= C070402; G14= *Nfonikpa*; G15= S040401; G16= S050102; G17= S080302; G18= S080401; G19= Z010701; G20= Z020101

Figure 3.3.6 GGE biplot showing the “ideal genotype” for grain yield

G1= C031702; G2= C031703; G3= C060801; G4= C080101; G5= S010101; G6= S040101; G7= S080301; G8= *Wagadoga*; G9= Z010601; G10= Z020102; G11= C031701; G12= C070301; G13= C070402; G14= *Nfonikpa*; G15= S040401; G16= S050102; G17= S080302; G18= S080401; G19= Z010701; G20= Z020101

3.3.3.4 Principal component analysis (PCA)

The first two principal component axes accounted for 79.75% of the total variation among the 20 fonio genotypes evaluated across five test environments (Table 3.3.7). These two PCs had eigenvalues greater than one (unity). PC1 accounted for 64.42% of the variation. This PC axis was attributed to traits such as raceme length, SPAD chlorophyll meter reading, number of days to 50% flowering, number of seeds per raceme, plant height, flag leaf width, number of racemes per panicle and grain yield. The second PC axis, which accounted for 15.33% of the total variation among the genotypes, was mainly driven by flag leaf length and 1000 seed weight.

Table 3.3.7 Principal component analysis of growth and yield components

Trait	PC1	PC2
Plant height (cm)	0.712	0.162
SPAD chlorophyll meter reading	0.855	0.016
Days to 50% flowering	0.836	0.056
Flag leaf length (cm)	0.216	0.660
Flag leaf width (cm)	0.707	0.164
Number of racemes per panicle	0.680	0.032
Raceme length (cm)	0.892	0.005
Number of seeds per raceme	0.818	0.090
Grain yield (kg/ha)	0.438	0.092
1000 seed weight (g)	0.290	0.254
Eigenvalue	6.442	1.533
Percent of variation (%)	64.42	15.33
Cumulative variation (%)	64.42	79.75

The figures in bold represent the traits that contributed to the variance for that principal component axis

3.3.3.5 Phenotypic correlations among measured traits

Pearson's correlation analysis among the ten traits examined across the five test environments revealed significant ($P < 0.05$) and positive associations among most of the traits (Fig 3.3.7). Grain yield was significant and positively correlated with number of days to 50% flowering, flag leaf width, number of racemes per panicle, raceme length and number of seeds per raceme. It was, however, significant and negatively correlated with SPAD chlorophyll meter reading. The correlations between grain yield and plant height, flag leaf length and 1000 seed weight were not significant ($P > 0.05$). The weight of one thousand seeds was significant but negatively correlated with number of days to 50% flowering, number of racemes per panicle, raceme length and number of seeds per raceme. The number of days to 50% flowering was significantly and positively correlated with plant height, flag leaf width, number of racemes per panicle, raceme length and number of seeds per raceme.

Figure 3.3.7 Pearson's correlation among traits phenotyped across environments.

TSW= 1000 seed weight (g); FLL= Flag leaf length (cm); PH= Plant height (cm); FLW= Flag leaf width (cm); GY = Grain yield (kg/ha); NRP= Number of racemes per panicle; DFF= Days to 50% flowering; RL= Raceme length (cm); NSR= Number of seeds per raceme; SCMR= SPAD chlorophyll meter reading

3.3.4 DISCUSSION

The concept of genotype \times environment interaction and its effect on the selection of superior cultivars in multi-environment trials are important in plant breeding (De Leon *et al.*, 2016; Dias *et al.*, 2018; Yan & Tinker, 2006).

The combined analysis of variance indicated significant genotype \times environment interaction for grain yield and most of the traits except for SCMR, raceme length and number of seeds per raceme. The significant genotype \times environment interactions for grain yield indicated that fonio genotypes responded differently in the test environments resulting in variations in their mean performances across the environments. For instance, genotype G16 (S050102) was the winning genotype in Ageadone however its performance was below average in three of the environments, Challam, Manga and Tinguri. Similarly, genotype G1 (C031702) produced the highest grain yield in Manga but its performance was below average in Nyankpala and Tinguri. Variations in grain yield were observed among many of the genotypes across the environments. This result is contrary to Addai *et al.* (2022) who reported non-significant genotype \times location interaction effect for grain yield when they evaluated five fonio accessions in two locations in northern Ghana. The significant genotype \times environment interaction in the current study may be due to the higher number of diverse genotypes as well as the number of test environments used. Genotype \times environment interaction tends to be larger when variations between environments are large. Therefore, if the variation among the environments is not large, the effect of genotype \times environment may be negligible. The magnitude of genotype \times environment interaction is greater in more favourable environments than harsh environments (Bratković *et al.*, 2024; Saltz *et al.*, 2018) so having more environments offer greater discriminatory power than having fewer environments. So, it is possible that the variations between the two locations in their study were not large enough to elicit significant genotype \times environment interaction for grain yield. There was a highly significant difference in grain yield among the genotypes which ranged from 283.9 kg/ha to 782.9 kg/ha with a mean of 560.7 kg/ha. This showed that considerable genetic diversity existed among the genotypes for grain yield production which can be harnessed for genetic improvement.

One key physiological cause of yield variation in crops is the time of maturity. Flowering time is an important trait which affects grain yield of crops. It is therefore expected that the current results might have been influenced by the variations observed among the genotypes for number of days to 50% flowering. Early flowering genotypes (less than 70 days) such as C031703, *Wagadoga* and S080301 had lower grain yield compared to intermediate genotypes flowering between 80 and 96 days. The early flowering genotypes had shorter plant height averaging 70 cm while the intermediate genotypes had plant height of 80 cm. There was a positive correlation between flowering time and plant height. The tallest plants were recorded among the late flowering genotypes (above 100 days after sowing), Z010701 and Z020101 with a plant height above 90 cm. Grain yield of the late flowering genotypes were lower than the intermediate genotypes. This observation agrees with Addai *et al.* (2022) who reported lower grain yields in late maturing fonio genotypes. This trend could also be due to the changing climatic conditions that shortened the growing season and as such poor grain filling for late duration genotypes. Although genotype \times environment interaction was not significant for raceme length and number of grains per raceme, significant differences were observed among the genotypes. This shows that these traits may be highly heritable, and selections based on them could be effective.

The study further revealed that flowering time had a significant and positive correlation with raceme length and number of grains per raceme. Early flowering genotypes had shorter racemes and lower number of grains whilst the intermediate and late flowering genotypes had longer racemes and greater number of grains. This suggests that the longer it takes a cultivar to mature, the higher grain yield. This is because a longer growing season delays leaf senescence and prolong the grain filling period thereby allowing enough photosynthates to accumulate in grains before the season ends (Moradi *et al.*, 2022; Zheng *et al.*, 2022; Zhiipao *et al.*, 2023). However, grain yield of late flowering genotypes was lower than the intermediate flowering genotypes. This observation could be attributed to terminal drought which can impact negatively on grain filling in long duration cultivars especially when the period coincides with high temperatures (Yang *et al.*, 2017).

Plant height was not significantly correlated with grain yield. This observation is in accordance with Addai *et al.* (2022) who reported non-significant correlation between plant height at maturity and grain yield of fonio. Tall plants may invest a lot of

resources in developing vegetative structures at the expense of reproductive structures. However, if the reproductive phase of the crop coincides with terminal drought, grain filling will be negatively impacted leading to low grain yield.

The main effects of environment significantly influenced grain yield and other agronomic traits among the fonio genotypes. This underscores the importance of multi-location evaluations to measure the magnitude of the effect of genotype \times environment interaction on traits of importance before cultivar recommendation. The results of the present study are similar to the observation of Addai *et al.* (2022) who found a significant location effect on grain yield of fonio in Ghana. From their report, mean grain yield of fonio in the Guinea Savanna agro-ecological zone (913.25 kg/ha) was greater than that of the Sudan Savanna agro-ecological zone (788.42 kg/ha). From the current study, the highest mean grain yield was recorded at Nyankpala while the lowest was recorded at Ageadone. Although the GGE biplot revealed that these two environments were highly correlated, the difference in grain yield may be ascribed to the differences in soil texture and rainfall amount. For instance, soil texture at Nyankpala was sandy loam while that of Ageadone was loamy sand. This suggests the presence of significant variations among the environments to elicit genotype \times environment interaction on grain yield of fonio. Nyankpala and Manga were negatively correlated with high levels of crossover genotype \times environment interactions between the two environments. Similar observations on the importance of environmental factors particularly rainfall and soil variability as the cause of grain yield variations have been reported in crops such as wheat and maize (Basso *et al.*, 2012; De Vita *et al.*, 2007). Rankings of the genotypes for grain yield were completely different in the two environments. This observation is in accordance with Yan & Tinker (2006) who indicated that crossover genotype \times environment interaction among environments can result in negative correlation between the environments.

One important use of the GGE biplot is for examining the discriminatory and representativeness of environments. Results from the current study showed that two environments, Nyankpala and Manga, were highly discriminatory even though less representative. Yan & Tinker (2006) indicated that test environments with high discriminatory power are needed for effective evaluation of genotypes although such environments may be ideal for recommending superior genotypes with specific adaptation. On the other hand, Tinguri had moderate discriminatory power but was the

most representative environment. This environment could be utilized as a mega environment in future evaluations for selecting genotypes with wide or broad adaptation.

Yan & Tinker (2006) indicated that the GGE biplot analysis is a useful tool in quantifying sensitivities of genotypes to different environmental conditions in multi-environment trials. The GGE biplot analysis proved effective in examining pattern of grain yield and stability among the genotypes in this study. Several studies have employed the use of the GGE biplot to identify genotypes that combined superior performance with high stability across environments (Adu *et al.*, 2013; Olanrewaju *et al.*, 2021; Uchendu *et al.*, 2022). In this study, GGE biplot analysis revealed that genotype G7 (S080301) combined high stability with below average performance across the environments. Its performance remained consistently poor in all the environments and could be described as having static stability. On the contrary, genotype G14 (*Nfonikpa*) which had above average grain yield was identified as highly unstable due to the lower-than-average grain yield it produced in Manga and Tinguri compared to the other environments. This genotype produced its best grain yield in Ageadone and Nyankpala which are highly correlated environments. This suggests that G14 (*Nfonikpa*) could be specifically adapted to these environments. However, genotypes G13 (C070402), G18 (S080401), G12 (C070301), G6 (S040101) G15 (S040401), G17 (S080302), G11 (C031701) and G5 (S010101) were identified as the genotypes that combined high grain yield with good stability in performance across the test environments. These genotypes should be further evaluated in more environments particularly in the major fonio growing areas from where the fonio accessions were collected.

CHAPTER FOUR

4.0 GENERAL DISCUSSION

Fonio (*Digitaria exilis* (Kippist) Stapf) has the potential to address food and nutrition insecurity issues for many households in West Africa in the face of climate change (Ayenan *et al.*, 2018; Gari, 2002). The crop thrives well on marginal soils with poor soil fertility (Ayenan *et al.*, 2018; Gari, 2002) and should be promoted to curb the negative impact of climate change in an era where the production of the major staple cereals is challenging (Adoukonou-Sagbadja *et al.*, 2006; Barnaud *et al.*, 2022; Diop *et al.*, 2018). Nonetheless, fonio research has been neglected globally compared to other cereals such as rice, maize, sorghum and millet (Barnaud *et al.*, 2022; Gari, 2002). In Ghana, there is a paucity of information on the genetic diversity and agronomic performance among fonio accessions. There is inadequate information on the effect of genotype \times environment interaction on the grain yield and other traits as well as adaptable varieties to specific environments. No fonio varieties have been released with no formal seed system to regulate the dissemination of varieties in communities where the crop is cultivated. Farmers therefore rely on landraces with questionable quality and yield potential. These challenges have implications on conservation and efficient utilization of fonio genetic resources (Govindaraj *et al.*, 2015; Adjebeng-Danquah *et al.*, 2020). This study thus focused on assessing the genetic diversity and population structure among fonio accessions using SSR markers and associated ethnobotanical data. It examined the agronomic performance and morphological diversity among the fonio accessions. Lastly, the study analyzed the effects of genotype \times environment interaction on fonio grain yield and other traits and selected genotypes with high and stable yield.

4.1 Genetic diversity and structure among fonio accessions

The success of any crop improvement program is hinged on the level of genetic diversity in key traits among the available germplasm and the heritability of these traits (Govindaraj *et al.*, 2015; Salgotra & Chauhan, 2023). Assessment of genetic diversity in crops is an essential pre-breeding activity aimed at identifying distinct genotypes, developing efficient conservation strategies and effective utilization of the genetic resources (Govindaraj *et al.*, 2015; Adjebeng-Danquah *et al.*, 2020). However, crop

genetic diversity has been reported to be influenced by the interaction between the genotype, environment and social factors i.e. G×E×S (Leclerc & Coppens d'Eeckenbrugge, 2011). Therefore, it is important to consider the socio-cultural factors in genetic diversity studies. Leclerc & Coppens d'Eeckenbrugge (2011) emphasized that human activities such as selection, cropping systems, seed exchange practices and long-term interaction with environmental factors contribute to the structuring of crop genetic diversity.

In this study, 21 farmer-named fonio cultivars belonging almost exclusively to one ethnic group were identified. Farmer-named fonio cultivars can be considered as an identity mark, suggesting the existence of a social barrier between the ethnic groups. This suggests that seed exchanges among farmers from different communities are not frequent. This observation is relevant for crops without formal seed systems such as fonio. Since fonio is an autogamous crop, the large proportion of seeds that is self-produced by farmers implies that genetic diversity within and between cultivars remain the same season after season. Farmer-saved seed practices induce interethnic variability of a crop because of selection and limited seed mediated gene flow between ethnic groups (Delêtre *et al.*, 2011; Leclerc & Coppens d'Eeckenbrugge, 2011).

Population structure analysis revealed six ancestral populations among the 140 Ghanaian fonio accessions. The highest number of the accessions (64 individuals) was classified as admixture at an ancestry coefficient of at least 70%. The admixed population comprised fonio accessions from all the four ethnic groups. A greater number of the admixed population was collected from the Anufor farmers and could be due to the fact that this ethnic group contributed the highest number of accessions compared to the other groups. Although significant F_{ST} was observed among some of the ethnic groups, the social organization of fonio genetic diversity in Ghana was largely influenced by farmer-named cultivars, which have contributed to maintaining fonio genetic diversity over time. This observation corroborates the findings of Diop *et al.* (2023) who reported influence of the ethnicity of farmers on Senegal's fonio genetic diversity. They observed that Fulani people cultivated early maturing fonio accessions, whilst the Balante ethnic group cultivated late maturing accessions with no seed exchange between them. Other studies have also reported the influence of

ethnicity on genetic diversity patterns of crops such as sorghum (Labeyrie *et al.*, 2014), maize (Orozco-Ramírez *et al.*, 2016) and pearl millet (Naino Jika *et al.*, 2017).

The study revealed significant genetic variability among the fonio accessions, which is important considering the restricted area of fonio cultivation in Ghana. Notably, farmer-named fonio cultivars played a substantial role in shaping this genetic diversity. The findings underscore the pivotal role of farmers in long-term preservation of fonio genetic diversity. Moreover, the Ghanaian fonio accessions are distinct and stand out in comparison to the global diversity observed in the West African collections. Although some Ghanaian fonio accessions originated from Togo and the cultivation areas are close to each other, there is unique genetic diversity between the accessions from these two countries (Kaczmarek *et al.*, 2023).

To understand the factors contributing to this unique diversity, future studies should prioritize an in-depth ethnobotanical investigation. This would shed light on farmers' practices, social, environmental and biological factors that have structured the fonio genetic diversity in Ghana. Recognizing the importance of farmers' role in shaping fonio genetic diversity, strategies for the management and conservation of fonio genetic resources should consciously incorporate farmers' knowledge and traditional farming practices (Ceccarelli & Grando, 2002).

The observed genetic diversity among the accessions offers an opportunity for selecting genetically distinct individuals, laying the foundation for tailored product profile development. However, the highly autogamous nature of fonio coupled with its small-sized flowers requires that efficient hybridization strategies are identified to develop new fonio varieties for different market segments.

4.2 Agronomic performance and morphological diversity in fonio

The use of agro-morphological traits in germplasm characterization is not only easy to score but provides opportunity for breeders to evaluate and select superior genotypes for crop improvement purposes (Badu-Apraku *et al.*, 2021; Mitsuhashi, 2024). Assessment of morphological diversity and grouping of fonio accessions into morphotypes have been reported by many authors (Balma *et al.*, 2023; Ibrahim Bio Yerima *et al.*, 2020; Sekloka *et al.*, 2016).

In the current study, assessment of morphological diversity in fonio revealed three morphological clusters. However, the level of morphological diversity among the accessions based on qualitative traits was low. This result is similar to the findings of Ibrahim Bio Yerima *et al.* (2020) and Balma *et al.* (2023) who equally reported low diversity in qualitative traits in fonio in Benin and Burkina Faso respectively. The morphological clustering in this study was significantly influenced by quantitative traits. This observation corroborates the account of Ibrahim Bio Yerima *et al.* (2020) and Nyam *et al.* (2017) who reported greater phenotypic diversity in quantitative traits among fonio accessions compared to qualitative traits. The study therefore focused on the traits that structured the morphological diversity.

Significant differences were observed among the accessions for plant height, number of days to 50% flowering and maturity, leaf blade length, flag leaf length, number of leaves per plant, number of racemes per panicle, raceme length, number of seeds per raceme, grain weight per plant and 1000 seed weight. This provides a great opportunity for selection as suggested by earlier reports on the significance of genetic variability in crop improvement (Amombo *et al.*, 2024; Elshafei *et al.*, 2024; Govindaraj *et al.*, 2015; Mishra *et al.*, 2024; Narain, 2000). Apart from leaf blade length and flag leaf length, the rest of the traits are important for farmers since they contribute to biomass and grain yields. Additionally, these traits can be easily assessed on farmers' fields to aid in the selection of desirable cultivars. Therefore, assessment of diversity at the farm level could focus on traits that reflect the interest of farmers. Hence plant height, crop cycle, plant biomass, number of racemes per panicle, raceme length, number of seeds per raceme and grain weight should be prioritized in the selection of superior fonio accessions.

Average raceme length and number of seeds per raceme recorded in this study are higher than what was reported among 180 fonio accessions from five West African countries (Ibrahim Bio Yerima *et al.*, 2020). This indicates that the Ghanaian accessions possessed longer racemes with higher number of seeds. The diversity in these traits could be useful in improving raceme length and number of seeds among the global fonio collection. This would improve fonio grain yield since raceme length and number of seeds per raceme were found to be significant and positively correlated.

This study revealed ample significant variations in flowering and maturity times among the fonio accessions, agreeing with the findings of studies that classified fonio accessions into different maturity classes (Clottey *et al.*, 2006b; Saidou *et al.*, 2014; Sekloka *et al.*, 2016). Having variability in crop phenology is an important trait in the face of climate change particularly in drier areas with unpredictable rainfall patterns (Mishra *et al.*, 2024). High broad sense heritability estimates were observed for these traits, days to 50% flowering (99%) and days to 50% maturity (97%), indicating that selections based on these traits could result in much progress. This would provide farmers an opportunity to cultivate the most desirable cultivar depending on the rainfall pattern in the locality to avoid crop failure.

Diversity in traits among the morphological clusters could be harnessed by selecting desirable parental cultivars for developing product profiles for diverse market segments. For instance, variation in plant height could be exploited to develop lodging resistant fonio varieties especially when short plants with high yield potential are targeted. To this, there is the need for high-throughput phenotyping of the morphological clusters in important traits with high heritability estimates to provide the basis for parental selection. Farmers and other value chain actors need to be actively involved in the varietal evaluations and selection of promising candidates that meet their needs.

4.3 Effect of genotype × environment interaction on fonio grain yield and other traits

The significance of genotype × environment interaction effects on cultivar selection in multi-environment trials are important in plant breeding (De Leon *et al.*, 2016; Dias *et al.*, 2018; Yan & Tinker, 2006). This is because G × E affects the performance of genotypes in different environments and confounds the recommendation of varieties for different environments. The combined analysis of variance indicated significant genotype × environment interaction for grain yield and most of the traits except for SCMR, raceme length and number of grains per raceme. Since grain yield is the most important trait in fonio, the analysis focused on quantifying the effects of G × E on fonio grain yield.

The variations in the grain yield of fonio in the test environments contradicts the findings of Addai *et al.* (2022) who reported non-significant genotype \times location interaction effect on grain yield of five fonio accessions grown in two locations in northern Ghana. The significant genotype \times environment interaction in the current study could be due to the higher number of diverse genotypes as well as the number of test environments used. The effect of genotype \times environment interaction tends to be larger when variations between environments are large. Therefore, if the variation among the environments is not large, the effect of genotype \times environment may be negligible. The magnitude of genotype \times environment interaction is greater in more favourable environments than harsh environments (Bratković *et al.*, 2024; Saltz *et al.*, 2018) so having more environments offer greater discriminatory power than having fewer environments. So, it is possible that variations between the two locations in their study were not large enough to elicit significant genotype \times environment interaction for grain yield.

The main effects of environment significantly influenced grain yield and other agronomic traits in this study. This underscores the importance of multi-location evaluations to measure the magnitude of the effect of genotype \times environment interaction on traits of importance before cultivar recommendation. Results of the present study are similar to the observation of Addai *et al.* (2022) who found a significant location effect on grain yield of fonio in Ghana. From the current study, the highest mean grain yield was recorded at Nyankpala while the lowest was recorded at Ageadone. This suggests the presence of significant variations among the environments to elicit genotype \times environment interaction on grain yield of fonio. Nyankpala and Manga were negatively correlated with high levels of crossover genotype \times environment interactions between the two environments. This observation is in accordance with Yan & Tinker (2006) who indicated that crossover genotype \times environment interaction among environments can result from negative correlation between the environments.

Statistical tools such as GGE biplot, AMMI, etc are effective in elucidating genotype \times environment interaction in plant breeding and varietal recommendation. For instance, Adu *et al.* (2013), Olanrewaju *et al.* (2021) and Uchendu *et al.* (2022) utilized the GGE biplot in analyzing genotype \times environment interaction effect in maize, Bambara groundnut and cassava respectively. In the present study, the GGE biplot analysis proved effective in examining the pattern of grain yield and stability among the genotypes in this study. Genotype S080301 consistently had below average grain yield across the environments. Genotype, *Nfonikpa*, which had above average grain yield was identified as highly unstable and could be specifically adapted to Nyankpala environment where it produced its highest grain yield. However, genotypes C070402, S080401, C070301, S040101, S040401, S080302, C031701 and S010101 were identified as the genotypes that combined high grain yield with good stability across the test environments. These genotypes should be further evaluated in more environments particularly in the major fonio growing areas from where the fonio accessions were collected.

CHAPTER FIVE

5.0 CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 CONCLUSIONS

The SSR marker assay revealed significant genetic diversity among the fonio accessions to warrant development of efficient conservation strategies in Ghana. The Ghanaian fonio accessions are genetically distinct, particularly those from the Chereponi district, and stand out in comparison to the genetic diversity in the West African collections.

Population structure analysis revealed six ancestral populations with 45% of the accessions being admixtures. The bulk of this admixed population consisted of the accessions collected from the Chereponi district.

There was no isolation by distance pattern between the communities. Some fonio accessions collected from different communities were identified to be duplicates based on the SSR markers suggesting possible free movement of accessions.

Fonio *in-situ* varietal diversity was socially organized, with farmer-named cultivars contributing substantially to the genetic diversity.

The assessment of phenotypic diversity among the fonio accessions revealed higher diversity in quantitative traits compared to qualitative traits.

Genotypic differences were observed among the accessions for most of the agronomic traits to warrant selection.

Estimates of variance components revealed that most of the traits were under genetic control which could be improved through selection and breeding.

Highly significant and positive correlations existed between grain weight and traits such as raceme length, number of racemes per panicle, number of seeds per raceme and maturity time, which could be used in indirect selection for accessions with superior grain yield potential.

Morphological diversity was structured by traits such as plant height, flowering and maturity time, raceme length, number of leaves, raceme number and grain yield. These traits, which are important for farmers, should be emphasized in the evaluation of morphological diversity and selection in fonio.

Three morphological clusters were identified, which will enable the selection of distinct accessions for evaluation in different environments to determine their performance and adaptability.

The effects of genotype \times environment interaction on fonio were significant for grain yield and most of the traits.

Genotypes C070402, S080401, C070301, S040101, and C031701 combined high grain yield with good stability. These genotypes also had broad adaptation and could be selected for environments with similar characteristics to the test environments.

Genotypes *Nfonikpa* and C031702 had specific adaptation in the Nyankpala and Manga environments respectively, where they produced the highest grain yields.

Genotype S080301 consistently had below average grain yield across the environments.

Nyankpala and Manga were highly discriminatory environments while Tinguri was the most representative environment for evaluation of genotypes with broad adaptation.

5.2 RECOMMENDATIONS

Future studies should consider high-density molecular markers such as single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) for genetic diversity and population structure analysis in fonio. Also, Genome-wide association studies (GWAS) should be conducted to identify quantitative trait loci (QTLs) regions that regulate important agronomic traits in fonio.

Future studies should consider a high number of polymorphic SSR markers.

Further studies should prioritize extensive ethnobotanical surveys and focus group discussions to unravel the factors that have organized the pattern of genetic diversity of fonio to understand the evolutionary history and domestication of fonio in Ghana.

Although the study revealed significant genotype \times environment interaction for grain yield and other agronomic traits in fonio, seasonal variation can alter crop performance and ranking of genotypes. Therefore, future studies should consider the effect of multiple years and more environments especially in the areas of collection in genotype \times environment interaction analysis.

The fonio genotypes that combined high grain yield with good stability such as C070402, S080401, C070301, S040101, S040401, S080302, C031701 and S010101, should be further subjected to proximate composition analysis, pests and diseases reaction as well as consumer preference assessment towards release and recommendation to farmers for cultivation.

Targeted breeding programmes could focus on improving traits such as earliness, lodging resistance, non-shattering, seed size and grain yield. There is the need to broaden the genetic base through introduction of diverse fonio accessions from other producing countries.

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APPENDICES

Appendix 1 Fonio germplasm collection in Ghana

Map of Africa highlighting fonio producing countries (A), Map of Ghana with fonio producing regions (B, North East region in yellow; Northern region in orange), District map of Ghana showing the locations of the fonio germplasm collection (C) fonio production fields in the Chereponi district (D and E, ©Anthony Kojo, Chereponi, Ghana)

Appendix 2 Semi-structured questionnaire for fonio germplasm collection

FONIO GERMPLASM COLLECTION AND ETHNOBOTANICAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE

Information on the surveyor

Name / _____ / Surname / _____ / surveyors' number
/ _____ /

Start time / _____ / H _____ / mn; Date: / _____ / _____ / _____ /

Holding Identification Number: / _____ /

TEXT TO READ:

Hello, my name is..... I am a PhD student at the Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology (KNUST). I am collecting ethnobotanical data and fonio accessions for my PhD studies which is looking at analysis of genetic diversity among fonio accessions in Ghana. The PhD studies is part of a broader project sponsored by the EU Horizon 2020 EWA-BELT Project, which seeks to link East and West Africa farming systems into a belt of sustainable intensification. The information you provide will be treated confidentially. It will only be used for statistical analysis and will be put together with responses from other farmers for use in the formulation of programmes and policies to promote more productive and sustainable agriculture. This interview should take approximately one hour. I appreciate your participation in answering these questions. If you have any questions regarding this survey, you are welcome to ask before we begin the interview. I express my gratitude for your participation in this survey in advance.

General Information

Address of the holding

Name of the location: _____

Name of the sub location: _____

GPS coordinates of the holding

Longitude _____

Latitude _____

Altitude _____

I. Record the following information on the respondent

I.1. First name / _____

I.2. Surname / _____/

I.2a Contact No. _____/

I.3. Sex of the respondent: 1. Male /___/; 2. Female /___/

I.4. Ethnic group of the respondent: /_____/

I.5. Marital status:

1 married /___/

2. single /___/

3. divorce /___/

4. widow /___/

I.6. What is your approximate age

/___/<20, /___/20-30, /___/30-40, /___/40-50, /___/50-60, /___/>60)

I.7. Size of household members:

1. Total number of the household members

2. Number of adults (> 16 years)/___/;

3. Number of children (0-16 years)/___/;

4. Number of persons working effectively involved in farm operations /___/.

I.8. Education

1. None /___/; 2. Primary school /___/, 3. secondary school; 4. Adult (tertiary) education /___/, 5. University/___/ 6. other /___/

Passport Data sheet

No.	Category	NUS
1	Date of collection	
2	Country	
3	Region	
4	District	
5	Community	
6	Name of collector	
7	Name of farmer	
8	Gender	
9	Phone contact	
10	Accession code	
11	Name of variety/accession	
12	Meaning of name	
13	Origin of variety/accession	
14	Purpose of cultivation	
15	How long in possession	
16	Selection practice	
17	Noteworthy traits	
18	Days to maturity	
19	Grain colour	
20	Storage type/system (take photo if possible)	
21	Sampling type	
22	Agro-ecology	
27	Remarks	

Appendix 3. Survey and collection of fonio in Sangbana, Chereponi district.

Appendix 4. List of 14 SSR markers used for genotyping fonio accessions

Locus	Forward primers (5' – 3')	Reverse primers (5' – 3')	Repeat motif	Size (bp)	GenBank accession no.
De-04	CATTTTCCCGAA GACAGAGG	GACCTTGTGG CACCCATC	(GAA) ₃₃	258	JN587185
De-05	AAGCCTTGCGTT CTATCTTA	TTAATATGAT GCTACCCCTC A	(GT) ₉	219	JN587186
De-07	TCATGGTGTTC ACTTAATCC	AAATAGATGC CAATCACACC	(GT) ₈	202	JN587188
De-08	TTGGTGGATATT GGAATTATG	TTTACCCAAC GCATAGGTAG	(CA) ₁₃	206	JN587189
De-15	AAAAGTTCCCCT TTAACTCC	AGAAGCAACA GAGGTGAGAA	(CA) ₇	212	JN587196
De-17	GTAACGAACATC GGGTGA	CTGATGGCAA GGATGTGT	(GT) ₆	201	JN587198
De-22	ATCGAGAGTTCA GTGAGTCC	GATCATCAAA CCATTTACCC	(TG) ₆	193	JN587203
De-24	CCTCGATAATGC GTTTGT	CAGCATTTTA ATTGTTACAG	(CT) ₁₈	209	JN587205
De-25	GGCCAGAAGGTA ATCACAG	AAGCAGAAGA GACAAAGCAG	(TC) ₁₈	225	JN587206
De-29	TCCTTGTCCTTAA AATGCTC	TTGTCATCTTC CTCCTGTTC	(CT) ₁₂	179	JN587210
De-34	ACTAACAACCAG CGGTGA	CTAGCAGTGT TTCAATGTGC	(AC) ₁₁	197	JN587215
De-36	GAAGACAGCCCA TTGTTAGA	AGACATTGCC AAGAAAATTG	(CA) ₈	174	JN587217
De-37	TGAACAAATTCC TCTTGCTC	TGGCAATGTT CCATAAAGA	(TTC) ₂₉	198	JN587218
De-38	AAAACGAAAACC AAATCTCA	AGCCCAAGAA GTATTGCTAA	(CA) ₆	207	JN587219

(Barnaud *et al.*, 2012)

Appendix 5 Genotyping of S040401 with SSR markers De_19 and De_22

Appendix 6 A cross-entropy plot depicting the number of ancestral populations

A

B

C

D

Appendix 7 Population structure of 140 fonio accessions using DAPC method

A. cumulative variance versus number of principal components retained. **B.** Value of Bayesian Information Criterion versus number of clusters. **C** and **D.** DAPC scatter plots showing the clustering of 140 fonio accessions as depicted by axes 1 and 2 and 1 and 3 respectively.

Appendix 8 Contingency Table comparing sNMF with DAPC clustering

		sNMF					
DAPC	0	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3	Cluster 4	Cluster 5	Cluster 6
0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0
Cluster 1	15	0	0	1	0	6	3
Cluster 2	5	0	0	0	7	0	0
Cluster 3	15	0	0	27	0	0	0
Cluster 4	10	3	0	0	0	1	0
Cluster 5	7	0	1	0	0	0	8
Cluster 6	11	0	1	0	17	0	0

Chi-squared test (2000 iterations), X-squared = 219.48, p-value (Monte-Carlo simulations) = 0.000498. sNMF= sparse Non-negative Matrix Factorization, DAPC= Discriminant analysis of principal components

Appendix 9 Principal component analysis of farmer-named fonio cultivars

Appendix 10 Gender, age range and educational level of farmers

District	Gender	Number of accessions
Chereponi	Female	28
Chereponi	Male	94
Gushegu	Male	4
Saboba	Male	33
Tatale	Female	1
Tatale	Male	4
Zabzugu	Female	5
Zabzugu	Male	7
Total		176
Female		34 (19%)
Male		142 (81%)

Age range	Number of accessions
less than 30	30
between 31 and 40	45
between 41 to 50	43
between 51 to 60	42
above 60	16
Total	176

Educational level	Number of accessions
None	147
Primary school	12
Secondary school	10
University	3
Adult education	4
Total	176

Appendix 11 Maturity, landrace name and meaning 176 fonio landraces.

Accession	Maturity	Ethnicity of farmer	Name of landrace	Meaning of landrace name
C010101	Early	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	Named after a tribe in Togo
C010201	Late	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	Named after Togo president Yadema
C010301	Early	Anufor	<i>Namba</i>	Namba tribe in Togo
C010401	Early	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	Named after Togo president Yadema
C010501	Early	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	Named after Togo president Yadema
C010601	Late	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	Named after Togo president Yadema
C010701	Early	Anufor	<i>Namba</i>	Named after Togo president Yadema
C010801	Late	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	Named after Togo president Yadema
C010901	Late	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	Named after Togo president Yadema
C011001	Late	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	Named after Togo president Yadema
C011101	Early	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	No idea
C011201	Early	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	Early maturity
C011301	Early	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	No idea
C011401	Early	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	No idea
C011501	Early	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	No idea
C020101	Early	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	No idea
C020201	Early	Anufor	<i>Namba</i>	Namba tribe in Togo
C020301	Early	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	No idea
C020401	Early	Anufor	<i>Namba</i>	No idea
C020501	Early	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	No idea
C020601	Early	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	Named after Togo president Yadema
C020701	Early	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	Named after Togo president Yadema
C020901	Late	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	Named after Togo president Yadema
C021001	Early	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	No idea
C021101	Late	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	No idea
C021201	Late	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	Named after Togo president Yadema
C021301	Late	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	Named after Togo president Yadema
C021401	Early	Anufor	<i>Namba</i>	Namba tribe in Togo
C021501	Early	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	No idea
C030101	Early	Anufor	<i>Namba</i>	No idea
C030201	Late	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	No idea
C030301	Early	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	Named after Togo president Yadema
C030401	Early	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	No idea
C030501	Early	Anufor	<i>Namba</i>	No idea
C030601	Early	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	Named after Togo president Yadema

Note: 2 – 3 months = Early maturing fonio landraces; 3.5 – 5 months = Late maturing fonio landraces

Appendix 11 Maturity, landrace name and meaning 176 fonio landraces.

Accession	Maturity	Ethnicity of farmer	Name of landrace	Meaning of landrace name
C030701	Early	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	Named after Togo president Yadema
C030801	Early	Anufor	<i>Namba</i>	No idea
C030901	Early	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	No idea
C031001	Early	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	No idea
C031101	Early	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	Named after Togo president Yadema
C031201	Early	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	No idea
C031301	Early	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	Named after Togo president Yadema
C031401	Early	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	No idea
C031501	Early	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	Hunger suppressor
C031601	Early	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	Unknown
C031701	Late	Anufor	<i>Nvonikpa</i>	Proper fonio
C031702	Early	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	Named after Togo president Yadema
C031703	Early	Anufor	<i>Namba</i>	No idea
C040101	Early	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	Unknown
C040201	Early	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	Unknown
C040301	Early	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	Named after Togo president Yadema
C040401	Early	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	Named after Togo president Yadema
C040501	Early	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	Unknown
C040601	Early	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	Named after Togo president Yadema
C040701	Early	Anufor	<i>Fefeke</i>	No idea
C040801	Early	Anufor	<i>Fefeke</i>	Simply good
C040901	Early	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	No idea
C041001	Early	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	No idea
C041101	Early	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	No idea
C050101	Early	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	Matures early
C050201	Early	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	No idea
C050301	Early	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	No idea
C050401	Early	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	Named after Togo president Yadema
C050501	Early	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	Named after Togo president Yadema
C050601	Early	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	No idea
C050701	Early	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	No idea
C060101	Early	Anufor	<i>Namba</i>	Namba tribe in Togo
C060201	Early	Anufor	<i>Fefeke</i>	Early maturing
C060301	Early	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	No idea
C060401	Early	Anufor	<i>Fefeke</i>	Early maturing

Note: 2 – 3 months = Early maturing fonio landraces; 3.5 – 5 months = Late maturing fonio landraces

Appendix 11 Maturity, landrace name and meaning 176 fonio landraces.

Accessions	Maturity	Ethnicity of farmer	Name of landrace	Meaning of landrace name
C060501	Early	Anufor	<i>Fefeke</i>	Matures early
C060601	Early	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	None other
C060701	Early	Anufor	<i>Namba</i>	Namba tribe in Togo
C060702	Late	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	Named after Togo president Yadema
C060801	Late	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	Named after Togo president Yadema
C060901	Late	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	Named after Togo president Yadema
C061001	Late	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	No idea
C061101	Late	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	Named after Togo president Yadema
C061201	Late	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	No idea
C061301	Early	Anufor	<i>Fefeke</i>	Matures quickly
C061401	Early	Anufor	<i>Fefeke</i>	Early maturity
C061501	Early	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	Named after Togo president Yadema
C070101	Early	Anufor	<i>Namba</i>	Namba tribe in Togo
C070201	Early	Anufor	<i>Namba</i>	No idea
C070301	Late	Anufor	<i>Fieja</i>	Male fonio
C070401	Early	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	Medium maturing variety
C070501	Late	Anufor	<i>Fieja</i>	Late maturing variety
C070601	Early	Anufor	<i>Namba</i>	Namba tribe in Togo
C070701	Early	Anufor	<i>Namba</i>	Namba tribe in Togo
C070801	Early	Anufor	<i>Namba</i>	Male Namba
C070901	Early	Anufor	<i>Namba bieso</i>	Female Namba
C071001	Early	Anufor	<i>Namba bieso</i>	Male Namba
C071101	Early	Anufor	<i>Namba bieso</i>	Male Namba
C071201	Early	Anufor	<i>Namba bieso</i>	Male Namba
C071301	Early	Anufor	<i>Namba bieso</i>	No idea
C071401	Early	Anufor	<i>Namba bala</i>	Female Namba
C071501	Early	Anufor	<i>Namba</i>	No idea
C071601	Early	Anufor	<i>Namba</i>	No idea
C080101	Early	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	Named after Togo president Yadema
C080201	Late	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	True Fonio
C080301	Late	Anufor	<i>Nvonikpa</i>	True Fonio
C080401	Late	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	Named after Togo president Yadema
C080601	Early	Anufor	<i>Kpentike</i>	No idea
C080701	Early	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	No idea
C080801	Early	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	No idea

Note: 2 – 3 months = Early maturing fonio landraces; 3.5 – 5 months = Late maturing fonio landraces

Appendix 11 Maturity, landrace name and meaning 176 fonio landraces.

Accession	Maturity	Ethnicity of farmer	Name of landrace	Meaning of landrace name
C080901	Late	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	No idea
C081001	Late	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	No idea
C081101	Late	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	Togo
C081201	Late	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	The best among all
C081301	Late	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	Named after Togo president Yadema
C081401	Late	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	No idea
C090101	Early	Anufor	<i>Namba</i>	Number one in terms of maturity
C090201	Early	Anufor	<i>Namba</i>	No idea
C090301	Early	Anufor	<i>Namba</i>	No idea
C090401	Early	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	No idea
C090501	Early	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	Named after Togo president Yadema
C090601	Early	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	No idea
C090701	Early	Anufor	<i>Namba</i>	No idea
C090801	Early	Anufor	<i>Namba</i>	No idea
C090901	Early	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	Named after Togo president Yadema
C100101	Late	Anufor	<i>Nvonikpa</i>	True fonio
C100201	Late	Anufor	<i>Nvonikpa</i>	No idea
G010101	Early	Dagomba	<i>Kabga</i>	No idea
G010201	Early	Dagomba	<i>Kabga</i>	Fonio
G020101	Late	Dagomba	<i>Kabga</i>	Fonio
G020201	Late	Dagomba	<i>No idea</i>	No idea
S010101	Late	Konkomba	<i>Ipui piln</i>	White fonio
S010201	Early	Konkomba	<i>Ipui bolne</i>	Black fonio-black skin
S010301	Early	Konkomba	<i>Ipui bolne</i>	Black skin fonio
S010401	Late	Konkomba	<i>Ipui</i>	No idea
S010501	Late	Konkomba	<i>Ipui bolne</i>	Black fonio (skin color)
S010601	Early	Konkomba	<i>Yadema</i>	Togo name
S010701	Late	Konkomba	<i>Ipui</i>	No idea
S010801	Early	Konkomba	<i>Ipui</i>	No idea
S020101	Early	Konkomba	<i>Ipui maln</i>	Red fonio
S020201	Early	Konkomba	<i>Ipui maln</i>	Red fonio
S030101	Early	Anufor	<i>Nvonikpa</i>	Good fonio
S030201	Early	Anufor	<i>Namba</i>	Namba tribe in Togo
S040101	Early	Konkomba	<i>Ipui</i> <i>Ukabreja</i>	Variety from Togo
S040201	Early	Konkomba	<i>Ukabreja</i>	Kabre tribe in Togo

Note: 2 – 3 months = Early maturing fonio landraces; 3.5 – 5 months = Late maturing fonio landraces

Appendix 11 Maturity, landrace name and meaning 176 fonio landraces.

Accession	Maturity	Ethnicity of farmer	Name of landrace	Meaning of landrace name
S040301	Early	Konkomba	<i>Ukabreja</i>	Kabre tribe in Togo
S040401	Late	Konkomba	<i>Ipui piln</i>	White fonio
S040501	Late	Konkomba	<i>Ipui maln</i>	Red fonio
S050101	Early	Konkomba	<i>Yadema</i>	No idea
S050102	Late	Konkomba	<i>Ipui maln</i>	Red fonio
S050103	Early	Konkomba	<i>Ukabreja</i>	Kabre tribe in Togo
S050201	Late	Anufor	<i>Ukabreja</i>	Kabre tribe in Togo
S050301	Late	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	From Togo
S050401	Early	Anufor	<i>Yadema</i>	Named after Togo president Yadema
S060101	Early	Konkomba	<i>Ukabreja</i>	Kabre tribe in Togo
S060201	Early	Konkomba	<i>Ipui maln</i>	Red fonio
S070101	Late	Konkomba	<i>Ipui maln</i>	Red skin fonio
S070201	Late	Konkomba	<i>Ipui maln</i>	Red fonio
S070301	Early	Konkomba	<i>Ipui maln</i>	Red skin fonio
S080101	Late	Konkomba	<i>Ipui maln</i>	Red fonio
S080201	Early	Konkomba	<i>Ipui maln</i>	Red fonio
S080301	Early	Konkomba	<i>Ukabreja</i>	Kabre tribe in Togo
S080302	Late	Konkomba	<i>Ipui maln</i>	Red fonio
S080401	Late	Konkomba	<i>Ipui maln</i>	No idea
T010101	Early	Konkomba	<i>Ipui piln</i>	White fonio
T010201	Early	Konkomba	<i>Ipui</i>	No idea
T010301	Early	Konkomba	<i>Ipui piln</i>	White fonio
T010401	Early	Konkomba	<i>Ipui piln</i>	White fonio
T020101	Early	Konkomba	<i>Ipui maln</i>	Red skin fonio
Z010101	Early	Kabre	<i>Kafia</i>	Early maturing
Z010102	Early	Kabre	<i>Kafia</i>	Early maturing
Z010201	Early	Kabre	<i>Yoona</i>	Early maturing
Z010301	Early	Kabre	<i>Semiri</i>	Early maturing
Z010401	Early	Kabre	<i>Semiri</i>	Early maturing
Z010501	Early	Kabre	<i>Semiri</i>	Early maturing
Z010601	Early	Kabre	<i>Semiri</i>	Early maturing
Z010701	Early	Kabre	<i>Senbre</i>	Early crop
Z020101	Early	Kabre	<i>Afiang</i>	High yielding
Z020102	Early	Kabre	<i>Yahran</i>	Tiny grain
Z020201	Early	Kabre	<i>Afiang</i>	No idea
Z020301	Early	Kabre	<i>Afiang</i>	Name for fonio in Kabre language

Note: 2 – 3 months = Early maturing fonio landraces; 3.5 – 5 months = Late maturing fonio landraces

Appendix 12 Ethnicity, source of seeds and purpose of fonio cultivation

Ethnicity of farmers	Origin of landraces	Number of seed lots
Anufor	Cote d'Ivoire	3
Anufor	Togo	71
Anufor	No idea	53
Dagomba	Company	4
Kabre	Company	6
Kabre	Togo	1
Kabre	No idea	5
Konkomba	Company	3
Konkomba	Togo	2
Konkomba	No idea	28
	Total	176
Source of seeds	Number of farmers	Percent (%)
Seeds from the household	148	89.7
Seed from neighbour	5	3.0
Seeds from marketing companies	12	7.3
Total	165	
Purpose of cultivation	Number of farmers	Percent (%)
Food alone	98	59.5
Food and income	61	36.9
Income	6	3.6
Total	165	

Appendix 13 Groups of duplicate fonio accessions based on SSR markers

Number	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4	Group 5	Group 6	Group 7	Group 8	Group 9
1	S030201	C011401	C030101	C081101	C040201	C061001	C020701	C081301	C080801
2	C031201	C020401	Z020102	T010301	C050501	S080201	C020501	S010301	C010401
3	C021001	C081201				T010101	C090401	C060702	C010201
4	C020301	T010401						Z010102	
5	C090801								
6	C020101								
7	C020901								
8	C071101								
9	C021101								
10	C031601								

Appendix 14 Principal component analysis of ethnicity and maturity of fonio

Appendix 15 Inferred subpopulation of fonio accessions based on sNMF

Accessions	V1	V2	V3	V4	V5	V6	Group	Inferred sub population
C010101	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.9995	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	4	4
C010201	1.00E-04	0.022233	0.270016	0.707451	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	4	4
C010401	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.9995	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	4	4
C010501	0.017541	1.00E-04	0.238756	0.743403	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	4	4
C010601	0.031549	1.00E-04	0.604225	0.363925	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	3	0
C010701	0.004239	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.995361	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	4	4
C010801	0.056453	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.817598	0.125649	1.00E-04	4	4
C010901	0.096085	0.231629	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.671987	1.00E-04	5	0
C011001	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.731141	0.146129	0.12243	1.00E-04	3	3
C011201	1.00E-04	0.313749	0.685851	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	3	0
C011301	1.00E-04	0.036306	0.084147	0.144315	1.00E-04	0.735032	6	6
C011401	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.268751	0.730849	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	4	4
C011501	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.643202	0.198458	0.016931	0.141209	3	0
C020101	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.9995	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	3	3
C020201	1.00E-04	0.034376	1.00E-04	0.965224	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	4	4
C020301	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.9995	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	3	3
C020401	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.9995	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	4	4
C020501	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.131287	0.868313	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	4	4
C020601	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.536941	0.46266	1.00E-04	4	0
C020701	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.131287	0.868313	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	4	4

Note: V1, V2, V3, V4, V5 and V6 = ancestry coefficients of the six subpopulations; Group= Subpopulation with highest ancestry coefficient; Inferred sub population 0 = Admixture

Appendix 15 Inferred subpopulation of fonio accessions based on sNMF

Accessions	V1	V2	V3	V4	V5	V6	Group	Inferred sub population
C020901	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.9995	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	3	3
C021001	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.9995	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	3	3
C021101	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.645051	0.354549	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	3	0
C021301	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.021825	0.429818	0.180667	0.36749	4	0
C021401	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.155473	1.00E-04	0.496349	0.347879	5	0
C021501	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.099434	0.636948	0.149527	0.113891	4	0
C030101	0.281865	1.00E-04	0.223336	1.00E-04	0.271242	0.223357	1	0
C030201	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.264324	0.680903	0.010839	0.043734	4	0
C030301	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.302601	0.696999	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	4	0
C030401	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.992909	0.006691	1.00E-04	4	4
C030501	0.233133	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.579964	0.186603	1.00E-04	4	0
C030601	0.166055	1.00E-04	0.319063	0.514582	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	4	0
C030701	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.636409	0.345557	1.00E-04	0.017734	3	0
C030801	0.760324	1.00E-04	0.156744	0.082632	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	1	1
C030901	0.020241	1.00E-04	0.790845	1.00E-04	0.025111	0.163603	3	3
C031001	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.702205	0.245266	0.025314	0.027016	3	3
C031101	1.00E-04	0.212234	1.00E-04	0.766004	0.021462	1.00E-04	4	4
C031201	1.00E-04	0.018451	0.859042	0.122208	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	3	3
C031301	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.583262	0.204264	0.088463	0.123812	3	0
C031401	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.309071	0.635145	0.0116	0.043984	4	0

Note: V1, V2, V3, V4, V5 and V6 = ancestry coefficients of the six subpopulations; Group= Subpopulation with highest ancestry coefficient; Inferred sub population 0 = Admixture

Appendix 15 Inferred subpopulation of fonio accessions based on sNMF

Accessions	V1	V2	V3	V4	V5	V6	Group	Inferred sub population
C031501	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.321596	0.678004	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	4	0
C031601	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.9995	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	3	3
C031701	1.00E-04	0.34965	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.649951	6	0
C031702	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.070724	0.928876	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	4	4
C031703	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.094857	0.302154	0.223399	0.37939	6	0
C040101	1.00E-04	0.588779	0.375569	0.035352	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	2	0
C040201	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.131287	0.868313	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	4	4
C040301	0.316439	1.00E-04	0.240632	0.167564	0.275166	1.00E-04	1	0
C040401	0.017071	1.00E-04	0.982529	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	3	3
C040601	1.00E-04	0.204392	0.550863	0.244445	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	3	0
C040701	0.593377	1.00E-04	0.175341	1.00E-04	0.063801	0.167281	1	0
C040801	0.048203	1.00E-04	0.163581	0.213011	0.208765	0.366341	6	0
C040901	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.9995	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	3	3
C041001	1.00E-04	0.188099	1.00E-04	0.547096	0.264505	1.00E-04	4	0
C041101	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.845134	0.152923	1.00E-04	0.001643	3	3
C050101	0.076695	0.011598	0.160714	0.714814	0.036078	1.00E-04	4	4
C050301	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.415056	0.556429	0.000566	0.027749	4	0
C050401	0.472693	0.011457	1.00E-04	0.395739	1.00E-04	0.119911	1	0
C050501	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.131287	0.868313	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	4	4
C050601	0.032735	1.00E-04	0.744178	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.222787	3	3

Note: V1, V2, V3, V4, V5 and V6 = ancestry coefficients of the six subpopulations; Group= Subpopulation with highest ancestry coefficient; Inferred sub population 0 = Admixture

Appendix 15 Inferred subpopulation of fonio accessions based on sNMF

Accessions	V1	V2	V3	V4	V5	V6	Group	Inferred sub population
C050701	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.225007	0.59136	0.183333	1.00E-04	4	0
C060101	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.055948	0.212358	0.731395	1.00E-04	5	5
C060301	1.00E-04	0.310059	0.510144	0.167704	0.011893	1.00E-04	3	0
C060401	1.00E-04	0.014942	0.070499	1.00E-04	0.914259	1.00E-04	5	5
C060601	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.801225	0.140964	0.057512	1.00E-04	3	3
C060702	1.00E-04	0.07259	0.92701	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	3	3
C060801	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.836034	1.00E-04	0.163566	1.00E-04	3	3
C061001	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.9995	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	4	4
C061101	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.631833	0.332321	1.00E-04	0.035546	3	0
C061401	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.610614	0.264874	0.124211	1.00E-04	3	0
C070101	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.9995	1.00E-04	5	5
C070301	1.00E-04	0.231588	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.431078	0.337033	5	0
C070701	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.061322	0.265683	0.496246	0.176549	5	0
C070901	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.9995	1.00E-04	5	5
C071001	0.017268	0.089295	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.893137	1.00E-04	5	5
C071101	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.9995	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	3	3
C071401	0.636551	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.007985	1.00E-04	0.355165	1	0
C071501	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.990566	0.009034	5	5
C080201	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.362272	0.427357	0.155487	0.054685	4	0
C080301	0.847161	0.130316	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.022223	1.00E-04	1	1

Note: V1, V2, V3, V4, V5 and V6 = ancestry coefficients of the six subpopulations; Group= Subpopulation with highest ancestry coefficient; Inferred sub population 0 = Admixture

Appendix 15 Inferred subpopulation of fonio accessions based on sNMF

Accessions	V1	V2	V3	V4	V5	V6	Group	Inferred sub population
C080401	0.035795	0.028206	0.859339	1.00E-04	0.07646	1.00E-04	3	3
C080601	1.00E-04	0.079024	0.663998	0.256678	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	3	0
C080701	0.108857	1.00E-04	0.250075	1.00E-04	0.288416	0.352453	6	0
C080801	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.281715	0.717885	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	4	4
C080901	1.00E-04	0.092113	0.324415	0.583172	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	4	0
C081101	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.985743	0.013857	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	3	3
C081201	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.268751	0.730849	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	4	4
C081301	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.675627	0.323973	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	3	0
C081401	0.072213	0.31798	0.490777	0.118829	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	3	0
C090101	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.798264	0.201336	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	3	3
C090201	0.446941	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.239595	0.313165	1	0
C090301	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.325638	1.00E-04	0.156418	0.517644	6	0
C090401	0.002616	1.00E-04	0.264635	0.73245	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	4	4
C090501	1.00E-04	0.090381	0.651908	0.257411	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	3	0
C090601	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.947823	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.051778	3	3
C090801	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.9995	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	3	3
G010101	0.346012	1.00E-04	0.323368	1.00E-04	0.33032	1.00E-04	1	0
G010201	0.322332	1.00E-04	0.165426	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.511942	6	0
G020101	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.31387	0.114969	0.463119	0.107841	5	0
G020201	0.043627	1.00E-04	0.374391	0.581682	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	4	0

Note: V1, V2, V3, V4, V5 and V6 = ancestry coefficients of the six subpopulations; Group= Subpopulation with highest ancestry coefficient; Inferred sub population 0 = Admixture

Appendix 15 Inferred subpopulation of fonio accessions based on sNMF

Accessions	V1	V2	V3	V4	V5	V6	Group	Inferred sub population
S010101	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.085872	0.058327	0.855501	6	6
S010201	0.293205	0.097468	0.114269	0.28379	1.00E-04	0.211168	1	0
S010301	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.9995	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	3	3
S010401	1.00E-04	0.425875	1.00E-04	0.051514	0.153056	0.369356	2	0
S010501	1.00E-04	0.034541	0.923668	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.04149	3	3
S010701	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.092622	0.196745	1.00E-04	0.710333	6	6
S010801	0.043552	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.057736	0.284766	0.613747	6	0
S020101	0.101286	0.095368	0.13342	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.669726	6	0
S020201	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.640387	0.09753	0.177055	0.084829	3	0
S030101	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.073611	0.274799	1.00E-04	0.65129	6	0
S030201	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.9995	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	3	3
S040101	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.35345	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.64615	6	0
S040201	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.9995	6	6
S040301	0.024786	1.00E-04	0.008911	0.013307	0.237681	0.715215	6	6
S050101	0.110277	0.020768	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.868655	6	6
S050102	0.362665	1.00E-04	0.066323	0.02392	0.176514	0.370478	6	0
S050103	0.034924	0.114124	0.113489	0.605088	1.00E-04	0.132275	4	0
S050201	1.00E-04	0.9995	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	2	2
S050401	1.00E-04	0.759219	0.214231	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.02625	2	2
S060101	0.894836	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.104764	1	1

Note: V1, V2, V3, V4, V5 and V6 = ancestry coefficients of the six subpopulations; Group= Subpopulation with highest ancestry coefficient; Inferred sub population 0 = Admixture

Appendix 15 Inferred subpopulation of fonio accessions based on sNMF

Accession	V1	V2	V3	V4	V5	V6	Group	Inferred sub population
S070201	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.9995	6	6
S070301	1.00E-04	0.074036	1.00E-04	0.168169	0.027372	0.730222	6	6
S080101	0.232612	0.41789	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.349198	2	0
S080201	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.950579	0.031294	0.017827	4	4
S080301	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.613685	0.250343	0.135673	1.00E-04	3	0
S080302	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.008477	0.054078	0.130327	0.806917	6	6
S080401	0.143024	0.007802	1.00E-04	0.309573	0.091385	0.448117	6	0
T010101	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.9995	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	4	4
T010201	1.00E-04	0.312664	1.00E-04	0.123591	0.563445	1.00E-04	5	0
T010301	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.828938	0.170662	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	3	3
T010401	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.229966	0.769635	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	4	4
Z010102	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.9995	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	3	3
Z010401	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.281995	0.717605	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	4	4
Z010501	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.015373	0.984228	6	6
Z010601	1.00E-04	0.237842	0.325493	0.430229	0.006236	1.00E-04	4	0
Z010701	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.722545	0.277055	5	5
Z020101	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.9995	6	6
Z020102	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.9995	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	3	3
Z020201	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.445046	0.145591	0.409062	4	0
Z020301	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	1.00E-04	0.610606	0.388994	5	0

Note: V1, V2, V3, V4, V5 and V6 = ancestry coefficients of the six subpopulations; Group= Subpopulation with highest ancestry coefficient; Inferred sub population 0 = Admixture

Appendix 16 Estimation of Fixation index (F_{ST}) between ethnic groups

	Anufor	Dagomba	Kabre	Konkomba
Anufor	-			
Dagomba	0.088**	-		
Kabre	0.028NS	0.052*	-	
Konkomba	0.079***	0.053*	0.000	-

*, ** and *** = significant at $p < 0.05$, $p < 0.01$ and $p < 0.001$ respectively

Appendix 17 Principal component analysis of West African fonio (axes 1 and 3)

Appendix 18 Fonio accessions used for agro-morphological study.

Entry no	Accession	Community	District	Genetic data
1	C040301	Tosala-Kombonli	Chereponi	Yes
2	C010401	Sangbana	Chereponi	Yes
3	C021101	Banjani	Chereponi	Yes
4	C040201	Tosala-Kombonli	Chereponi	Yes
5	Z020201	Kpalgagbini	Zabzugu	Yes
6	C030801	Ando Nyamanu	Chereponi	Yes
7	S050201	Gbangbanpong	Saboba	Yes
8	C070301	Wonjuga	Chereponi	Yes
9	Z010501	Mangoase	Zabzugu	Yes
10	C080901	Ando Nderenu	Chereponi	Yes
11	C050601	Bulasu	Chereponi	Yes
12	S010101	Liwalbu	Saboba	Yes
13	C020801	Banjani	Chereponi	No
14	C030101	Ando Nyamanu	Chereponi	Yes
15	S030101	Yawbuesu	Saboba	Yes
16	C020401	Banjani	Chereponi	Yes
17	C080101	Ando Nderenu	Chereponi	No
18	C031702	Ando Nyamanu	Chereponi	Yes
19	G020201	Villi	Gushegu	Yes
20	C010201	Sangbana	Chereponi	Yes
21	C071401	Wonjuga	Chereponi	Yes
22	C060401	Kudani	Chereponi	Yes
23	C071201	Wonjuga	Chereponi	No
24	C050701	Bulasu	Chereponi	Yes
25	C081401	Ando Nderenu	Chereponi	Yes
26	C070402	Wonjuga	Chereponi	No
27	S010201	Liwalbu	Saboba	Yes
28	C090301	Naturi	Chereponi	Yes
29	C031001	Ando Nyamanu	Chereponi	Yes
30	C081301	Ando Nderenu	Chereponi	Yes
31	C020501	Banjani	Chereponi	Yes
32	C031301	Ando Nyamanu	Chereponi	Yes
33	C080301	Ando Nderenu	Chereponi	Yes
34	C011301	Sangbana	Chereponi	Yes
35	C031201	Ando Nyamanu	Chereponi	Yes
36	G020101	Villi	Gushegu	Yes
37	C030901	Ando Nyamanu	Chereponi	Yes
38	S050301	Gbangbanpong	Saboba	Yes
39	C031401	Ando Nyamanu	Chereponi	Yes
40	C011201	Sangbana	Chereponi	Yes

Appendix 18 Fonio accessions used for agro-morphological study.

Entry no	Accession	Community	District	Genetic data
41	C080201	Ando Nderenu	Chereponi	Yes
42	S020201	Timbu	Saboba	Yes
43	C070901	Wonjuga	Chereponi	Yes
44	C070201	Wonjuga	Chereponi	No
45	C021501	Banjani	Chereponi	Yes
46	C071101	Wonjuga	Chereponi	Yes
47	Z010102	Mangoase	Zabzugu	Yes
48	C031501	Ando Nyamanu	Chereponi	Yes
49	C070101	Wonjuga	Chereponi	Yes
50	C100201	Chombosu Angor	Chereponi	No
51	C040101	Tosala-Kombonli	Chereponi	Yes
52	C010701	Sangbana	Chereponi	Yes
53	C031101	Ando Nyamanu	Chereponi	Yes
54	C060701	Kudani	Chereponi	Yes
55	C100101	Chombosu Angor	Chereponi	Yes
56	T010401	Kpalbutabu	Tatale	Yes
57	S050101	Gbangbanpong	Saboba	Yes
58	C090701	Naturi	Chereponi	No
59	C031703	Ando Nyamanu	Chereponi	Yes
60	Z020102	Kpalgagbini	Zabzugu	Yes
61	C061301	Kudani	Chereponi	No
62	S010801	Liwalbu	Saboba	Yes
63	C010601	Sangbana	Chereponi	Yes
64	C071501	Wonjuga	Chereponi	Yes
65	C071001	Wonjuga	Chereponi	Yes
66	C020601	Banjani	Chereponi	Yes
67	C060601	Kudani	Chereponi	Yes
68	SARI 1	CSIR-SARI	Tolon	Yes
69	T010101	Kpalbutabu	Tatale	Yes
70	C030601	Ando Nyamanu	Chereponi	Yes
71	C010501	Sangbana	Chereponi	Yes
72	C070801	Wonjuga	Chereponi	No
73	C011001	Sangbana	Chereponi	Yes
74	S080201	Toma	Saboba	Yes
75	C060801	Kudani	Chereponi	Yes
76	S040401	Nakpel Konkomba	Saboba	Yes
77	C011501	Sangbana	Chereponi	Yes
78	T010301	Kpalbutabu	Tatale	Yes
79	S080101	Toma	Saboba	Yes
80	C040801	Tosala-Kombonli	Chereponi	Yes

Appendix 18 Fonio accessions used for agro-morphological study.

Entry no	Accession	Community	District	Genetic data
81	C040401	Tosala-Kombonli	Chereponi	Yes
82	Z010201	Mangoase	Zabzugu	Yes
83	S050102	Gbangbanpong	Saboba	Yes
84	S060101	Sanguli	Saboba	Yes
85	C040501	Tosala-Kombonli	Chereponi	No
86	C070401	Wonjuga	Chereponi	No
87	C081101	Ando Nderenu	Chereponi	Yes
88	C040601	Tosala-Kombonli	Chereponi	Yes
89	C010801	Sangbana	Chereponi	Yes
90	C061101	Kudani	Chereponi	Yes
91	S060201	Sanguli	Saboba	Yes
92	C090601	Naturi	Chereponi	Yes
93	C050101	Bulasu	Chereponi	Yes
94	C080401	Ando Nderenu	Chereponi	Yes
95	C090201	Naturi	Chereponi	Yes
96	C021201	Banjani	Chereponi	Yes
97	S080401	Toma	Saboba	Yes
98	C030701	Ando Nyamanu	Chereponi	Yes
99	C020101	Banjani	Chereponi	Yes
100	C021401	Banjani	Chereponi	Yes
101	C060301	Kudani	Chereponi	Yes
102	C031701	Ando Nyamanu	Chereponi	Yes
103	C070701	Wonjuga	Chereponi	Yes
104	<i>Nfonikpa</i>	KDC	Tamale	Yes
105	Z010101	Mangoase	Zabzugu	No
106	C050201	Bulasu	Chereponi	No
107	C050301	Bulasu	Chereponi	Yes
108	S040201	Nakpel Konkomba	Saboba	Yes
110	Z010701	Mangoase	Zabzugu	Yes
111	C061501	Kudani	Chereponi	No
112	Z010401	Mangoase	Zabzugu	Yes
113	S040101	Nakpel Konkomba	Saboba	Yes
114	C011401	Sangbana	Chereponi	Yes
115	Z010601	Mangoase	Zabzugu	Yes
116	C080801	Ando Nderenu	Chereponi	Yes
118	S010701	Liwalbu	Saboba	Yes
119	S020101	Timbu	Saboba	Yes
120	Z020101	Kpalgagbini	Zabzugu	Yes
121	C030401	Ando Nyamanu	Chereponi	Yes
122	G010201	Nayugu	Gushegu	Yes

Appendix 18 Fonio accessions used for agro-morphological study.

Entry no	Accession	Community	District	Genetic data
123	Z010301	Mangoase	Zabzugu	Yes
124	C040701	Tosala-Kombonli	Chereponi	Yes
125	C071601	Wonjuga	Chereponi	No
126	C090901	Naturi	Chereponi	No
127	C041001	Tosala-Kombonli	Chereponi	Yes
128	<i>Wagadoga</i>	KDC	Tamale	Yes
129	T010201	Kpalbutabu	Tatale	Yes
130	C050401	Bulasu	Chereponi	Yes
131	S080302	Toma	Saboba	Yes
132	C030501	Ando Nyamanu	Chereponi	Yes
133	C030301	Ando Nyamanu	Chereponi	Yes
134	C061201	Kudani	Chereponi	No
135	C061001	Kudani	Chereponi	Yes
136	C090101	Naturi	Chereponi	Yes
137	C070601	Wonjuga	Chereponi	No
138	C061401	Kudani	Chereponi	Yes
139	C081001	Ando Nderenu	Chereponi	Yes
140	C020201	Banjani	Chereponi	Yes
141	S050103	Gbangbanpong	Saboba	Yes
142	C010101	Sangbana	Chereponi	Yes
143	C080701	Ando Nderenu	Chereponi	Yes
144	S080301	Toma	Saboba	Yes
145	C030201	Ando Nyamanu	Chereponi	Yes
146	C011101	Sangbana	Chereponi	No
147	C050501	Bulasu	Chereponi	Yes
148	C081201	Ando Nderenu	Chereponi	Yes
149	C090801	Naturi	Chereponi	Yes
150	S040301	Nakpel Konkomba	Saboba	Yes
151	C040901	Tosala-Kombonli	Chereponi	Yes
152	G010101	Nayugu	Gushegu	Yes
153	C010901	Sangbana	Chereponi	Yes

Appendix 19 Study site for morphological characterization of fonio accessions

(A) Map of Africa showing the location of Ghana, (B) Map of Ghana highlighting the districts (Chereponi, Gushegu, Saboba, Tatale and Zabzugu districts) of fonio germplasm collection and the location of the experiment at Nyankpala in the Tolon district of the Northern Region and (C) picture of the experimental field

Appendix 20 Qualitative traits observed on 151 fonio accessions.

Traits/variables	Code	Description	Remarks
Basal leaf sheath color	BLSC	1. Green 2. Green with purple lines 3. Purple	Scored at late vegetative stage
Leaf sheath anthocyanin coloration	LSAC	0. Absent 3. Weak 5. Medium 7. Strong	Scored at late vegetative stage
Leaf blade anthocyanin coloration	LBAC	0. Absent 1. Present	Scored at late vegetative stage
Leaf blade anthocyanin distribution	LBAD	0. Absent 1. On tips only 2. On margins only 3. In blotches 4. Even (uniform purple)	Scored at late vegetative stage
Leaf blade color intensity	LBCI	3. Light green 5. Green 7. Dark green	Scored at late vegetative stage
Leaf blade attitude	LBA	1. Erect 5. Horizontal 7. Drooping	Scored at late vegetative stage prior to heading
Leaf blade pubescence	LBP	1. Glabrous 2. Intermediate 3. Pubescent	Scored at late vegetative stage
Flag leaf attitude	FLA	1. Erect 3. Semi-erect 5. Horizontal 7. Descending	Scored at anthesis
Culm anthocyanin coloration on nodes	CACN	0. Absent 1. Purple 2. Light purple 3. Purple lines	Scored at after flowering to near maturity

Appendix 20 Cont'd. Qualitative traits observed on 151 fonio accessions.

Traits/variables	Code	Description	Remarks
Culm internode anthocyanin	CIA	0. Absent 1. Purple 2. Purple lines	Scored at after flowering to near maturity
Culm internode anthocyanin intensity	CIAI	0. Absent 1. Weak 2. Strong	Scored at after flowering to near maturity
Plant growth habit	PGH	1. Erect 2. Spreading	Scored at late vegetative stage
Anther color	AC	1. Purple 2. Yellow 3. Brown	Scored at anthesis
Raceme attitude on branches	RAB	1. Erect 3. Semi-erect 5. Spreading 7. Horizontal 9. Drooping	Scored at near maturity
Raceme secondary branching	RSB	0. Absent 1. Sparse 2. Dense 3. Clustered	Scored at near maturity
Panicle exertion	PE	1. Enclosed 7. Moderately exerted 9. Well exerted	Scored at near maturity
Seed color	SC	1. Brown 2. Dark brown	Scored at after harvesting

Appendix 21 Mean squared values for 15 quantitative traits in fonio

Traits	Mean Squared values		
	Replication (df=2)	Genotype (df=150)	Residual (df= 300)
Plant height (cm)	484.00	89.26***	21.29
SPAD Chlorophyll Meter Reading	216.40	60.60 ns	57.15
Flag leaf length (cm)	1.53	2.20***	0.99
Number of days to 50% flowering	0.75	172.57***	5.92
Flag leaf width (cm)	0.02	0.01 ns	0.01
Grain weight per plant (g)	325.75	24.74***	11.68
Leaf area index	14.63	0.56 ns	0.49
Leaf blade length (cm)	29.28	5.91***	3.15
Leaf blade width (cm)	0.01	0.01ns	0.004
Number of days to 50% maturity	627.30	176.81***	16.35
Number of leaves per plant	90926.00	1039.19***	382.00
Number of racemes per panicle	0.18	0.28***	0.14
Number of seeds per raceme	146.00	1712.93***	950.92
Raceme length (cm)	6.28	3.03***	0.71
1000 seed weight (g)	0.01	0.01***	0.002

df= degrees of freedom; *, ** and *** = significant at 0.05, 0.01 and 0.001

Appendix 22 Performance of fonio accessions for growth and yield traits

Accession	PH (cm)	SCMR	FLL (cm)	DFE	FLW (cm)
S030101	67.77	45.70	9.76	81.67	0.40
S080101	86.43	40.93	9.59	87.33	0.54
C021201	73.37	45.37	9.04	73.33	0.36
S040401	70.97	39.70	8.97	84.33	0.42
C070301	80.53	36.07	8.89	91.33	0.41
Z020101	81.07	41.03	8.88	100.67	0.37
S010801	61.70	41.55	8.83	85.00	0.42
C100101	72.23	39.80	8.81	72.67	0.41
S040101	63.00	33.47	8.72	75.33	0.40
S010201	68.43	35.53	8.60	81.67	0.40
S020201	70.00	41.87	8.56	78.67	0.40
S010101	66.67	39.27	8.56	76.33	0.40
C041001	71.37	34.03	8.49	73.67	0.39
S050103	74.43	37.00	8.38	73.67	0.40
C030901	75.77	36.00	8.32	74.33	0.39
C010501	71.23	44.37	8.31	74.00	0.39
Z010701	93.10	39.50	8.28	102.67	0.39
C080701	68.90	46.03	8.27	72.67	0.38
S020101	69.67	52.47	8.21	84.67	0.39
C100201	68.67	49.20	8.18	74.33	0.40
C031001	74.00	43.00	8.08	72.00	0.36
C040101	70.87	41.30	8.08	72.67	0.39
C031401	70.43	47.83	8.02	74.00	0.36
S050102	74.10	43.47	8.00	87.33	0.38
S010701	68.37	38.90	7.94	77.00	0.43
T010401	63.53	48.90	7.88	75.00	0.38
S050301	63.30	35.40	7.87	78.00	0.36
C040401	68.03	39.23	7.83	74.00	0.39
C010801	71.67	37.40	7.82	74.00	0.38
C070601	73.00	46.33	7.81	74.00	0.38
Z010401	65.47	32.83	7.79	77.33	0.39
C031701	70.77	42.10	7.77	83.67	0.44
<i>Nfonikpa</i>	74.23	42.00	7.77	82.33	0.38
C070402	77.33	40.73	7.76	87.33	0.40
C081201	64.17	41.50	7.73	73.00	0.38
C030401	65.53	39.80	7.72	74.33	0.40
C090701	60.03	42.03	7.70	62.00	0.32
S080401	79.23	44.70	7.69	91.33	0.40
C061101	68.57	42.30	7.68	75.33	0.38
C011501	74.43	40.00	7.68	73.00	0.36
SE	0.44	0.36	0.07	0.62	0.00
CV (%)	6.93	18.30	13.88	3.36	19.84

PH= Plant height; SCMR=SPAD chlorophyll meter reading; FLL= Flag leaf length; DFE= Number of days to 50% flowering; FLW= Flag leaf width; SE= Standard error of mean; CV= Coefficient of variation

Appendix 22 Performance of fonio accessions for growth and yield traits

Accession	PH (cm)	SCMR	FLL (cm)	DFF	FLW (cm)
Z020102	71.67	45.63	7.66	73.33	0.38
S050101	72.23	35.30	7.63	84.00	0.33
C031501	68.57	40.43	7.61	73.67	0.40
C020101	74.87	45.87	7.59	73.67	0.36
C021501	70.43	33.73	7.59	70.33	0.41
S050201	63.33	39.47	7.58	74.33	0.40
C020501	64.33	39.57	7.54	73.67	0.38
C010101	66.10	39.93	7.52	65.33	0.40
C071101	70.33	42.03	7.50	72.67	0.38
C011401	65.87	40.93	7.48	74.00	0.40
C061001	66.87	46.63	7.46	73.67	0.39
C011301	70.57	39.67	7.46	73.67	0.39
C010401	72.20	39.90	7.38	72.67	0.41
C031101	69.63	46.00	7.36	73.67	0.40
C090101	71.70	40.73	7.36	74.00	0.33
C011001	77.77	38.10	7.36	73.00	0.39
Z010101	66.90	37.87	7.34	73.33	0.37
C040801	63.43	39.80	7.33	62.33	0.37
C071201	63.67	42.77	7.32	62.00	0.38
C010701	67.00	43.33	7.32	70.00	0.36
C030101	66.67	43.93	7.31	73.00	0.40
C081301	71.37	42.97	7.30	73.00	0.34
C020601	71.80	42.43	7.28	68.67	0.38
C050601	73.77	42.57	7.27	73.00	0.37
S080201	73.33	39.43	7.26	87.67	0.37
C021101	70.00	46.97	7.26	73.00	0.36
C031201	71.53	46.13	7.22	68.67	0.37
C060601	72.80	47.50	7.20	74.33	0.36
C060801	68.83	47.55	7.20	67.00	0.38
S040201	63.53	37.87	7.20	76.67	0.39
C011101	68.30	39.30	7.13	73.67	0.36
C040201	70.57	47.90	7.13	73.00	0.40
C081001	75.67	41.77	7.12	72.67	0.36
T010301	75.43	31.37	7.09	73.67	0.40
Z010201	71.00	45.10	7.09	74.00	0.34
Z010601	68.43	34.93	7.08	73.00	0.37
C050501	70.03	42.20	7.07	73.33	0.36
C050701	73.67	37.07	7.04	72.33	0.41
C020801	75.00	35.57	7.00	74.33	0.39
T010201	61.10	43.13	7.00	64.00	0.39
SE	0.44	0.36	0.07	0.62	0.00
CV (%)	6.93	18.30	13.88	3.36	19.84

PH= Plant height; SCMR=SPAD chlorophyll meter reading; FLL= Flag leaf length; DFF= Number of days to 50% flowering; FLW= Flag leaf width; SE= Standard error of mean; CV= Coefficient of variation

Appendix 22 Performance of fonio accessions for growth and yield traits

Accession	PH (cm)	SCMR	FLL (cm)	DFE	FLW (cm)
C020401	72.00	45.03	6.96	73.33	0.39
C031702	74.47	38.87	6.96	73.67	0.41
C080401	71.00	34.97	6.96	73.33	0.37
C040601	71.33	42.63	6.96	73.67	0.39
S080302	78.00	41.00	6.96	93.33	0.39
C050101	71.67	41.33	6.94	74.00	0.37
C040301	69.47	44.13	6.91	65.67	0.37
G020201	62.77	34.40	6.89	60.67	0.30
C030301	69.70	41.23	6.87	76.00	0.38
C020201	74.23	40.07	6.86	73.00	0.36
C090301	69.90	46.40	6.86	63.67	0.40
Z010102	73.23	47.00	6.86	73.67	0.42
C030501	63.30	48.03	6.86	63.33	0.42
S040301	73.90	46.30	6.83	69.33	0.42
C010201	68.87	46.53	6.83	72.67	0.36
C010601	71.67	40.50	6.83	73.00	0.39
C021401	61.67	52.80	6.83	68.67	0.37
C080901	70.57	43.90	6.83	72.67	0.36
C070101	58.37	43.23	6.82	63.00	0.38
C050401	64.90	38.63	6.81	65.33	0.34
S080301	62.20	45.87	6.80	62.67	0.37
C061501	69.63	39.43	6.77	73.33	0.41
C081101	66.57	44.47	6.77	71.33	0.39
C070201	62.03	45.40	6.76	65.67	0.40
C080101	73.33	40.33	6.76	72.33	0.34
C030601	74.13	33.87	6.73	72.67	0.36
C090601	72.67	46.63	6.73	72.33	0.36
SARI 1	66.03	36.00	6.71	72.67	0.38
S060201	67.10	37.63	6.70	62.33	0.38
C060301	73.00	40.93	6.69	73.33	0.40
C080301	61.13	41.80	6.66	62.67	0.39
Z010501	71.67	41.27	6.64	73.00	0.39
G020101	64.63	40.07	6.63	63.33	0.38
C030201	73.33	41.57	6.62	73.67	0.33
C071601	71.00	36.60	6.60	74.33	0.37
C040501	72.67	45.53	6.59	72.67	0.36
C071501	64.43	50.27	6.59	61.33	0.36
C081401	66.80	36.70	6.58	73.00	0.37
C050201	70.77	42.40	6.53	73.33	0.42
C040701	68.13	45.20	6.52	63.00	0.39
SE	0.44	0.36	0.07	0.62	0.00
CV (%)	6.93	18.30	13.88	3.36	19.84

PH= Plant height; SCMR=SPAD chlorophyll meter reading; FLL= Flag leaf length; DFE= Number of days to 50% flowering; FLW= Flag leaf width; SE= Standard error of mean; CV= Coefficient of variation

Appendix 22 Performance of fonio accessions for growth and yield traits

Accession	PH (cm)	SCMR	FLL (cm)	DFF	FLW (cm)
C090201	62.70	35.07	6.52	62.67	0.34
C050301	69.10	47.13	6.51	73.67	0.39
G010201	66.00	40.80	6.49	63.33	0.37
Z020201	67.77	50.07	6.47	73.33	0.38
C060401	60.57	40.80	6.46	63.00	0.41
C090801	73.33	35.47	6.42	73.00	0.36
C060701	62.20	37.77	6.39	61.67	0.34
C030801	62.77	41.80	6.38	66.33	0.32
C031703	58.33	38.40	6.36	64.67	0.34
C070801	64.23	39.07	6.32	66.67	0.43
C070701	68.67	32.15	6.32	61.67	0.35
C010901	61.33	35.37	6.31	62.67	0.32
C061301	63.10	41.20	6.29	64.67	0.28
C011201	74.20	49.93	6.24	73.00	0.38
C080801	63.10	42.73	6.24	62.00	0.33
G010101	65.77	43.67	6.21	62.00	0.34
S060101	63.37	46.27	6.20	61.67	0.32
C071401	60.57	50.27	6.19	61.00	0.36
Z010301	71.33	42.53	6.18	74.33	0.36
C030701	67.77	39.37	6.17	72.33	0.38
T010101	64.20	41.50	6.16	63.67	0.37
C040901	72.00	29.07	6.13	73.00	0.37
C090901	66.70	39.55	6.02	65.00	0.33
C031301	70.43	35.87	5.91	72.33	0.34
C071001	59.43	49.27	5.89	62.00	0.32
C070401	64.23	39.80	5.74	72.00	0.37
C080201	75.67	39.80	5.72	72.67	0.33
C061401	61.53	42.43	5.51	62.67	0.32
C070901	59.77	38.40	5.31	62.00	0.32
<i>Wagadoga</i>	63.10	49.87	4.98	59.33	0.34
C061201	59.97	41.57	4.96	62.33	0.28
SE	0.44	0.36	0.07	0.62	0.00
CV (%)	6.93	18.30	13.88	3.36	19.84

PH= Plant height; SCMR=SPAD chlorophyll meter reading; FLL= Flag leaf length; DFF= Number of days to 50% flowering; FLW= Flag leaf width; SE= Standard error of mean; CV= Coefficient of variation

Appendix 22 Performance of fonio accessions for growth and yield traits

Accession	LAI	LBL (cm)	LBW (cm)	DFM	NLP
S030101	1.98	10.30	0.43	119.67	115.67
S080101	2.62	14.09	0.49	122.67	109.33
C021201	1.66	7.77	0.39	110.00	116.00
S040401	2.12	10.92	0.41	120.00	111.56
C070301	2.70	9.88	0.43	127.00	127.89
Z020101	1.23	12.13	0.49	135.00	138.06
S010801	1.73	9.33	0.47	119.67	64.83
C100101	1.82	10.09	0.41	108.67	75.89
S040101	1.72	10.51	0.41	113.67	88.33
S010201	1.89	10.71	0.40	115.67	116.00
S020201	2.32	8.86	0.43	118.00	94.44
S010101	2.10	7.68	0.43	118.00	100.33
C041001	2.32	7.82	0.36	108.33	100.56
S050103	2.13	9.10	0.38	108.67	100.56
C030901	1.52	6.84	0.36	109.33	85.89
C010501	1.06	11.21	0.47	109.00	75.89
Z010701	2.26	10.31	0.47	135.00	137.22
C080701	1.41	6.80	0.39	108.33	91.22
S020101	1.98	9.91	0.42	120.67	106.78
C100201	1.48	10.90	0.41	111.67	89.00
C031001	2.50	8.16	0.46	107.67	103.22
C040101	2.31	8.23	0.38	112.00	84.33
C031401	1.85	6.83	0.40	113.33	87.22
S050102	3.24	10.08	0.36	123.00	126.78
S010701	2.11	9.38	0.37	113.00	100.11
T010401	1.53	8.07	0.39	115.33	77.78
S050301	2.44	9.22	0.46	118.00	96.67
C040401	1.55	9.64	0.40	111.67	75.78
C010801	2.04	8.28	0.39	115.00	89.11
C070601	2.18	8.06	0.39	113.00	93.33
Z010401	1.54	8.91	0.39	115.00	83.89
C031701	2.45	9.36	0.46	122.33	114.22
<i>Nfonikpa</i>	2.73	8.79	0.36	119.33	119.00
C070402	1.89	9.62	0.48	124.33	113.67
C081201	1.64	11.25	0.40	108.00	49.83
C030401	1.57	6.98	0.34	116.33	68.56
C090701	1.51	7.80	0.42	96.67	71.89
S080401	1.58	9.48	0.50	127.33	128.56
C061101	1.85	9.19	0.38	114.33	85.67
C011501	1.93	8.40	0.39	112.67	99.44
SE	0.04	0.11	0.00	0.62	1.49
CV (%)	40.77	21.37	16.67	3.69	23.54

LAI= Leaf area index; LBL= Leaf blade length; LBW= Leaf blade width; DFM= Number of days to 50% maturity; NLP= Number of leaves per plant; SE= Standard error of mean; CV= Coefficient of variation

Appendix 22 Performance of fonio accessions for growth and yield traits

Accession	LAI	LBL (cm)	LBW (cm)	DFM	NLP
Z020102	2.05	9.00	0.41	109.67	87.89
S050101	2.97	9.57	0.46	120.67	117.89
C031501	1.70	8.90	0.43	110.33	84.22
C020101	1.93	7.91	0.41	112.67	86.89
C021501	1.76	8.50	0.40	111.67	76.00
S050201	1.58	9.54	0.40	104.00	93.22
C020501	1.40	6.90	0.39	112.33	65.00
C010101	1.58	8.94	0.39	106.67	81.00
C071101	2.25	8.64	0.37	110.33	93.00
C011401	1.87	7.80	0.39	112.00	89.89
C061001	1.43	8.47	0.38	108.00	72.11
C011301	1.74	7.67	0.39	111.67	87.56
C010401	1.98	8.66	0.40	106.67	103.22
C031101	1.83	7.64	0.38	110.67	78.22
C090101	1.59	7.67	0.40	112.33	85.33
C011001	2.32	8.27	0.37	108.67	111.00
Z010101	1.95	8.58	0.36	111.33	79.89
C040801	1.58	6.14	0.39	101.33	61.67
C071201	1.08	7.98	0.46	99.00	68.22
C010701	2.01	8.66	0.37	106.00	92.78
C030101	1.75	7.68	0.41	109.67	96.44
C081301	1.70	7.87	0.43	109.33	116.78
C020601	2.23	8.22	0.43	105.33	87.11
C050601	1.50	7.54	0.41	110.67	90.22
S080201	2.42	10.42	0.42	122.67	128.22
C021101	1.70	7.52	0.38	108.67	93.78
C031201	1.98	8.43	0.38	105.67	82.78
C060601	1.61	9.17	0.34	113.33	91.89
C060801	1.82	7.75	0.37	100.33	77.33
S040201	1.77	9.52	0.42	111.67	97.67
C011101	1.46	7.03	0.38	111.67	84.22
C040201	1.56	6.66	0.37	113.33	93.11
C081001	1.96	7.84	0.37	111.33	97.67
T010301	1.80	9.06	0.49	114.33	102.11
Z010201	2.36	8.44	0.34	112.00	94.33
Z010601	1.64	9.96	0.39	113.00	81.56
C050501	1.37	7.52	0.40	109.33	78.00
C050701	1.43	9.44	0.44	105.67	74.78
C020801	1.95	7.94	0.49	109.00	107.11
T010201	2.28	7.38	0.36	105.00	71.11
SE	0.04	0.11	0.00	0.62	1.49
CV (%)	40.77	21.37	16.67	3.69	23.54

LAI= Leaf area index; LBL= Leaf blade length; LBW= Leaf blade width; DFM= Number of days to 50% maturity; NLP= Number of leaves per plant; SE= Standard error of mean; CV= Coefficient of variation

Appendix 22 Performance of fonio accessions for growth and yield traits

Accession	LAI	LBL (cm)	LBW (cm)	DFM	NLP
C020401	1.65	7.29	0.33	111.00	73.89
C031702	1.60	7.70	0.38	111.00	103.67
C080401	1.49	8.21	0.41	109.00	73.78
C040601	1.86	8.22	0.39	115.00	82.00
S080302	2.13	10.43	0.37	130.67	135.00
C050101	1.56	7.82	0.39	110.33	80.44
C040301	1.49	7.42	0.34	101.67	105.56
G020201	1.57	6.52	0.37	96.33	86.11
C030301	2.19	7.88	0.40	112.33	94.78
C020201	1.19	8.29	0.38	110.00	98.33
C090301	1.57	8.08	0.37	100.67	82.22
Z010102	1.82	9.13	0.48	112.33	109.89
C030501	0.95	7.82	0.36	99.00	59.22
S040301	1.32	8.37	0.39	104.67	81.78
C010201	2.39	8.64	0.43	110.00	101.22
C010601	1.48	8.11	0.42	110.00	78.33
C021401	1.56	8.49	0.46	102.33	73.78
C080901	2.10	6.70	0.37	106.67	84.11
C070101	2.11	6.83	0.34	100.00	58.11
C050401	1.88	7.26	0.34	98.67	76.56
S080301	1.33	7.33	0.39	96.33	60.56
C061501	1.10	7.42	0.41	113.33	90.78
C081101	1.92	7.09	0.37	109.67	91.56
C070201	1.61	7.37	0.38	101.00	65.56
C080101	1.62	8.28	0.44	108.00	84.22
C030601	1.58	7.87	0.40	113.00	91.11
C090601	1.97	7.26	0.40	110.67	95.00
SARI 1	2.42	8.21	0.43	109.33	76.56
S060201	2.31	9.33	0.33	100.00	88.67
C060301	1.69	7.26	0.37	109.33	84.56
C080301	1.04	6.60	0.36	100.67	71.56
Z010501	1.76	7.77	0.43	108.00	75.00
G020101	1.43	7.97	0.37	101.33	61.44
C030201	2.37	9.16	0.44	117.67	104.33
C071601	1.25	8.19	0.40	114.33	78.89
C040501	2.20	7.32	0.37	110.33	96.67
C071501	2.29	6.18	0.36	98.33	68.00
C081401	0.79	7.00	0.38	106.67	90.22
C050201	1.26	9.23	0.39	109.33	69.56
C040701	2.17	7.16	0.37	102.00	87.11
SE	0.04	0.11	0.00	0.62	1.49
CV (%)	40.77	21.37	16.67	3.69	23.54

LAI= Leaf area index; LBL= Leaf blade length; LBW= Leaf blade width; DFM= Number of days to 50% maturity; NLP= Number of leaves per plant; SE= Standard error of mean; CV= Coefficient of variation

Appendix 22 Performance of fonio accessions for growth and yield traits

Accession	LAI	LBL (cm)	LBW (cm)	DFM	NLP
C090201	1.33	10.53	0.47	100.00	65.89
C050301	1.69	8.43	0.34	111.67	80.89
G010201	1.24	7.42	0.34	105.33	73.11
Z020201	1.01	7.83	0.34	108.67	74.56
C060401	1.06	7.06	0.33	99.33	68.44
C090801	1.67	7.49	0.39	108.00	96.56
C060701	1.87	6.24	0.36	107.33	56.78
C030801	1.53	8.84	0.39	102.00	62.78
C031703	1.31	7.78	0.42	103.00	47.89
C070801	1.64	7.12	0.37	101.33	64.78
C070701	2.07	11.47	0.37	96.67	68.33
C010901	1.59	6.10	0.40	98.00	66.44
C061301	1.44	6.08	0.30	101.67	57.89
C011201	2.28	8.10	0.44	111.00	99.11
C080801	1.97	6.01	0.33	100.00	69.78
G010101	1.68	6.20	0.34	97.33	68.33
S060101	1.95	12.01	0.40	98.67	78.78
C071401	1.72	6.74	0.36	96.00	61.33
Z010301	1.74	7.76	0.49	115.67	83.33
C030701	1.68	6.59	0.37	109.67	93.89
T010101	1.31	5.74	0.37	101.00	60.33
C040901	1.02	7.17	0.34	109.33	94.11
C090901	1.23	6.25	0.35	98.00	80.83
C031301	1.84	9.19	0.48	109.67	90.67
C071001	1.61	6.92	0.34	100.33	60.56
C070401	0.95	7.78	0.38	112.33	65.22
C080201	1.26	7.47	0.38	112.33	90.33
C061401	1.51	9.44	0.34	101.67	70.00
C070901	1.88	10.21	0.43	98.00	61.67
<i>Wagadoga</i>	2.67	6.23	0.32	95.67	86.44
C061201	0.84	5.86	0.36	98.67	64.22
SE	0.04	0.11	0.00	0.62	1.49
CV (%)	40.77	21.37	16.67	3.69	23.54

LAI= Leaf area index; LBL= Leaf blade length; LBW= Lead blade width; DFM= Number of days to 50% maturity; NLP= Number of leaves per plant; SE= Standard error of mean; CV= Coefficient of variation

Appendix 22 Performance of fonio accessions for growth and yield traits

Accession	NRP	NSR	RL (cm)	GWP (g)	TSW (g)
S030101	3.33	108.33	12.40	12.27	0.48
S080101	3.78	136.67	12.43	15.63	0.47
C021201	3.44	111.67	13.42	13.13	0.48
S040401	3.67	139.33	12.89	17.93	0.47
C070301	3.56	192.67	13.62	11.20	0.52
Z020101	3.78	134.33	13.46	7.37	0.45
S010801	3.83	159.33	13.80	13.57	0.46
C100101	3.56	117.67	13.10	11.30	0.54
S040101	3.22	115.00	12.71	15.87	0.49
S010201	3.67	166.33	13.49	13.63	0.47
S020201	3.78	113.33	13.23	11.23	0.45
S010101	3.67	114.67	12.54	17.37	0.51
C041001	3.67	119.33	12.54	9.77	0.49
S050103	3.33	124.00	12.93	10.70	0.53
C030901	3.22	142.33	12.91	8.50	0.49
C010501	3.56	111.00	12.26	9.67	0.50
Z010701	4.00	128.00	13.19	7.77	0.45
C080701	3.33	116.67	11.86	12.93	0.49
S020101	3.11	91.33	12.00	13.73	0.47
C100201	3.56	113.67	12.33	9.47	0.53
C031001	3.11	107.33	12.13	9.63	0.44
C040101	3.11	124.00	12.61	10.17	0.47
C031401	3.56	109.33	12.48	13.43	0.50
S050102	3.67	136.67	13.54	15.60	0.48
S010701	3.33	102.00	12.70	15.30	0.52
T010401	3.44	122.00	13.63	10.77	0.53
S050301	3.78	138.00	12.96	12.97	0.50
C040401	3.33	113.00	11.77	11.57	0.48
C010801	3.22	109.00	12.86	11.93	0.46
C070601	3.67	111.67	12.54	7.13	0.49
Z010401	3.33	118.00	12.68	13.63	0.50
C031701	3.22	175.33	12.69	11.00	0.44
<i>Nfonikpa</i>	3.78	134.00	11.88	14.73	0.48
C070402	3.89	274.33	13.50	7.63	0.47
C081201	3.50	119.00	12.07	7.40	0.55
C030401	3.33	113.00	12.88	14.90	0.47
C090701	2.78	97.33	10.53	8.30	0.52
S080401	3.44	141.33	11.99	17.43	0.48
C061101	4.00	161.00	12.39	14.90	0.44
C011501	3.33	139.33	12.03	13.27	0.48
SE	0.02	1.92	0.08	0.23	0.00
CV (%)	11.40	26.91	6.95	32.93	10.18

NRP= Number of racemes per panicle; NSR= Number of seeds per raceme; RL= Raceme length; GWP= Grain weight per plant; TSW= 1000 seed weight; SE= Standard error of mean; CV= Coefficient of variation

Appendix 22 Performance of fonio accessions for growth and yield traits

Accession	NRP	NSR	RL (cm)	GWP (g)	TSW (g)
Z020102	3.11	106.67	12.42	10.27	0.50
S050101	3.22	145.67	12.19	13.30	0.45
C031501	3.00	114.00	12.47	13.27	0.48
C020101	3.44	124.33	12.82	11.43	0.45
C021501	3.11	115.00	13.09	14.97	0.48
S050201	3.33	115.67	12.02	10.80	0.49
C020501	3.11	123.33	12.67	10.30	0.50
C010101	3.22	120.67	11.19	9.60	0.45
C071101	3.11	119.67	11.48	14.67	0.48
C011401	3.44	108.33	12.56	7.83	0.50
C061001	3.33	107.00	12.10	5.30	0.49
C011301	3.11	113.67	12.94	11.10	0.51
C010401	3.33	114.67	12.21	11.33	0.47
C031101	3.33	122.67	12.32	9.37	0.48
C090101	3.22	108.67	12.58	11.43	0.54
C011001	3.78	138.33	13.10	11.53	0.47
Z010101	3.00	110.33	12.91	13.07	0.53
C040801	3.11	76.00	10.77	8.10	0.46
C071201	3.11	102.00	10.44	5.60	0.52
C010701	3.33	141.67	12.50	8.60	0.48
C030101	3.89	111.00	11.67	10.17	0.50
C081301	3.56	126.33	12.48	10.33	0.54
C020601	3.33	109.67	12.09	8.87	0.49
C050601	3.44	120.00	12.29	10.13	0.48
S080201	3.67	157.67	12.16	13.80	0.47
C021101	3.00	102.67	12.48	10.07	0.50
C031201	3.11	110.00	12.83	11.50	0.52
C060601	3.67	117.33	12.94	14.23	0.50
C060801	3.00	96.00	12.83	14.43	0.48
S040201	3.78	133.00	11.74	13.93	0.46
C011101	3.33	97.00	12.39	12.07	0.50
C040201	3.67	109.00	13.68	10.83	0.50
C081001	3.11	97.00	12.99	10.97	0.51
T010301	3.33	128.33	12.82	8.87	0.50
Z010201	3.33	114.67	12.80	11.63	0.51
Z010601	3.22	110.33	12.62	15.97	0.50
C050501	3.11	133.33	12.59	12.27	0.46
C050701	3.11	114.00	12.48	5.90	0.51
C020801	3.22	125.67	12.72	13.27	0.46
T010201	3.22	102.33	10.36	9.43	0.51
SE	0.02	1.92	0.08	0.23	0.00
CV (%)	11.40	26.91	6.95	32.93	10.18

NRP= Number of racemes per panicle; NSR= Number of seeds per raceme; RL= Raceme length; GWP= Grain weight per plant; TSW= 1000 seed weight; SE= Standard error of mean; CV= Coefficient of variation

Appendix 22 Performance of fonio accessions for growth and yield traits

Accession	NRP	NSR	RL (cm)	GWP (g)	TSW (g)
C020401	2.89	126.00	12.14	7.70	0.45
C031702	3.44	147.00	12.20	6.27	0.49
C080401	3.22	90.00	13.21	7.90	0.47
C040601	3.44	115.00	13.26	7.80	0.45
S080302	3.78	115.00	12.54	7.93	0.47
C050101	3.22	127.67	12.62	12.87	0.49
C040301	3.00	115.33	10.99	9.27	0.49
G020201	2.67	101.33	11.11	7.50	0.52
C030301	4.11	149.00	12.90	10.10	0.46
C020201	3.56	108.67	12.11	13.53	0.40
C090301	3.33	115.67	11.91	7.70	0.54
Z010102	3.44	105.00	12.48	11.77	0.50
C030501	3.11	120.33	10.22	12.53	0.52
S040301	3.00	98.00	12.13	11.70	0.36
C010201	3.22	102.00	12.60	10.23	0.49
C010601	3.33	108.67	12.44	14.83	0.49
C021401	2.89	114.00	11.30	9.13	0.49
C080901	3.11	111.33	12.28	10.67	0.49
C070101	3.00	82.67	9.76	7.30	0.53
C050401	3.33	82.33	10.86	9.67	0.38
S080301	3.00	84.67	10.47	6.23	0.49
C061501	3.33	129.67	13.08	10.07	0.50
C081101	3.22	97.67	12.03	13.27	0.51
C070201	2.78	90.67	10.11	6.23	0.50
C080101	3.22	116.00	12.07	11.17	0.51
C030601	3.67	104.33	12.88	11.60	0.47
C090601	3.67	124.67	11.79	10.43	0.49
SARI 1	3.89	115.00	12.85	6.73	0.50
S060201	3.33	105.33	11.60	8.23	0.50
C060301	3.33	92.33	12.61	10.90	0.48
C080301	2.89	91.67	9.79	8.70	0.50
Z010501	3.22	104.33	12.00	12.03	0.50
G020101	3.22	103.33	11.42	6.83	0.51
C030201	3.44	122.67	12.73	8.43	0.48
C071601	3.44	110.67	12.61	9.50	0.51
C040501	3.44	131.67	12.63	11.27	0.45
C071501	3.33	109.00	10.29	7.97	0.53
C081401	3.56	94.33	12.91	8.17	0.56
C050201	3.33	127.67	11.73	10.63	0.47
C040701	3.11	85.00	10.94	8.50	0.50
SE	0.02	1.92	0.08	0.23	0.00
CV (%)	11.40	26.91	6.95	32.93	10.18

NRP= Number of racemes per panicle; NSR= Number of seeds per raceme; RL= Raceme length; GWP= Grain weight per plant; TSW= 1000 seed weight; SE= Standard error of mean; CV= Coefficient of variation

Appendix 22 Performance of fonio accessions for growth and yield traits

Accession	NRP	NSR	RL (cm)	GWP (g)	TSW (g)
C090201	3.00	118.00	10.08	6.07	0.53
C050301	3.22	131.33	11.50	7.80	0.44
G010201	3.22	111.33	10.68	7.07	0.51
Z020201	2.78	109.00	12.64	8.10	0.49
C060401	2.56	95.00	9.86	4.80	0.48
C090801	3.33	135.33	12.47	13.33	0.52
C060701	3.11	92.67	10.42	7.07	0.48
C030801	3.11	84.67	11.13	6.77	0.47
C031703	2.56	84.33	10.37	5.70	0.49
C070801	3.22	85.33	10.26	6.80	0.49
C070701	3.00	112.00	10.87	13.53	0.51
C010901	3.11	90.33	11.11	12.13	0.49
C061301	3.00	87.00	10.81	7.60	0.51
C011201	3.22	131.33	12.29	11.87	0.50
C080801	2.67	94.00	10.32	7.87	0.50
G010101	2.89	82.33	11.42	7.47	0.50
S060101	3.22	75.00	10.41	8.20	0.49
C071401	2.89	90.00	10.69	6.53	0.51
Z010301	3.67	132.33	12.60	12.43	0.46
C030701	3.22	110.67	12.96	10.57	0.55
T010101	3.00	90.33	10.71	5.53	0.51
C040901	3.22	101.33	13.06	10.67	0.45
C090901	3.50	116.67	11.82	9.77	0.50
C031301	3.11	128.00	12.57	8.13	0.51
C071001	3.00	100.67	10.04	5.73	0.50
C070401	3.11	105.33	14.79	10.80	0.52
C080201	3.89	111.67	13.54	9.23	0.48
C061401	2.89	96.33	10.72	8.23	0.46
C070901	2.89	83.00	10.46	5.80	0.53
<i>Wagadoga</i>	2.89	97.33	10.29	9.33	0.55
C061201	2.78	163.67	9.73	7.80	0.47
SE	0.02	1.92	0.08	0.23	0.00
CV (%)	11.40	26.91	6.95	32.93	10.18

NRP= Number of racemes per panicle; NSR= Number of seeds per raceme; RL= Raceme length; GWP= Grain weight per plant; TSW= 1000 seed weight; SE= Standard error of mean; CV= Coefficient of variation

Appendix 23 Mean performance and comparisons among morphological clusters

Traits	Cluster A	Cluster B	Cluster C	Cluster A vs Cluster B	Cluster A vs Cluster C	Cluster B vs Cluster C
DFF	63.00±1.62	73.00±2.17	85.00±7.08	***	***	***
DFM	100.00±2.65	110.00±3.34	122.00±6.01	***	***	***
PH	63.08±2.74	70.41±3.41	73.01±7.41	***	***	*
NLP	69.00±11.01	87.00±11.89	112.00±17.38	***	***	***
RL	10.60±0.51	12.50±0.54	12.75±0.61	***	***	ns
NSR	97.00±16.00	116.00±12.03	143.00±36.56	***	***	***
GWP	7.71±1.78	10.80±2.26	13.05±3.06	***	***	***
NRP	3.01±0.22	3.33±0.24	3.64±0.24	***	***	***

p>0.05: ns - non significant; 0.01<p<0.05: significant - *; 0.001<p<0.01: significant - ** and p<0.001: significant - ***; N= number of fonio accessions in a morphological cluster; DFF= number of days to 50% flowering; DFM= number of days to 50% maturity; RL= raceme length (cm); PH= plant height (cm); NSR= number of seeds per raceme; NLP= number of leaves per plant; NRP= number of raceme per plant; GWP= grain weight per plant (g); C.A vs C.B= Cluster A versus Cluster B; C.A vs C.C= Cluster A versus Cluster C; C.B vs C.C= Cluster B versus Cluster C

Appendix 24 Correlation between morphological clusters and qualitative traits.

PGH_1= erect plant growth habit; PGH_2= spreading plant growth habit; CIAI_1= weak culm internode anthocyanin intensity; CIAI_2= strong culm internode anthocyanin intensity; RAB_3= semi-erect racemes; RAB_5= spreading racemes; LBCI_5= green leaf blade; LBCI_7= dark green leaf blade; SC_1= brown seed color; SC_2= dark brown seed color; LSAC_0= no anthocyanin on leaf sheath; LSAC_3= weak anthocyanin on leaf sheath; LSAC_5= medium anthocyanin on leaf sheath; LBA_1= erect leaf blade; LBA_5= horizontal leaf blade; LBAC_0= no anthocyanin on leaf blade; LBAC_1= anthocyanin coloration on leaf blade; LBAD_0= no anthocyanin distribution; LBAD_1= anthocyanin distribution of leaf tips only; LBAD_2= anthocyanin distribution on leaf margins only

Appendix 25 Principal component analysis showing the variance of PC 1 and 2

Appendix 26 Biplot of the relationship and the discriminativeness of the traits.

FLL= Flag leaf length (cm); Flo 50= Days to 50% flowering; FLW= Flag leaf width (cm); GW.plt= Grain weight per plant (g); LAI= Leaf area index; LBL= Leaf blade length (cm); LBW= Leaf blade width (cm); Maturity 50= Days to 50% maturity; No.Leaves.plt= Number of leaves per plant; No.Raceme.plant= Number of racemes per panicle; No.seed.raceme= Number of seeds per raceme; PH= Plant height (cm); RL= Raceme length (cm); SCMR= SPAD chlorophyll meter reading; TSW= Weight of 1000 seeds (g).

K=6

Appendix 27 Population structure analysis of 140 fonio at K= 6.

Each bar plot on the X-axis represents an individual fonio accession. The Y-axis shows the ancestry proportions of the individuals. Membership coefficient was set at ≥ 0.7

Appendix 28 Contingency table of genetic and morphological clusters

Genetic groups	Morphological clusters		
	Cluster A	Cluster B	Cluster C
Group 1	0	0	3
Group 2	0	1	0
Group 3	4	13	2
Group 4	3	18	2
Group 5	1	1	4
Group 6	4	4	1

The numbers indicate the number of fonio accessions belonging to the morphological clusters or genetic groups

Appendix 29 Map of northern Ghana showing the trial locations

The trials were conducted in Nyankpala (Tolon district), Challam (Savelugu municipal), Tinguri (West Mamprusi municipal), Ageadone (Talensi district) and Manga (Binduri district)

Appendix 30 Fonio evaluation trial at Challam, Savelugu Municipal, 2023

Appendix 31 Fonio evaluation trial at Nyankpala, Tolon District, 2023

Appendix 32 Growth and yield performance of 20 fonio genotypes at Ageadone

Genotype	Code	PH	SCMR	DFF	FLL	FLW	NRP	RL	NSR	GY	TSW
C031702	G1	89.50	36.10	70.00	8.99	0.39	4.09 (2.01)	9.60	93.30 (9.64)	526.00	0.44
C031703	G2	81.20	39.70	71.30	7.45	0.33	3.87 (1.97)	7.93	81.00 (8.95)	509.00	0.36
C060801	G3	101.20	38.90	76.00	9.91	0.42	4.98 (2.23)	11.09	113.90 (10.68)	330.00	0.49
C080101	G4	92.60	34.90	75.00	8.58	0.37	4.95 (2.22)	9.27	94.30 (9.73)	451.00	0.47
S010101	G5	84.90	36.90	73.70	9.49	0.39	3.87 (1.97)	12.29	160.00 (12.64)	522.00	0.42
S040101	G6	93.40	40.50	73.70	9.73	0.39	4.55 (2.13)	11.99	134.60 (11.66)	597.00	0.49
S080301	G7	73.90	39.80	73.70	6.95	0.33	3.87 (1.96)	8.35	75.30 (8.60)	318.00	0.52
<i>Wagadoga</i>	G8	82.60	44.80	70.00	7.66	0.33	3.91 (1.98)	9.55	106.70 (10.25)	320.00	0.60
Z010601	G9	91.80	38.00	82.00	10.56	0.41	4.05 (2.02)	10.65	118.90 (10.92)	303.00	0.54
Z020102	G10	92.50	34.00	70.00	10.64	0.40	4.87 (2.21)	10.12	100.10 (9.99)	310.00	0.46
C031701	G11	86.70	33.80	91.00	6.47	0.38	3.89 (1.97)	11.91	138.30 (11.79)	506.00	0.58
C070301	G12	94.80	33.30	99.00	5.95	0.32	4.45 (2.11)	12.40	139.00 (11.81)	577.00	0.50
C070402	G13	92.50	36.70	103.00	7.61	0.38	4.24 (2.05)	12.73	156.90 (12.61)	404.00	0.52
<i>Nfonikpa</i>	G14	82.80	35.70	91.00	6.98	0.38	3.98 (2.00)	12.01	118.60 (10.77)	642.00	0.51
S040401	G15	90.00	37.90	91.00	7.19	0.38	3.89 (1.97)	11.67	128.20 (11.28)	592.00	0.49
S050102	G16	86.10	36.10	91.00	6.75	0.36	4.21 (2.04)	11.16	110.60 (10.54)	653.00	0.48
S080302	G17	90.60	36.40	93.70	5.88	0.33	3.80 (1.94)	11.63	137.60 (11.61)	456.00	0.50
S080401	G18	92.30	40.10	96.30	7.14	0.37	4.42 (2.10)	11.56	143.00 (11.96)	352.00	0.44
Z010701	G19	106.90	35.40	111.00	7.96	0.38	3.89 (1.97)	13.52	141.10 (11.79)	345.00	0.48
Z020101	G20	106.00	33.20	107.00	7.84	0.37	4.13 (2.03)	12.66	125.90 (11.20)	410.00	0.52
Mean		90.61	37.11	85.47	7.99	0.37	4.20 (2.04)	11.10	120.87 (10.92)	456.15	0.49
SE		3.27	2.69	4.11	0.64	0.03	0.33 (0.06)	0.49	10.44 (0.48)	97.01	0.05
p-value		***	ns	***	***	ns	ns	***	***	***	ns

PH= plant height (cm); SCMR= SPAD chlorophyll meter reading; DFF= days to 50% flowering; FLL= flag leaf length (cm); FLW= flag leaf width (cm); NRP= number of racemes per panicle; RL= raceme length (cm); NSR= number of seeds per raceme; GY= grain yield (kg/ha); TSW= thousand seed weight (g). Means in parentheses were transformed using square root transformation.

Appendix 33 Growth and yield performance of 20 fonio genotypes at Challam

Genotype	Code	PH	SCMR	DFF	FLL	FLW	NRP	RL	NSR	GY	TSW
C031702	G1	79.10	39.00	69.60	7.81	0.34	4.00 (2.00)	11.45	119.40 (11.00)	511.00	0.63
C031703	G2	60.00	41.10	61.10	5.26	0.31	3.22 (1.79)	8.78	82.80 (9.07)	230.00	0.56
C060801	G3	86.30	34.50	73.40	8.41	0.37	3.44 (1.86)	10.89	114.40 (10.58)	467.00	0.66
C080101	G4	74.00	35.70	67.90	7.36	0.35	3.78 (1.94)	9.91	103.00 (10.02)	441.00	0.45
S010101	G5	72.70	34.80	77.90	7.74	0.34	3.56 (1.88)	11.76	128.20 (11.33)	622.00	0.68
S040101	G6	78.60	32.30	71.80	7.50	0.32	4.00 (2.00)	10.21	115.40 (10.76)	819.00	0.49
S080301	G7	60.70	41.20	59.30	6.43	0.30	3.11 (1.76)	9.04	88.50 (9.36)	225.00	0.56
<i>Wagadoga</i>	G8	62.20	37.00	60.90	6.09	0.32	2.89 (1.70)	9.94	96.40 (9.70)	355.00	0.58
Z010601	G9	80.50	35.70	72.90	9.01	0.41	3.22 (1.79)	11.29	107.10 (10.40)	458.00	0.64
Z020102	G10	77.90	34.50	71.90	7.81	0.36	3.67 (1.91)	10.57	107.30 (10.30)	602.00	0.61
C031701	G11	73.70	33.50	90.00	6.65	0.33	3.00 (1.73)	10.89	117.90 (10.90)	553.00	0.57
C070301	G12	80.70	30.70	95.30	7.92	0.34	4.11 (2.03)	12.00	144.00 (12.06)	792.00	0.41
C070402	G13	75.70	27.50	90.60	7.12	0.31	4.11 (2.02)	11.02	152.20 (12.32)	867.00	0.54
<i>Nfonikpa</i>	G14	79.40	29.90	93.60	8.74	0.41	3.56 (1.89)	11.92	155.60 (12.38)	499.00	0.53
S040401	G15	77.50	31.70	91.60	7.72	0.39	3.78 (1.94)	11.73	134.70 (11.64)	567.00	0.52
S050102	G16	76.00	33.50	88.20	7.98	0.36	4.44 (2.11)	11.38	132.60 (11.47)	421.00	0.50
S080302	G17	77.40	29.90	93.90	6.74	0.32	3.44 (1.85)	12.36	164.70 (12.78)	522.00	0.49
S080401	G18	75.00	30.30	92.60	7.46	0.35	4.11 (2.02)	12.05	156.10 (12.50)	678.00	0.51
Z010701	G19	88.90	31.50	104.50	9.03	0.42	3.78 (1.94)	13.20	161.70 (12.63)	200.00	0.48
Z020101	G20	79.80	28.90	106.20	9.89	0.36	3.67 (1.91)	12.53	157.80 (12.54)	183.00	0.51
Mean		75.81	33.66	81.66	7.63	0.35	3.64 (1.90)	11.15	126.99 (11.19)	500.60	0.55
SE		3.83	2.75	2.88	0.80	0.03	0.29 (0.06)	0.68	12.52 (0.47)	96.92	0.05
p-value		***	*	***	*	ns	*	*	***	***	*

PH= plant height (cm); SCMR= SPAD chlorophyll meter reading; DFF= days to 50% flowering; FLL= flag leaf length (cm); FLW= flag leaf width (cm); NRP= number of racemes per panicle; RL= raceme length (cm); NSR= number of seeds per raceme; GY= grain yield (kg/ha); TSW= thousand seed weight (g). Means in parentheses were transformed using square root transformation.

Appendix 34 Growth and yield performance of 20 fonio genotypes at Manga

Genotype	Code	PH	SCMR	DFF	FLL	FLW	NRP	RL	NSR	GY	TSW
C031702	G1	90.10	31.70	71.00	7.88	0.33	3.54 (1.88)	9.77	90.90 (9.52)	839.00	0.51
C031703	G2	76.00	33.80	60.00	6.63	0.31	3.23 (1.79)	9.22	77.70 (8.76)	475.00	0.52
C060801	G3	75.40	28.10	73.00	7.36	0.30	3.88 (1.97)	10.52	95.60 (9.79)	673.00	0.56
C080101	G4	80.00	34.30	76.00	7.22	0.32	4.13 (2.03)	10.82	106.30 (10.32)	788.00	0.54
S010101	G5	76.50	29.60	79.00	8.48	0.33	3.61 (1.90)	10.79	120.50 (10.95)	689.00	0.50
S040101	G6	77.70	28.50	78.00	7.32	0.31	3.86 (1.97)	10.27	111.90 (10.57)	663.00	0.63
S080301	G7	68.10	35.50	66.00	6.04	0.23	3.38 (1.83)	7.85	73.80 (8.56)	294.00	0.63
<i>Wagadoga</i>	G8	74.30	32.00	67.00	6.75	0.32	3.31 (1.82)	9.94	103.90 (10.05)	415.00	0.60
Z010601	G9	90.30	33.20	73.00	8.21	0.33	3.85 (1.97)	10.38	101.20 (10.07)	770.00	0.49
Z020102	G10	90.00	30.30	78.00	8.91	0.38	4.04 (2.01)	10.57	100.20 (9.93)	657.00	0.51
C031701	G11	76.90	32.50	87.00	4.99	0.31	3.24 (1.79)	12.72	134.90 (11.57)	537.00	0.53
C070301	G12	76.50	33.40	94.00	5.73	0.36	3.77 (1.94)	11.68	123.80 (11.06)	519.00	0.52
C070402	G13	75.80	34.70	93.00	5.55	0.34	3.45 (1.85)	10.25	128.90 (11.38)	682.00	0.58
<i>Nfonikpa</i>	G14	78.70	30.90	90.00	4.81	0.35	3.90 (1.97)	10.66	122.80 (11.06)	395.00	0.50
S040401	G15	71.70	31.30	88.00	5.92	0.34	3.78 (1.94)	12.34	144.50 (12.01)	593.00	0.51
S050102	G16	74.00	33.50	85.00	5.05	0.33	3.55 (1.89)	12.13	139.40 (11.79)	284.00	0.58
S080302	G17	77.80	32.90	90.00	5.65	0.34	4.23 (2.05)	11.79	133.90 (11.60)	574.00	0.53
S080401	G18	77.00	32.90	95.00	5.59	0.36	3.87 (1.97)	10.73	121.30 (10.93)	692.00	0.49
Z010701	G19	88.50	31.10	95.00	6.39	0.37	3.23 (1.79)	11.16	115.50 (10.70)	272.00	0.47
Z020101	G20	84.60	32.60	98.00	5.84	0.33	4.10 (2.03)	11.62	140.60 (11.86)	531.00	0.52
Mean		78.9	32.14	81.74	6.52	0.33	3.70 (1.92)	10.76	114.38 (10.64)	567.10	0.53
SE		4.55	2.28	2.97	0.62	0.02	0.20 (0.06)	0.72	11.48 (0.46)	97.06	0.04
p-value		*	ns	***	**	ns	**	**	***	*	ns

PH= plant height (cm); SCMR= SPAD chlorophyll meter reading; DFF= days to 50% flowering; FLL= flag leaf length (cm); FLW= flag leaf width (cm); NRP= number of racemes per panicle; RL= raceme length (cm); NSR= number of seeds per raceme; GY= grain yield (kg/ha); TSW= thousand seed weight (g). Means in parentheses were transformed using square root transformation.

Appendix 35 Growth and yield performance of 20 fonio genotypes at Nyankpala

Genotype	Code	PH	SCMR	DFE	FLL	FLW	NRP	RL	NSR	GY	TSW
C031702	G1	70.10	30.10	77.30	5.88	0.32	3.02 (1.73)	9.77	106.90 (10.32)	663.00	0.57
C031703	G2	61.20	30.00	63.30	5.13	0.34	2.56 (1.59)	10.52	104.30 (10.22)	343.00	0.58
C060801	G3	67.90	37.10	76.30	5.37	0.33	2.78 (1.66)	10.48	95.50 (9.76)	481.00	0.46
C080101	G4	67.10	35.30	68.00	5.38	0.34	3.36 (1.82)	11.18	107.50 (10.37)	444.00	0.66
S010101	G5	74.60	31.40	81.30	5.78	0.31	3.36 (1.83)	11.42	108.40 (10.39)	553.00	0.58
S040101	G6	73.50	31.80	72.30	5.02	0.31	3.20 (1.79)	10.18	101.00 (10.04)	677.00	0.49
S080301	G7	61.30	34.90	61.30	4.08	0.29	2.86 (1.70)	8.92	87.60 (9.34)	316.00	0.41
<i>Wagadoga</i>	G8	70.60	30.40	61.70	4.93	0.30	2.67 (1.63)	9.78	91.70 (9.56)	537.00	0.89
Z010601	G9	72.10	34.10	79.30	4.79	0.29	3.67 (1.91)	10.59	110.00 (10.47)	481.00	0.57
Z020102	G10	76.60	33.10	75.70	6.59	0.35	3.19 (1.79)	11.11	110.00 (10.47)	443.00	0.67
C031701	G11	76.30	34.60	86.30	6.60	0.37	3.88 (1.97)	11.47	141.60 (11.89)	849.00	0.53
C070301	G12	76.80	30.90	95.00	9.52	0.42	4.35 (2.08)	12.11	155.20 (12.45)	813.00	0.48
C070402	G13	85.00	28.20	89.70	8.51	0.35	3.65 (1.91)	12.23	153.20 (12.36)	1053.00	0.53
<i>Nfonikpa</i>	G14	83.00	26.90	87.30	7.04	0.34	3.99 (2.00)	10.53	138.00 (11.72)	984.00	0.55
S040401	G15	78.80	37.40	90.30	7.74	0.35	3.79 (1.94)	11.52	141.90 (11.90)	684.00	0.52
S050102	G16	83.50	33.20	91.00	7.85	0.38	4.12 (2.03)	12.35	145.10 (12.02)	870.00	0.53
S080302	G17	79.40	28.10	93.00	7.28	0.35	3.64 (1.91)	12.10	141.60 (11.89)	866.00	0.53
S080401	G18	78.10	33.40	92.30	6.67	0.31	4.12 (2.03)	11.79	135.90 (11.62)	1009.00	0.55
Z010701	G19	99.80	28.80	101.00	8.52	0.34	3.54 (1.88)	12.85	149.20 (12.21)	717.00	0.54
Z020101	G20	91.90	29.90	102.00	8.28	0.34	3.91 (1.97)	13.55	141.70 (11.90)	790.00	0.48
Mean		76.38	31.98	82.22	6.55	0.34	3.48 (1.86)	11.22	123.32 (11.05)	678.65	0.56
SE		4.21	3.13	1.80	0.48	0.02	0.21 (0.06)	0.46	8.81 (0.46)	96.91	0.08
p-value		***	ns	***	***	*	***	***	***	**	ns

PH= plant height (cm); SCMR= SPAD chlorophyll meter reading; DFF= days to 50% flowering; FLL= flag leaf length (cm); FLW= flag leaf width (cm); NRP= number of racemes per panicle; RL= raceme length (cm); NSR= number of seeds per raceme; GY= grain yield (kg/ha); TSW= thousand seed weight (g). Means in parentheses were transformed using square root transformation.

Appendix 36 Growth and yield performance of 20 fonio genotypes at Tinguri

Genotype	Code	PH	SCMR	DFE	FLL	FLW	NRP	RL	NSR	GY	TSW
C031702	G1	81.70	33.10	75.90	8.08	0.36	3.50 (1.87)	10.82	106.30 (10.29)	401.00	0.58
C031703	G2	67.90	43.60	63.60	6.53	0.27	2.89 (1.70)	9.57	92.60 (9.53)	445.00	0.54
C060801	G3	83.80	32.50	74.70	8.23	0.39	3.11 (1.76)	11.31	120.60 (10.96)	556.00	0.47
C080101	G4	79.80	38.30	76.00	6.85	0.34	3.56 (1.88)	12.24	109.20 (10.44)	464.00	0.57
S010101	G5	77.50	32.50	87.40	7.68	0.34	3.44 (1.86)	12.68	155.90 (12.42)	825.00	0.56
S040101	G6	68.70	37.80	88.30	9.10	0.44	3.61 (1.90)	11.54	131.90 (11.58)	678.00	0.60
S080301	G7	68.80	44.00	58.40	6.92	0.33	3.00 (1.73)	9.51	72.90 (8.60)	266.00	0.52
<i>Wagadoga</i>	G8	62.30	42.90	64.70	6.30	0.27	2.78 (1.67)	10.28	98.00 (9.90)	327.00	0.59
Z010601	G9	85.30	39.00	73.70	7.70	0.33	3.44 (1.85)	12.38	124.10 (11.16)	489.00	0.48
Z020102	G10	82.90	34.80	82.70	8.18	0.36	3.44 (1.85)	12.02	116.80 (10.67)	626.00	0.71
C031701	G11	80.90	32.90	92.30	5.81	0.37	4.22 (2.05)	12.16	132.70 (11.56)	784.00	0.53
C070301	G12	83.10	33.50	96.10	5.99	0.32	4.67 (2.16)	12.19	137.80 (11.72)	836.00	0.49
C070402	G13	80.90	35.20	95.20	7.65	0.38	4.11 (2.03)	13.17	158.20 (12.64)	908.00	0.46
<i>Nfonikpa</i>	G14	79.40	36.20	93.00	7.87	0.40	4.56 (2.13)	12.28	142.90 (11.85)	496.00	0.63
S040401	G15	82.30	36.20	91.60	6.80	0.35	4.00 (2.00)	12.40	133.20 (11.43)	747.00	0.48
S050102	G16	79.50	35.00	91.30	6.86	0.39	4.44 (2.11)	12.62	141.10 (11.80)	572.00	0.45
S080302	G17	79.50	37.30	97.90	6.84	0.35	4.22 (2.05)	12.67	148.40 (12.19)	669.00	0.39
S080401	G18	85.10	34.90	94.30	7.02	0.35	4.33 (2.08)	11.68	143.60 (12.03)	861.00	0.46
Z010701	G19	93.20	32.70	104.00	7.20	0.35	4.11 (2.02)	13.09	139.00 (11.81)	444.00	0.49
Z020101	G20	91.50	32.60	104.70	8.41	0.39	3.67 (1.91)	12.87	136.70 (11.67)	629.00	0.51
Mean		79.71	36.25	85.29	7.30	0.35	3.76 (1.93)	11.87	127.10 (11.21)	601.15	0.53
SE		17.46	2.45	1.85	0.72	0.02	0.21 (0.06)	0.49	10.66 (0.47)	97.12	0.06
p-value		ns	**	***	ns	***	***	***	***	***	ns

PH= plant height (cm); SCMR= SPAD chlorophyll meter reading; DFE= days to 50% flowering; FLL= flag leaf length (cm); FLW= flag leaf width (cm); NRP= number of racemes per panicle; RL= raceme length (cm); NSR= number of seeds per raceme; GY= grain yield (kg/ha); TSW= thousand seed weight (g). Means in parentheses were transformed using square root transformation.